

The Impact of Melanocortin Receptor Ligands on Astrocyte Signalling and Metabolism

Submitted by

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Abstract

Melanocortin peptides, which act on melanocortin receptors (MCRs), play multifaceted roles in the body through various tissues and mechanisms that regulate physiological functions. MCRs, comprising a family of five subtypes (MC1R to MC5R), are 7 transmembrane receptors that can couple with G proteins or function independently of them. These receptors are present in the central nervous system (CNS) and other body tissues. This thesis concentrates on the role of MCRs within the CNS and explores their functional role in astrocytes.

Astrocytes, once underestimated glial cells, are now recognised as crucial contributors to brain function. Although considered non-excitabile cells, they increase their intracellular calcium ion levels in response to a stimulus or signalling event. They maintain brain homeostasis through the regulation of diverse cellular signals, extracellular potassium ion buffering, and metabolic activities. While MC3R and MC4R were initially considered the main MCR subtypes expressed in CNS neurons, recent evidence suggests that other MCR subtypes may also be present, although their expression and function in astrocytes remain poorly defined.

This thesis addresses this gap by investigating the expression of all MCRs and the impact of pharmacological modulation on astrocytic signalling pathways, ion dynamics and metabolism. It explores how melanocortin peptides influence metabolic functions in astrocytes, particularly focusing on mitochondrial and glycolytic activity, ERK1/2, PKA and PLC signalling, and calcium and potassium ion flux, in these cells. Through experimental approaches including RT-PCR, immunoblotting, real-time fluorescence imaging, cell bioenergetics and metabolic assays, this work provides new insights into the complex interplay between melanocortin signalling, metabolic and ion changes in astrocytic function. The findings enhance our understanding of how MCRs contribute to brain homeostasis and highlight their potential as therapeutic targets for metabolic and neurological disorders.

The overarching hypothesis of this thesis speculates that MCRs are expressed in astrocytes and exhibit functional signalling, alterations in potassium and calcium ion dynamics, and changes in metabolic activity in response to synthetic MCR ligands. This hypothesis was assessed in two cell models: neonatal mouse primary cortical astrocytes and the human astrogloma cell line U373.

The findings of this thesis indicate that MCRs are expressed in both cell models examined. Pharmacological modulation of MCRs led to increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation and enhanced cell metabolism in the human U373 astrogloma cell line, though no changes in intracellular calcium ion levels were observed. Melanocortin ligands did not alter ERK1/2 and PKA signalling, and calcium ion influx in mouse primary astrocytes. Despite exploration, melanocortin ligand induced modulation of potassium channels in U373 cells remains unclear. In conclusion, MCRs were found to be present on astrocytes and showed active signalling via ERK1/2 in U373 cells following treatment with melanocortin agonists, leading (directly or indirectly) to the regulation of cell metabolism. MCRs on astrocytes may play a significant role in maintaining brain/systemic homeostasis and may be a therapeutic target for mitigating pathological disorders. Although this thesis does not focus on a disease model, the data generated from this thesis supports further investigation of astrocyte melanocortin signalling in the context of pathophysiology.

Authors declaration

All work presented in this thesis was conducted at the University of Exeter RILD laboratories or BSU by the author, Asmaa Al-khalidi, apart from the following:

Neonatal primary cell isolation and cell culture: Performed by Dr Wyn Firth and Katherine Pye on some occasions where I was unable to.

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Mouse brain tissue sonication: Performed by Dr Nicole Morrisey

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
2-DG	2-deoxy-6-glucose
3-NP	3-nitropropionic acid
AC	Adenylyl cyclase
ACBP	Acyl-CoA-binding protein
Acetyl-CoA	Acetyl-coenzyme A
ACTH	Adrenocorticotropin
AGRP	Agouti-related protein
ALDH1L1	Aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1
AM	Acetoxymethyl
AMPK	AMP-activated protein kinase
α -MSH	Alpha-melanocyte-stimulating hormone
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
APS	Ammonium persulfate
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
ATP	Adenosine nucleotide transporter
B-MSH	Beta-melanocyte stimulating hormone
BBB	Blood-brain barrier
BDNF	Brain-derived neurotrophic factor
BSA	Bovine serum albumin
Ca ²⁺	Calcium ions
cDNA	Complementary deoxyribose nucleotide
cAMP	Cyclic adenosine monophosphate
CCKAR/CCKBR	Cholecystokinin A and B receptor
cFOS	Proto-oncogene
CLIP	Corticotropin-like intermediate peptide
CNS	Central nervous system
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CREB	cAMP-response element binding protein
DAG	Diacylglycerol

DAPI	4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole
DAPI	4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole fluorescent stain
ddH ₂ O	Double distilled water
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DNA	Deoxyribose nucleotide
EC ₅₀	Half maximal effective concentration
ECACC	European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures
ECAR	Extracellular acidification rate
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EPAC	Exchange proteins activated by cyclic AMP
ER	Endoplasmic reticulum
ERK1/2	Extracellular signal-regulated kinase
ETC	Electron transport chain
FACS	Fluorescence-activated cell sorting
FBS	Fetal bovine serum
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FSC	Forward side scatter
FCCP	Carbonyl cyanide p-trifluoro methoxyphenylhydrazone
γ-MSH	Gamma-melanocyte stimulating hormone
G3P	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate
GAPDH	Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase
GBM	Glioblastoma
GFAP	Glial fibrillary acidic protein
GHSR	Growth hormone secretagogue receptor
GLUT1	Glucose transporter 1
GPCR	G protein coupled receptor
GST	Glycolysis stress test
GT1-1 + GT1-7	Immortalised mouse hypothalamic neuronal cell line
Gai	G protein (inhibitory)
Gaq	G protein (stimulatory)
HBSS	Hanks balance salted solution
HEK293	Human Embryonic Kidney Cells

HEPES	4-(2-Hydroxyethyl) piperazine-1-ethane-sulfonic acid
HPA	Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal
IBA1	Ionized calcium binding adapter protein 1
IC50	Half-maximal inhibitory concentration
iCa ²⁺	Intracellular calcium
ICAM-1	Intercellular adhesion molecule 1
ICC	Immunocytochemistry
IP3	Inositol trisphosphate
IP3R	Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate receptor
Kb	Kilobase
kDa	Kilo Dalton
K ⁺	Potassium ion
LEPR	Leptin Receptor
L	Ladder
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
MAPK	Mitogen-activated protein kinase
MC1R – MC5R	Melanocortin 1 – 5 receptors
MCRS	Melanocortin receptors
MPTP	1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine
MSH	Melanocyte stimulating hormone
MST	Mitochondrial stress test
MTII	Melanotan II
mTOR	Mammalian target of rapamycin
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
NaVO ₄	Sodium orthovanadate
N-POMC	NH ₂ -terminal peptide POMC
NDP-MSH	Nle,D-Phe-melanocyte stimulating hormone
NDRG2	N-myc downregulated gene 2
NAD ⁺	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide
NADH	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide hydrogen
nM	Nano molar
NDS	Normal donkey serum

P	Passage
PBS	Phosphate buffered saline
PC1/3	Pro-hormone convertases 1/3
PC12	A rat cell line: pheochromocytoma
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PEP	Phosphoenolpyruvate
PGC1	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma coactivator
PI3K	Phosphoinositide-3 kinase
PIP2	Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate
PKA	Protein Kinase A
PKC	Protein kinase C
PLC	Protein lipase C
PLL	Poly-L-Lysine
PMSF	Phenylmethanesulfonyl fluoride
PNS	Peripheral nervous system
POMC	Pro-opiomelanocortin
PPAR- γ	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma
P-PKA	Phospho or phosphorylated protein kinase A
P-PLC	Phospho or phosphorylated protein lipase C
PRF	Phenol red-free
PVN	Paraventricular nucleus
PNS	Peripheral nervous system
PRF	Phenol red-free
qPCR	Quantitative PCR
RFU	Relative fluorescence units
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPM	Revolutions per minute
RSK	P90, ribosomal S6 kinase 2
RT	Room Temperature
RTKS	Receptor tyrosine kinases
RT-PCR	Reverse Transcriptase Polymerase Chain Reaction

Rot/A	Rotenone/antimycin
ROUT	Robust regression and outlier removal
S100 β	S100 calcium-binding protein B
SCC	Side scatter
SDS	Sodium dodecyl sulphate
SDS-PAGE	Sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
SHU9119	MCR inhibitor
SIRT1 α	Silencing information regulator 2 related enzyme 1
STR	Short Tandem Repeat
TAE buffer	Tris acetate EDTA
TBST	Tris-buffered saline with 0.1% Tween® 20 detergent
TCA	Krebs cycle / Tricarboxylic acid cycle
TEMED	Tetramethylethylenediamine
Thr197	Therosine 197
TI	Thallium sulphate
TNF- α	Tumour necrosis factor
TMRE	Tetramethylrhodamine ethyl ester
TrkB	Tropomyosin receptor kinase B
V	volts
v/v	Volume to volume

1 INTRODUCTION

This thesis focuses on understanding the impact of melanocortin peptides acting on melanocortin receptors (MCRs) on astrocytes in the brain. The physiological roles of this family of receptors and their ligands are complex. Ever-growing evidence over the years has demonstrated that melanocortin peptides and their receptors participate in physiology and pathophysiology.

1.1 Overview of brain composition

The brain is a highly complex organ consisting of a network of neurons and glial cells, which work together to maintain neural functions within the central nervous system (CNS). Neurons are responsible for transmitting electrical signals throughout the brain, enabling various functions, including motor control, cognition, and sensory processing. The glial cells, which include astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, and microglia, play essential roles in supporting and modulating neuronal activity.

1.1.1 Glial cells and their roles

Astrocytes, also known as astroglia, are non-neuronal cells that regulate the wider central nervous system environment (CNS) (Verkhratsky & Nedergaard, 2018). Astrocytes, once considered passive support cells, are now recognised as active participants in brain physiology. They regulate neurotransmitter uptake, control the extracellular environment, maintain ion balance, and modulate synaptic transmission. They also play critical roles in brain metabolism by providing energy substrates to neurons and maintaining the blood-brain barrier (Verkhratsky & Nedergaard, 2018).

Oligodendrocytes, are cells responsible for producing myelin sheaths that insulate axons, enabling faster signal transmission across neural networks (Kalafatakis & Karagogeos, 2021). Damage to oligodendrocytes is associated with neurodegenerative diseases like multiple sclerosis. Microglia, the brain's immune cells, monitor the brain for injury and infection (Kalafatakis &

Karagogeos, 2021). They act as the first line of defence, clearing debris and protecting neurons from potential threats through inflammatory responses.

1.1.2 Neural networks and glial contributions

The interaction between neurons and glial cells is essential for maintaining neural networks. Astrocytes are key regulators of synaptic function, helping to balance excitatory and inhibitory signals. They engage in bidirectional communication with neurons, responding to synaptic activity by releasing gliotransmitters, which modulate neuronal communication and network excitability (Achour & Pascual, 2012; Noriega-Prieto & Araque, 2021; Perea et al., 2009). This intricate crosstalk is vital for normal brain functioning and adaptability. Next, I will introduce astrocytes in more context and how they contribute to the CNS and whole-body physiology. Then, I will introduce how astrocytes support neuronal function and the wider CNS and describe astrocytic cell metabolism

1.2 Astrocytes as regulators of the central nervous system

Astrocytes, long regarded as primarily supportive cells in the CNS, are now acknowledged for their dynamic and multifaceted roles in regulating neuronal activity, synaptic transmission, and overall brain homeostasis (Montgomery, 1994; Verkhratsky & Nedergaard, 2018). They are essential cells in a variety of physiological and pathophysiological conditions. Their complex structure and diversity within the brain allow them to contribute to maintaining the blood-brain barrier (BBB, which regulates the extracellular environment by preventing the entry of harmful substances into the brain), the extracellular ion environment and modulating immune responses (Manu et al., 2023). Astrocytes are characterised by their star-shaped morphology; however, given their complexity, astrocytes display diverse morphological and functional features depending on the brain circuitry they surround. Due to their abundance and heterogeneity, they possess distinct structural and functional features in different brain regions. Astrocytes are histologically identified in the brain through the expression of the cytoskeleton filaments glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) and/or vimentin, N-myc downregulated gene 2 (NDRG2), or the metabolic enzyme aldehyde

dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1), and S100 calcium-binding protein B (S100 β) (Flügge et al., 2014; Jurga et al., 2021; O’Leary et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019). Depending on the brain region, the expression of these astrocytic markers is varied. The astrocyte population is composed of fibrous astrocytes and protoplasmic astrocytes, where the fibrous astrocytes use their projections to communicate with nodes of Ranvier (small gaps in the myelin sheath surrounding axons of neurons in the peripheral nervous system (PNS) and CNS).

In comparison, protoplasmic astrocytes use their projections to enclose neuronal synapses. There are differences in mature astrocytes compared with immature astrocytes, representing distinct stages of astrocytic development and functionality. Mature astrocytes that are fully differentiated tend to have a well-defined morphology and support CNS physiology in conjunction with other glial cells in the brain. In contrast, immature astrocytes are still developing with limited functionality. *In-vivo* and *in-vitro* studies confirm that astrocytes are among the primary CNS responders to physiological and pathophysiological conditions because of their diverse forms and functions. Whilst “normal” astrocytes support the CNS, astrocytes can become reactive in response to injury or disease to return the brain to normal homeostasis. Reactive astrocytes change their function, morphology, and molecular responses, which can contribute to pathophysiology when persistent.

While astrocytes are vital, ranking them more critical than other brain cells is challenging. They are crucial for many aspects of brain function and health, yet they are part of a broader system of glial cells, each contributing in essential ways. The nervous system relies on the integrated functions of all glial cells, as described in **sections 1.1.1** and **1.1.2**. For example, without oligodendrocytes, neurons could not efficiently transmit signals. Without microglia, the brain would be vulnerable to infections and incapable of clearing debris. Without ependymal cells, cerebrospinal fluid dynamics would be disrupted. The importance of astrocytes should be viewed in the context of the collective functions of all glial cells in maintaining a healthy and functional nervous system.

1.2.1 Regulation of physiology and neuronal function

Astrocytes have a multifaceted role in regulating energy and neuronal function through various mechanisms. Astrocytes communicate with neurons, a process known as gliotransmission, by producing and secreting signalling molecules such as ATP, D-serine, and others to biochemically signal and communicate with neurons. They also regulate the concentration of neurotransmitters such as glutamate and GABA in the synaptic cleft and remove excess neurotransmitters to prevent excitotoxicity (Noriega-Prieto & Araque, 2021). This bidirectional activity influences neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission, making astrocytes play key roles in synaptic plasticity. Astrocytes provide metabolic support to neurons and play a vital role in the brain's energy metabolism. This includes giving energetic substrates to neurons to help maintain cellular energy homeostasis and meet the high energetic demands of neuronal activity. Beyond this, astrocytes participate in the tissue response to brain injury and inflammation, providing neuroprotective properties and increasing tissue repair. Although astrocytes were deemed as the glue of the brain for many years, they are now understood as cells that play essential roles in the brain to maintain physiological environments, highlighting their significance in normal brain function, neurological disorders, and other pathophysiological conditions.

1.2.1.1 Receptors expressed by astrocytes

Central to astrocytes dynamic and multifaceted roles in regulating neuronal activity, synaptic transmission, and overall brain homeostasis is the expression of various receptors on their surface, allowing them to respond to a wide array of signalling molecules within the CNS microenvironment, including neuroendocrine hormones, such as melanocortin peptides, and peripheral hormones. Receptor expression in astrocytes encompasses a diverse range of receptor types, including neurotransmitter receptors, G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs), cytokine receptors, growth factor receptors, and many others. This complex network of receptors enables astrocytes to sense and integrate signals from neurons, other glial cells, and extracellular molecules, thus influencing neuronal function and CNS physiology. As mentioned earlier, among the GPCR receptors astrocytes express melanocortin receptors (MCRs)

one to five (MC1R to MC5R), a family of GPCRs. The role of melanocortin peptides and their receptors, MCRs, will be introduced next in the introduction.

1.3 Melanocortin ligands and receptors

Melanocortin receptors (MCRs) are GPCRs. Their endogenous melanocortin ligands, including α -melanocyte stimulating hormone (α -MSH) and adrenocorticotropin hormone (ACTH), act on these receptors. Five subtypes of MCRs (MC1R to MC5R) are expressed across different tissues, including the central nervous system (CNS), and have been implicated in a variety of physiological processes, such as energy homeostasis, metabolism, immune modulation, and inflammation. Next, I will outline what melanocortin peptides are and their origin, then I will introduce MCRs in more depth.

1.4 Endogenous melanocortin peptides

Melanocortin peptides are derived from the precursor peptide pro-opiomelanocortin (POMC) following proteolytic cleavage (Bertagna, 1994; Cone, 2006). **Figure 1.4.1-1** outlines a simplified schematic of how POMC processing results in melanocortin peptides in the brain and pituitary (Harno et al., 2018). The melanocortins are conserved regulatory peptides with numerous properties, including anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects in the brain and body (Cai & Hruby, 2016). The endogenous melanocortin peptide agonists adrenocorticotropin (ACTH) and the melanocyte-stimulating hormones (MSH) α -MSH, β -MSH and γ -MSH bind with varying affinity to all melanocortin receptors (MCRs), except ACTH which only binds to the melanocortin 2 receptor (MC2R) (Cone, 2006; Laiho & Murray, 2022). The endogenous melanocortin receptor antagonists are agouti and agouti-related peptide (AGRP). Agouti and AGRP have distinct functions; agouti is produced in the skin, regulating skin pigmentation via an action at the melanocortin 1 receptor (MC1R), while AGRP is found in neurons of the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus within the brain, where it acts via melanocortin 3 and 4 receptors (MC3R and MC4R) to regulate energy balance (Ollmann et al., 1997).

The endogenous melanocortin antagonists and agonists, as well as the synthetic ligands are biased and complex in their function; the endogenous antagonists also have dual functions such as biased agonist activity, activating different signalling profiles, and can also act as inverse agonists to decrease constitutive basal levels of MCR activity (Breit et al., 2006; Büch et al., 2009; Haskell-Luevano & Monck, 2001; Mo & Tao, 2013; Nijenhuis et al., 2001; Tao et al., 2010; Yang & Tao, 2017). The MCRs have diverse G protein coupling and signalling pathways with intertwining molecular mechanisms that remain poorly understood (Breit et al., 2011; Chaturvedi & Shukla, 2020; Hammad et al., 2022; He & Tao, 2014; Lotta et al., 2019; Mo & Tao, 2013; Paisdzior et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2021). Calcium ions have been revealed as biased co-factors influencing signalling responses downstream of MCRs and are required to initiate ligand binding and signal transduction (Chaturvedi & Shukla, 2020; Heyder et al., 2021; Link et al., 2020; Salomon, 1990; J. Yu et al., 2020). α -MSH is the most studied melanocortin peptide; it corresponds to ACTH's first 13 amino acids, where it is N-terminally acetylated and C-terminally amidated. The final processing of these peptides, through acetylation and amidation, is essential for their active biological moieties (Glembotski, 1982; A. I. Smith & Funder, 1988). ACTH is the only peptide that binds MC2R (Schiöth et al., 1996). All MSH ligands contain a His-Phe-Arg-Trp core amino acid sequence required for receptor activity/stimulation (Castrucci et al., 1989; Hruby et al., 1987; Metz et al., 2006; Sahm et al., 1994; Yeo et al., 2021). Melanocortin peptides are synthesised and expressed in tissues of the periphery and in the central nervous system (CNS), where α -MSH is produced in POMC-expressing neurons in the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus and the nucleus of the solitary tract of the brain stem (Harno et al., 2018).

1.4.1 Synthetic melanocortin ligands

Besides the endogenous melanocortin peptides, many synthetic MCR ligands have been designed for therapeutic targeting in several clinical conditions (Durek et al., 2018; Falls & Zhang, 2019; Sharma et al., 2019; Yeo et al., 2021; Yuan & Tao, 2022). The synthetic ligands are typically designed to target a specific MCR subtype(s) but tend to have affinities for more than one MCR due to the similarities in receptor sequence homology (Yeo et al., 2021). The

synthetic ligands contain the sequence His-Phe-Arg-Trp that is conserved throughout evolution, making it difficult to develop highly selective ligands for each receptor subtype (Cai & Hruby, 2016). The synthetic agonists Melanotan II (MTII) and NDP-MSH have been most widely used to date for pre-clinical research purposes; however, recently newer and more specific, synthetic MC4R-specific agonists such as Setmelanotide and Bremelanotide have been developed and are now FDA approved to treat obesity clinically (Kamermans et al., 2019; Sweeney et al., 2023; Trapp & Censani, 2023; Yeo et al., 2021; J. Yu et al., 2020; Yuan & Tao, 2022).

The synthetic antagonist SHU9119 is widely used for research studies *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*, demonstrating inhibitory effects on MCR signalling. Although SHU9119 is considered an antagonist for MC3R and MC4R, it is also a partial agonist for MC1R and MC5R (Schiöth et al., 1999). Recently, a systematic mischaracterisation of pharmacological properties of melanocortin peptides was identified, explaining the partial agonism of SHU9119 at MC1R and MC5R and some weak partial agonism at MC3R and MC4R (Gimenez et al., 2022). **Table 1.4-1** and **Table 1.4-2** list reported binding affinities of endogenous and synthetic melanocortin ligands for rodent and human MCRs. MC2R is not included in the tables as MTII and Setmelanotide do not bind to MC2R; this is also true for endogenous agonists except for ACTH (Fridmanis et al., 2017). These binding affinities were sourced from other studies that can be summarised in a recent review paper (Yeo et al., 2021). More ligands and binding affinities can be found in this review paper (Yuan & Tao, 2022). Due to the high variability in reported affinities and potencies of different ligands at each MCR between studies, as well as differences in downstream canonical signalling, it is suggested that endogenous melanocortin ligand binding can occur at all MCRs except MC2R.

Consequently, different pharmacological responses may arise from a ligand binding to different MCRs. Furthermore, these receptors and/or associated proteins may interact with each other (Laiho & Murray, 2022). Due to the focus of this thesis being the effects of synthetic ligands MTII, Setmelanotide and SHU9119, other synthetic melanocortin receptor ligands have not been included in the description above.

Figure 1.4.1-1 Simplified schematic of pro-opiomelanocortin (POMC) processing

Two populations of cells in the brain differentially post-translationally process POMC to produce adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH), α -MSH, β -MSH and γ -MSH (Harno et al., 2018). POMC is sequentially cleaved by the pro-hormone convertases 1/3 (PC1/3), producing pro-adrenocorticotrophic hormone (PRO-ACTH). PRO-ACTH is further cleaved by PC2 to produce ACTH and corticotropin-like intermediate peptide (CLIP). Further processing occurs, producing des-acetyl α -MSH (DA- α -MSH), which is then further acetylated, making the product α -MSH. PC2 cleaves β -lipotropic hormone (β -LPH) to β -endorphin (β -end) and γ -lipotropic, which is further cleaved to β -MSH. Then, NH₂-terminal peptide POMC (N-POMC) is further cleaved by PC2, resulting in γ 3-melanocyte stimulating hormone (γ 3-MSH), which is finally processed into γ -MSH. The end products of this processing are the melanocyte-stimulating hormones shown in the grey boxes. The red on α -MSH indicates the acetylation, and the blue indicates amidation. Figure created using Biorender.

Table 1.4-1 Endogenous melanocortin peptide affinities acting for human and rodent melanocortin receptors

	Rodent receptors (nM)				Human receptors (nM)			
	<i>MC1R</i>	<i>MC3R</i>	<i>MC4R</i>	<i>MC5R</i>	<i>MC1R</i>	<i>MC3R</i>	<i>MC4R</i>	<i>MC5R</i>
α -MSH	3.68	6.67	9.17	62.5	0.0334	15.5	19	120
		9.4	61.2	80	0.092	19	26	150
		30.2			0.230	20.7	38.7	332
		52			0.321	21.2	41.4	557
					1.5	31.5	522	928
					3.9	46	641	7160
					5.97	50.04	900	8240
β -MSH		34.6	27.2	212	0.449	13.4	19.9	306
		19.4			0.864	15.1	76	1750
					1.17	23.2	387	14,40
					2.29	39.46	22.74	0
					0.89	10.64	8.18	301.5
							76.90	
γ -MSH		6.7		1270	11.2	17.7	770	2500
		44			20.8	57.2	6250	3250
						72	100,00	100,0
							0	0
Agouti	2.6	190	54	1200	23	112	12	>1000
						140	70	
							1.8	
AgRP		2.8	0.66			1.1	0.5	25.6
			3.0			4.5	3.5	>40
						11.2	9.0	
							24.7	

Where more than one binding affinity value is listed in the table, this reflects binding affinities determined by different studies and the diversity of the values obtained. All binding affinity values were taken from a recent review paper (Yeo et al., 2021).

Table 1.4-2 Synthetic melanocortin ligand binding affinities for human and rodent melanocortin receptors

	Rodent receptors (nM)				<i>Human receptors (nM)</i>			
	MC1R	MC3R	MC4R	MC5R	MC1R	MC3R	MC4R	MC5R
MTII	0.22	1.85	1.74	28.4	0.20	1.6	0.07	0.89
		4.77	6.22		0.268	3.1	0.18	1.2
		67.8	0.50		0.36	20	0.25	17
					0.686	34.1	1.5	23
					6.4	24.0	2.66	23.1
						52.6	6.60	46.1
Setmelanotide			2.7		5.5	10	2.1	430
					3.9	18	5.0	1910
SHU9119		0.879	0.238		0.62	0.23	0.06	0.065
		1.68	0.38		0.714	1.20	0.07	0.09
			0.583			1.65	0.360	1.12
							0.689	

Where more than one binding affinity is listed, this reflects the value determined from different studies. All binding affinity values were taken from a recent review paper (Yeo et al., 2021). Further details on binding affinities and other ligands for synthetic melanocortins can be found in the review paper (Yeo et al., 2021).

1.5 Expression and characterisation of MCRs

Most melanocortin peptides exert their effects via MCRs expressed on the surface of cells. MCRs are GPCRs with 297 to 323 amino acids (Mountjoy et al., 1992; Yang, 2011). GPCRs contain seven transmembrane α -helical domains spanning the cell membrane. MCRs consist of five subtypes: MC1R, MC2R, MC3R, MC4R, and MC5R, each encoded by distinct genes and exhibiting unique tissue distribution and function (Laiho & Murray, 2022; Tatro, 1990). MCRs were cloned and named in the order of their discovery back in the 1990s (Mountjoy et al., 1992; Gantz, Konda, et al., 1993; Gantz, Miwa, et al., 1993; Roselli-Rehfuss et al., 1993). MC3R/MC4R were believed to be the predominant subtypes expressed in the brain (Liu et al., 2003; Cone, 2005; Tao, 2010; You et al., 2016; Lotta et al., 2019); however, MC5R and MC1R are also found in the CNS having diverse effects and functions (Getting, 2006; Kamermans et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2021, 2022). Before the discovery of MCRs, numerous physiological effects of melanocortin-stimulating hormones (MSH) and ACTH had been documented since the 1950s, when they were first shown to influence animal behaviour (Ferrari, 1958). MCRs share significant sequence homology, reflecting their evolutionary relationship and functional similarities (Dores et al., 2014; Logan et al., 2003), but the receptor subtypes tend to have different diverse roles in the body (Getting, 2006; Yeo et al., 2021). MC4R has high homology levels with the other four MCRs and is similar between species (Caruso et al., 2013). Mouse and rat MC4R share 93% of their amino acid sequence and structure with human MC4R (Caruso et al., 2013). MC3R in mice and rats also share 93% amino acid homology (Desarnaud et al., 1994; Okutsu et al., 2015; Roselli-Rehfuss et al., 1993). Receptor activation is associated with a range of cellular responses that have crucial roles in a variety of physiological processes, including pigmentation, energy homeostasis, and inflammation (Butler & Cone, 2002; Chang et al., 2021; Yeo et al., 2021). They play diverse and critical roles in brain function, influencing various aspects of neurophysiology and behaviour.

The melanocortin peptides have overlapping MCR binding profiles in the brain and periphery (Cone, 2005). When agonists bind to MCRs, they can induce different conformation changes within receptors, which activate diverse

signalling pathways despite the same expression levels, coupling and response of the receptor (Chai et al., 2006, 2007, 2009; Newman et al., 2006; Yang, 2011). This may be due to the differences in binding pockets of MCRs where agonists can bind allosteric pockets or orthosteric ligand binding sites, inducing different conformation states and cellular responses [see review, (Yang, 2011; Yang & Harmon, 2017; Kleinau et al., 2020)]. Over the years, the complexity of MCR interactions have become more evident. Further structural studies emerged, leading to an enhanced understanding of where they are found and how ligand binding sites in MC1R, MC3R, MC4R, and MC5R influence their conformation, signalling, and activity (Falls & Zhang, 2019; Feng et al., 2023; Hammad et al., 2022; Heyder et al., 2021; Mun et al., 2023; Patten et al., 2007). Next, I will briefly introduce what is known about each melanocortin receptor subtype, predominantly focusing on their functions in the brain.

1.5.1 MC1R

Although MC1R is primarily expressed in melanocytes and is integral to the regulation of skin and hair pigmentation (Guida, Guida and Goding, 2022), it is also expressed in the brain (Cai et al., 2022; X. Chen, Feng, et al., 2017; Gatti et al., 2006; Srivastava et al., 2023). *MC1R* mRNA and protein are found in the hypothalamus, amygdala, locus coeruleus, and dorsal raphe nucleus, areas of the brain involved in regulating emotion and stress (Bittencourt et al., 1992; Hervieu et al., 2000; Saito et al., 1999). Additionally, MC1R is present in the nucleus accumbens, a region associated with motivation and reward. It is also expressed in the periaqueductal grey matter of the brain, an area in pain regulation (Caruso et al., 2014). Mutations in the *MC1R* gene are associated with neurodegenerative diseases and melanoma (skin cancer). People with Parkinson's disease are more prone to developing melanoma, and conversely, melanoma patients are at a higher risk of developing Parkinson's disease (X. Chen, Chen, et al., 2017; X. Chen, Feng, et al., 2017; Tell-Marti et al., 2015; Tell-Marti, Puig-Butille, Potrony, et al., 2017). *MC1R* melanoma risk genetic variants are also associated with Huntington's disease (Tell-Marti, Puig-Butille, Gimenez-Xavier, et al., 2017) and Alzheimer's disease (Giuliani, Bitto, et al., 2014; Tell-Marti, Puig-Butille, Potrony, et al., 2017).

In the brain, pharmacological activation of MC1R has been shown to exert anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects in Parkinson's disease (Cai et al., 2022) and Multiple Sclerosis (Mykicki et al., 2016). In addition, epidemiological data has shown a link between the *MC1R* gene, pigmentation, melanoma, and Parkinson's disease in humans that is associated with influenced dopamine production and dopamine neuronal survival (X. Chen, Feng, et al., 2017). Conversely, another human case study indicates that *MC1R* gene variants have little to no association with the risk of Parkinson's disease (Gan-Or et al., 2016). Interestingly, MC1R activation through systemic NDP-MSH administration in a mouse model of Parkinson's disease conferred neuroprotection against dopaminergic nigrostriatal neuron loss induced by lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and MPTP (induces Parkinson-like symptoms) (Srivastava et al., 2023). Similarly, MC1R activation protects against alpha-synuclein-induced dopaminergic neurotoxicity pathology in human and mouse models of Parkinson's disease (Cai et al., 2022). In rats, pharmacological MC1R activation contributes to neuroprotection and anti-inflammatory properties in a neonatal hypoxic-ischemic brain injury (Yu et al., 2021, 2022). In mice, NDP-MSH binding to MC1R reduced neuroinflammation and blood-brain barrier (BBB) disruption following intracerebral haemorrhage (Wu et al., 2019).

Similarly, other rodent models of brain injury have shown that when melanocortin ligands act on MC1R in the brain, they show neuroprotective effects, mitigating brain damage through a reduction in inflammation and cell apoptosis (Mykicki et al., 2016; Schaible et al., 2013). Many studies also demonstrate melanocortin ligands in the brain protect against brain damage, inflammation, and neurodegenerative disorders, although they attribute this to MC4R (Giuliani et al., 2011, 2015, 2017; Giuliani, Bitto, et al., 2014; Lasaga et al., 2008; Leone et al., 2015). In mice, MC1R is involved in acute pain and pain caused by inflammation, and the inhibition of MC1R with an antagonist reduced induced inflammatory response and delayed neuropathic pain symptoms (Delaney et al., 2010).

1.5.2 MC2R

MC2R, also known as the adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) receptor, is essential in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and for adrenal physiology (Herman et al., 2016; Novoselova et al., 2019). It is predominantly found in the adrenal cortex, where it mediates the production of glucocorticoids in response to ACTH stimulation, thus playing a vital role in the stress response (Fridmanis, Roga and Klovins, 2017). In the periphery, MC2R is also expressed in adipocyte cells regulating lipolysis (Boston, 1999; Bradley et al., 2005; Møller et al., 2011; Rodrigues et al., 2013). Although MC2R is primarily associated with adrenal function and cortisol production (Gallo-Payet, 2016; Novoselova et al., 2019), it has some expression during foetal development and may contribute to organogenesis (Simamura et al., 2011). As MC2R is not a focus of this thesis, this section has been kept short.

1.5.3 MC3R

In addition to MC3R expression in the hypothalamus, where they regulate food intake and energy expenditure, MC3Rs are also found in the limbic regions of the brain, which control behaviour and emotional responses (Butler et al., 2017; Yeo et al., 2021). Activation of MC3R may modulate feeding behaviour and energy balance through interactions with other neuropeptides and neurotransmitter systems in the hypothalamus (Butler et al., 2017; Pei et al., 2019). Additionally, MC3R has been implicated in various physiological processes, such as regulating cardiovascular function, inflammation, and immune responses, although its precise functions in these contexts are still being investigated (Yanik and Durhan, 2023). However, MC3R/MC4R activity interplay in specific physiological processes, compared with MC4R, relatively little is known about MC3R-expressing cells in the brain and their organisation within the CNS (Bedenbaugh et al., 2022).

Brain-wide mapping of neurons found expression of MC3R to be highly dense in the hypothalamus but also found MC3R neuronal terminal labelling in multiple brain regions controlling a diverse range of physiological functions and behavioural processes (Bedenbaugh et al., 2022). In mice, hypothalamic MC3R-expressing neurons modulate energy expenditure, adiposity, and locomotor activity (Pei et al., 2019). During energy deficiency, MC3R expression

in AgRP-expressing neurons is required for normal activation of these neurons (Gui et al., 2023). MC3R knockout mice exhibit increased adiposity and accelerated diet-induced obesity (Begrache et al., 2011, 2013; Butler, 2006; Butler et al., 2017). Regional expression of brain MC3R is elevated in lean active rats compared to obese rats (Shukla et al., 2015). Recently, it was evidenced that MC3R detects the body's nutritional state and regulates the timing of puberty rate and sexual development in children accordingly (Lam et al., 2021). *MC3R* mutations are linked to an increased risk of obesity and slower growth during puberty. Individuals with these mutations tend to be shorter and less lean, though the mutations do not affect the overall amount of body fat. (Lam *et al.*, 2021). A recent study further supported this, indicating that loss of function MC3R alleles are associated with decreased height, obesity, and delayed puberty (Zheng et al., 2023). MC3R also plays a role in the modulation of circadian rhythms (Begrache et al., 2013; Sutton et al., 2010). MC3R within the neural circuits governing energy homeostasis has also been linked to anxiety-related behaviour in mice (Cho *et al.*, 2023) and anorexic disorders (Sweeney et al., 2021).

1.5.4 MC4R

Neuronal MC4Rs have been extensively studied within the melanocortin system for their role in regulating energy homeostasis. However, there is growing evidence of synaptic changes and plasticity in mood disorders, addiction, memory, and chronic pain mediated via MC4R (Caruso et al., 2014; Chu et al., 2012; Li et al., 2017; Tao, 2010; Zhao et al., 2019). In the CNS, MC4R's activation increases blood pressure and sympathetic activity. MC4Rs can regulate a diverse array of physiological functions, including erectile and reproductive function, pain regulation, stress response, cardiovascular function, glucose metabolism and other biological processes (Butler & Cone, 2002; Cone, 2005; Krashes et al., 2016; Mountjoy, 2010; Trevor J. Hallam et al., 2007; Van der Ploeg et al., 2002). My thesis focuses on the broader role of MC4R beyond the neuronal melanocortin system in the brain.

MC4R, as with the other MCRs, is a complex receptor with various physiological and pathophysiological roles. Historically, it was understood that MC4R is primarily distributed in the hypothalamus of the brain, acting as a key regulator

of energy homeostasis and food intake (Wang et al., 2020). MC4R is also expressed in both central and peripheral organs and has diverse roles in the body (Carmo et al., 2017). Over the years, it was found to be expressed in other brain regions beyond the hypothalamus, such as the medial prefrontal cortex, an area involved in function and decision-making (Bouyakdan et al., 2019; Fani et al., 2014; Mountjoy, 2010; Wang et al., 2020). It is also expressed in the periaqueductal grey area of the brain, involved in pain system and spinal information processing, where administration of α -MSH reduces the response to pain (Caruso et al., 2014; Li et al., 2017). In the mouse brain, it is expressed differentially throughout the arcuate nucleus, nucleus of the solitary tract, brain stem and other brain areas (Wang et al., 2020). Its expression in the brain in other neuronal populations, including cholinergic neurons, suggested its role in glucose homeostasis and control of body weight (Choi & Kim, 2022; Kleinridders et al., 2009; Morgan et al., 2015). Hypothalamic MC4R regulates glucose homeostasis through adrenaline-mediated control of glucose reabsorption via renal GLUT2 in mice, which explains why people with *MC4R*-associated monogenic obesity do not develop hyperglycaemia despite insulin resistance and obesity (de Souza Cordeiro et al., 2021).

MC4R is also expressed in peripheral organs such as the enteroendocrine L cells of the intestine (Wei et al., 2023). L cell stimulation by MC4R ligands results in the release of peptide YY and glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) that modulate weight and improve glucose metabolism, possibly associated with the central leptin-melanocortin system, complementing vagal and central receptor functions, autocrine and paracrine signalling (Panaro et al., 2014; Shen et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2023).

Mutations in *MC4R* are the most common monogenic genetic cause of severe obesity in humans and also cause obesity in rodents, highlighting its critical role in feeding behaviour and metabolic regulation (Fani et al., 2014; Farooqi et al., 2000; Fatima et al., 2022; Hill & Faulkner, 2017; Huszar et al., 1997; Sweeney et al., 2023; Yeo et al., 2021). Like MC3R, a regional expression of brain MC4R is elevated in lean active rats compared to obese rats (Shukla et al., 2015). Setmelanotide, the MC4R agonist, is now used to treat human weight management (Clément et al., 2020; Trapp and Censani, 2023).

Like MC1R, MC4R has neuroprotective and neuro-regenerative effects in many models of neuro disorders or chronic pain (Chu et al., 2012; Giuliani et al., 2017). Inhibition of MC4R in a rat model of chronic constriction injury using the selective antagonist HS014, administered into the periaqueductal grey brain area, reduced pain facilitation by regulating glial activation and inflammatory cytokine release (Chu et al., 2012). Similarly, MC4R activation in rats, via intraperitoneal administration of α -MSH, protected striatal neurons and glial cells but not those in the cortex. Melanocortin ligands, acting on MCRs by activating PPAR- γ and BDNF pathways, protect neurons and glial cells from 3-NP toxicity (Saba et al., 2019). MC4R has also been shown to have therapeutic potential for neuropathic pain (Bellasio et al., 2003; Chu et al., 2012; Korczeniewska et al., 2021; Vrinten et al., 2001), where its inhibition *in-vivo* with the antagonists HS014 and SHU9119 has been shown to alleviate induced pain in rats (Korczeniewska et al., 2021; Korczeniewska et al., 2023). Furthermore, when mice are subjected to pharmacologically induced pain, MTII injections increase pain sensitivity, which is then blocked by the antagonists SHU9119, HS014 and others, evidence strengthening the potential involvement of MC4R in pain regulation (Bellasio et al., 2003). Overall, beyond regulation of energy balance, MC4R, like MC1R, is implicated in the regulation of pain and inflammation, and its actions appear to be bifunctional depending on the wider physiological environment and CNS condition: either attenuating injury/inflammation during pathophysiology or contributing to pathophysiological conditions.

1.5.5 MC5R

MC5R has been primarily studied in the context of peripheral tissues, where it plays roles in exocrine gland function and lipid metabolism (Chen et al., 1997; Hatta et al., 2001; Møller et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2011). MC5R also regulates immunological responses in mouse models with auto-immune disorders (Lee & Taylor, 2011; McDonald et al., 2021). MC5R is expressed in various brain regions (Gantz et al., 1994; Liao et al., 2019; Shukla et al., 2015; Simamura et al., 2011; Zhou et al., 2021) and is thought to possibly be involved in broader regulatory neuroendocrine mechanisms (Shukla et al., 2015). While the exact functions of MC5R in the brain are not as well understood as those of MC3R and MC4R, it is believed to contribute to CNS activities due to its presence in brain regions involved in cognitive and emotional processes. MC5R might play a role in modulating inflammatory responses in the brain, as melanocortin receptors have been implicated in anti-inflammatory processes. Like MC3R/MC4R, a regional expression of brain MC5R is also elevated in lean active rats compared to obese rats (Shukla et al., 2015). MC5R is also involved in cognitive function (Zhou et al., 2021), stress response (Liao et al., 2019) and foetal brain development (Simamura et al., 2011). It is expressed later in the developing brain than MC2R, where MC5R may contribute to cortex development (Simamura et al., 2011). However, aged brains are reported to express comparatively less MC5R (Zhou et al., 2021).

Collectively, MCRs in the brain are integral to maintaining homeostasis, modulating stress and inflammatory responses, regulating energy balance and appetite, and influencing a range of behaviours. Understanding their specific roles and mechanisms continues to be a crucial area of neuroendocrine research, with significant implications for treating metabolic, neurodegenerative, and psychiatric disorders.

1.6 Melanocortin receptor signalling pathways

This section will briefly outline some MCR signalling pathways, highlighting their complexity. The diverse findings in the literature contribute to ongoing debates, indicating that our understanding of MCR cellular signalling is becoming increasingly complicated and nuanced. This will be introduced in more depth in **Chapter 3** focusing on MCR signalling pathways.

1.6.1 G protein signalling

MCRs are G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) that, like other GPCRs, are activated upon agonist binding, triggering downstream signalling pathways. Upon activation by a ligand, the receptor binds to a partner heterotrimeric G protein, defined into four classes: Gs or Gq11 / G12/13 (stimulatory), and Gi (inhibitory), (Wettschureck & Offermanns, 2005). The G proteins encompass an alpha (α) and beta-gamma ($\beta\gamma$) subunit complex. The binding of the receptor to the G α protein promotes the exchange of GTP for GDP. The GTP-bound α -subunit dissociates from the activated receptor and $\beta\gamma$ subunits. The free subunits can now activate and modulate signalling cascades, including ion channels, but the signalling type depends on the G protein coupling sub-type (Wettschureck & Offermanns, 2005). **Figure 1.6.1-1** shows a simplified diagram of different MCR G protein coupling and downstream signalling pathways, including protein kinase A (PKA) and protein lipase C (PLC).

G-protein-mediated signalling events downstream of MCRs modulate cell physiology to regulate many vital body functions. The “conventional” activation of the Gs-cAMP pathway occurs downstream of MC1R, MC3R, MC4R and MC5R, although there is conflicting evidence from different cell types and physiological contexts (Baldini & Phelan, 2019; Gantz, Miwa, et al., 1993; Glas et al., 2016; Laiho & Murray, 2022; Y. Li et al., 2016; Rodríguez et al., 2017; Sassone-Corsi, 2012). A systematic review on cAMP response to different ligands for all MCRs except MC2R found up to 100-fold differences in EC50 (potency) values in response to the same ligands (Laiho & Murray, 2022). Interestingly, MCRs are reported to have biased signalling in wild-type and mutant MCRs, triggering different signalling pathways in response to various

ligands (Breit et al., 2011; Lotta et al., 2019; Mo & Tao, 2013; Paisdzior et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2021; Yang & Tao, 2017).

MCR Signalling Pathways

Figure 1.6.1-1 Some G protein-coupled melanocortin receptor signalling pathways

Melanocortin receptors (MCRs) can couple to any of the G α_s , G α_q , and G α_i G proteins. MCRs can also couple to inwardly rectifying potassium channels independent of G proteins (not shown in the figure). The endogenous agonists alpha-melanocyte stimulating hormone (α -MSH) or the synthetic agonist melanotan II (MTII) bind to MCRs (except MC2R) and trigger the signalling pathways to phosphorylate protein kinase A (PKA) or protein lipase C (PLC) (indicated with the P letter in red). In contrast, the binding of agonists to MCRs can also inhibit PKA signalling when MCRs are coupled with the G α_i protein (inhibitory G protein) (indicated with the blunted arrow). The figure was created using a Biorender template with some modifications by me.

1.6.2 Melanocortin receptor accessory proteins (MRAPS)

Melanocortin receptor accessory proteins (MRAPs), specifically MRAP1 and MRAP2, are important endogenous regulators of MCRs (Wang et al., 2022). They are found in endocrine organs, the hypothalamus, and the adrenal gland, where they interact with MCRs to influence their activity through various mechanisms (Gorrigan et al., 2011; Laiho & Murray, 2022; Wang et al., 2022). MRAPs modulate MCR signalling, cell surface translocation, and ligand-stimulated downstream pathways (Chan et al., 2009; Laiho and Murray, 2022). MRAP1 enhances the activity of MC2R and is essential for its function, while MRAP2 can inhibit receptors like MC4R under certain conditions (Chan et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2022). Additionally, MRAPs affect ligand-binding properties, ensuring receptors respond appropriately to physiological ligand levels.

MRAPS play a role in the intracellular trafficking of MCRs, assisting in proper folding and transport to the plasma membrane. This process is crucial for the receptors' interaction with their ligands. Notably, MRAPs' interaction with MC2R promotes surface expression and signalling, while their interaction with MC1R, MC3R, MC4R, and MC5R reduces responsiveness to the agonist NDP-MSH (Chan et al., 2009). MRAP knockdown mice exhibit pathophysiological conditions such as obesity (Laiho and Murray, 2022). MRAPs fine-tune MCR activity through bidirectional regulation to maintain homeostasis in various biological processes.

1.7 Melanocortin receptors and astrocytes

Emerging evidence suggests that MCRs are expressed on glial cells, including astrocytes (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2012; Kamermans et al., 2019; Ramírez et al., 2015, 2019; Saba et al., 2019; Selkirk et al., 2007; Vaglini et al., 2018; W. Xu et al., 2020), although their role in astrocyte physiology remains underexplored. Previous research primarily focused on neuronal MCRs; however, there is growing interest in how astrocytic MCRs contribute to brain homeostasis, neuroprotection and increased cell metabolism (Ramírez et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2018). Understanding the interaction between melanocortin signalling and astrocytic function could reveal new therapeutic targets for neuroinflammatory and metabolic disorders. I will introduce what is currently known about MCRs on astrocytes and summarise the introduction, stating the overarching hypothesis and outlining this thesis's aims and investigations.

1.8 Melanocortin receptor modulation of astrocytes

As previously discussed above, astrocytes exert a wide range of functions in brain physiology. Following injury or trauma, reactive astrocytes respond by secreting inflammatory mediators to protect, restore and maintain the brain function. Melanocortin ligands are recognised to have neuroprotective activity and anti-inflammatory properties in the brain (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2007, 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lasaga et al., 2008; Ramírez et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2009, 2012; Saba et al., 2019; Vaglini et al., 2018; Wong K & N, 1997; Weilin Xu et al., 2020). Our knowledge of the processes underlying this is limited. Even though melanocortin effects in astrocytes were reported early in 1984, research into the expression of MCRs in astrocytes has been ongoing for several years. Some key studies in this area can be traced back to the early 2000s (Caruso et al., 2007, 2012; Kamermans et al., 2019; Ramírez et al., 2015, 2019; Saba et al., 2019; Selkirk et al., 2007; Vaglini et al., 2018). Therefore, given MCR expression in astrocytes and the crucial role astrocytes play in maintaining brain function, the collective role of these receptors and their ligands in regulating astrocyte function remains unclear. Likewise, despite our emerging understanding that melanocortin ligands exert

neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory effects in the CNS, the expression of these receptors and their function in astrocytes remains under explored. The subsequent sections will highlight the existing knowledge regarding MCR function in astrocytes.

1.8.1 Melanocortin receptor expression, signalling and function in astrocytes

MCRs are not exclusively expressed in neurons. Although present in various brain regions. MCR expression in astrocytes has been reported; however, their exact role in astrocytic function is still being studied. (Daniels et al., 2003; Vongs, Lynn and Rosenblum, 2004; Sutton et al., 2005a; Chai et al., 2006; Patten et al., 2007; Damm et al., 2012; Glas et al., 2016; Vaglini et al., 2018; Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2007; Ramírez et al., 2015; Saba et al., 2019). Studies on the expression of MCRs in astrocytes started to emerge in the early 2000s, describing the expression of MC4R in these cells (Caruso et al., 2007, 2012; Kamermans et al., 2019; Ramírez et al., 2015; Selkirk et al., 2007; Vaglini et al., 2018). Then, in 2020, the expression of MC1R was also reported in astrocytes (Xu, Yan, et al., 2020). Synthetic as well as endogenous ligands targeting MCRs have been shown to increase cAMP accumulation, PKA and ERK1/2 signalling in astrocytes [for review see (Laiho and Murray, 2022)]. The activation of these receptors in astrocytes has been demonstrated to attenuate early brain injury and inflammation by controlling mitochondrial metabolism (Caruso et al., 2007; Ramírez et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2020). Including astroglia cells (brain tumour), MC4R is expressed with gene polymorphisms associated with obesity, diabetes, breast cancer or antipsychotic-induced weight gain (Pasqualetti et al., 2018). The potential physiological functions of melanocortin receptors in astrocytes include roles in neuroprotection and preventing inflammation, however, their full role and functions remain to be clarified by further studies.

Activation of MCR signalling pathways in astrocytes has been associated with the upregulation of various transcription factors, including CREB/CRE, cFOS, and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (Caruso et al., 2012; Ramírez et al., 2015; Saba et al., 2019). BDNF is essential for various aspects of neuronal development, survival, and synaptic plasticity (Chan, 2014), and it also plays a

role in the anorexigenic effects of melanocortin's in the hypothalamus (Xu et al., 2003). Additionally, MCR activation in astrocytes has been linked to increased PPAR- γ protein expression (Carniglia et al., 2013) which has anti-inflammatory properties. Together, these findings suggest that MCRs in astrocytes may modulate brain function via various signalling pathways and transcription factors. Therefore, MCRs in astrocytes could be potential targets for therapeutic drug treatments. However, further research is needed to fully understand their expression levels, precise functions, and the specific subtypes of MCRs involved in these processes.

1.9 Summary of Introduction

In summary, melanocortin receptors and their peptides are crucial in maintaining brain and systemic homeostasis; disruption in MCR function and signalling causes neurological and pathophysiological disorders. This thesis will focus on how pharmacological activation of melanocortin receptors impacts astrocyte function.

1.10 Summary of current knowledge and research objectives

In recent years, increasing evidence has highlighted the importance of astrocytes in maintaining brain homeostasis and supporting neuronal functions. Astrocytes regulate various processes, including extracellular potassium buffering, calcium signalling, metabolic activity, and synaptic modulation (Achour & Pascual, 2012; Bonvento & Bolaños, 2021; Kofuji & Newman, 2004; Tasker et al., 2021). Much of the research on astrocytic function, particularly in neuroendocrine systems, has focused on their interaction with neurons, leaving significant gaps in understanding how other signalling pathways, such as those mediated by melanocortin receptors (MCRs), directly impact astrocyte physiology.

While MCRs, particularly MC3R and MC4R, have well-characterised CNS actions, their expression and functional role in astrocytes remain less understood. Initial evidence suggests that MC4R may be expressed in astrocytes (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2007, 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lasaga et al., 2008; Ramírez et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2009, 2012; Saba et al., 2019; Vaglini et al., 2018; Wong K & N, 1997; Xu et al., 2020), yet the broader influence of MCR modulation on astrocyte signalling, ion dynamics and metabolism has not been thoroughly investigated. Furthermore, the potential therapeutic targeting of astrocytic MCRs for neurological and metabolic disorders is of growing interest.

1.11 Rationale for using human U373 astroglioma cells and primary mouse astrocytes

In this thesis, both human U373 astroglioma cells and primary neonatal mouse cortical astrocytes were used as experimental models to investigate the role of melanocortin receptors in astrocytic metabolism and signalling. Human U373 astroglioma cells and neonatal mouse primary cortical astrocytes were chosen due to their availability within our lab and to characterise effects across species. Human primary astrocytes are difficult to obtain and because of their rare and precious nature would not have been the most appropriate model for our early exploratory work. Although glioblastoma derived, U373 cells have more properties in common with long-term cultured astrocytes than with cultured neurons or oligodendrocytes (Volkhardt et al., 2002). The U373 human astroglioma cell line provides a reliable and easily manipulated in-vitro model for studying astrocyte-like behaviour, allowing for repeated experiments with relatively stable cellular characteristics (Kamermans et al., 2019; Robb, 2020; Torsvik et al., 2014; Volkhardt et al., 2002). U373 cells are immortalised, making them highly proliferative and suitable for extended experimental protocols, which is beneficial for studying receptor signalling, ion dynamics and metabolic changes in response to pharmacological agents. However, U373 cells may not fully recapitulate the physiological conditions of astrocytes in-vivo due to their cancerous origin. Therefore, primary mouse cortical astrocytes were also used to provide a more physiologically relevant model of non-transformed astrocytes. These cells more accurately reflect the intracellular ion flux changes and signalling properties of astrocytes in their natural environment, offering insights into how melanocortin receptor activation may influence normal astrocytic functions. Neonatal mouse cortical astrocytes were chosen over astrocytes derived from older mice due the difficulty in culturing astrocytes from older mice compared with neonatal astrocytes, although it is appreciated these are immature cells.

1.12 Overarching hypothesis and aims of the thesis

Melanocortin ligands acting on melanocortin receptors modulate astrocyte function. This thesis aimed to test this hypothesis and to fill knowledge gaps regarding the role of melanocortin receptors in astrocyte physiology by addressing the following key objectives:

1. To investigate the expression of melanocortin receptors in astrocytes

Establish using PCR the MCR subtypes expressed in astrocytes, using both primary mouse cortical astrocytes and U373 human astrogloma cells as model systems. The findings of this aim will be presented in **Chapter 3**.

2. To examine the signalling pathways activated by melanocortin receptors in astrocytes:

Explore the downstream signalling mechanisms, particularly ERK1/2, PKA and PLC phosphorylation following MCR activation by synthetic ligands. The results will be presented in **Chapter 3**.

3. To examine ion dynamics (calcium and potassium flux) following MCR pharmacological modulation in astrocytes:

Explore the changes in astrocytic intracellular calcium ions and potassium uptake from the extracellular space. The results will be presented in **Chapter 4**.

4. To determine the impact of MCR modulation on astrocytic metabolism:

Evaluate how pharmacological modulation of MCRs affects astrocyte metabolism, focusing on oxygen consumption through mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis. These findings will be detailed in **Chapter 5**.

Together, these objectives will provide a comprehensive understanding of melanocortin receptor function in astrocytes and how these receptors may influence brain homeostasis and metabolism.

2 GENERAL METHODS

All materials are sourced from different suppliers as noted in **Table 2.18-2**. Where not specified, reagents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich or Fisher Scientific (UK).

2.1 Animal use and Ethics

The research involving animals adhered to the regulations outlined in the UK Animals in Scientific Procedures Act 1986 (ASPA), and the study protocols received approval from the institutional Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body at the University of Exeter. All work conducted was performed under the authority of personal and project licences. Mice were housed in groups under a 12:12 light-dark cycle at a temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, with unrestricted access to standard laboratory rodent diet (LabDiet [EU] Rodent diet 5LF2; LabDiet, London, UK) and water. Mouse primary cortical astrocytes were isolated from neonatal mice, between 1-5 days old from mating pairs of C57BL/6J mice, with both male and female offspring used in the research.

2.2 Primary astrocyte isolation and cell culture

Mouse primary cortical astrocytes were isolated using the method previously described (Schildge et al., 2013). Pups were euthanised via rapid decapitation and brains were removed from skulls. Forceps were used to remove meninges, cerebellum, and occipital lobes, followed by blunt dissection to extract the cortices and hypothalamus. Cortical regions were placed in a petri dish containing 1mL Hanks Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) and cut into smaller pieces using a scalpel to homogenise. Then homogenised cortices were digested in 0.5% w/v trypsin-EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) in HBSS for 30 minutes at 37°C with gentle agitation every 2-3 minutes. Trypsin was neutralised with supplemented Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Media; DMEM composition; 25 mM glucose, 8 mM L-glutamate, 10% v/v foetal bovine serum (FBS), 2% 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin. Using repeated pipetting motions, cells were then mechanically disrupted and filtered through a $70\ \mu\text{M}$ filter. Cells were then plated within 30-60 minutes of isolation (due to being in different buildings; ideally plate and culture immediately) in T75 flasks pre-coated with

poly-L-lysine (PLL; 4 µg/mL) and cultured in standard supplemented DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Media; DMEM composition; 25 mM glucose, 8 mM L-glutamate, 10% v/v foetal bovine serum (FBS), 2% 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin). Cells were maintained in a humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% carbon dioxide (CO₂). The following day, DMEM was aspirated, and cells were washed with 0.01M phosphate buffered saline (PBS) before DMEM was replaced every 2-3 days until cells were 80-90% confluent. Then cells were dissociated from the flasks with trypsin 0.05% w/v for 3-5 minutes in the humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. Flasks were gently tapped by hand to dislodge any cells attached to plastic and checked under a microscope. Cells were then neutralised from trypsin with supplemented media and centrifuged at 1000 revolutions per minute (RPM) for 5 minutes at room temperature. The supernatant was then aspirated, and cells were resuspended with warm supplemented standard DMEM and frozen down at -80 °C in 90% supplemented DMEM and 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and stored in liquid nitrogen until use. This thesis used frozen/thawed primary cortical and hypothalamic astrocytes in the subsequent experiments.

2.2.1 Culturing isolated primary neonatal astrocytes

For experimentation purposes, cell culture flasks (T75 for cortical astrocytes and T25 for hypothalamic astrocytes) were coated with poly-L-lysine (PLL; 4 µg/mL), incubated for 15–30-minutes at room temperature, and washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). PBS was removed from the flasks, and cells were thawed in a water bath prior to seeding. Mouse primary astrocyte cultures (cortical and hypothalamic) were seeded at 2-3 brains in T25/T75 flasks and maintained in DMEM containing 25 mM glucose and supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 2% 2% v/v penicillin-streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine. Cells were maintained in a humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% carbon dioxide (CO₂), and supplemented media was replaced every 2-3 days. Mouse primary cortical astrocytes were left to grow until 80-90% confluent, then dissociated from the flasks with trypsin 0.05% w/v for 3-5 minutes in the humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. Flasks were gently tapped by hand to dislodge any cells attached to plastic and checked under a microscope. Cells were then neutralised from trypsin with supplemented media and centrifuged at 1000 revolutions per

minute (RPM) for 5 minutes at room temperature. The supernatant was then aspirated, and cells were resuspended with warm supplemented 7.5mM glucose DMEM or 25mM glucose DMEM depending on the relevant experiments (DMEM composition with either glucose concentration; 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin-streptomycin, 8 mM L-glutamine). Cells were counted using the Cell Drop (DeNovix) to quantify cell numbers needed for the relevant experiments. Then cells were seeded in plastic cell culture dishes or plates at the required density and grown in DMEM composed of either 7.5mM or 25mM glucose (with other supplements as above) depending on the experiment in the relevant sections below. On the day of experimentation cells were cultured for two hours in serum free DMEM containing 2.5 mM glucose or 25mM glucose depending on the relevant experiment. Astrocyte purity was validated using immunocytochemistry (described below) to confirm that cells in culture were glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) immunoreactive astrocytes, (GFAP a marker for astrocytes)

2.3 Immunocytochemistry

Mouse primary cortical astrocytes were seeded at 5×10^4 cells onto prepared poly-L-Lysine (PLL) (4 μ g/ml) coated coverslips in a 6-well culture dish, then left to grow. When ready, the media was removed, and the cells were washed with 0.01M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Cells were fixed by adding ice-cold 100% methanol for 90 seconds, cells were then washed three times with 0.01M PBS. To block nonspecific binding, 5% normal donkey serum was added to the cells for 15 minutes at room temperature (RT). Then, cells were washed three times with 0.01M PBS, and antibodies against glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) or ionized calcium binding adaptor molecule 1 (IBA1) diluted in normal donkey serum (NDS) were added onto the coverslips (**Table 2.3-1**). For the no primary antibody negative control coverslip (secondary antibody only for the next day), PBS was added to prevent coverslip dryness. Coverslips were left covered up to incubate overnight at 4°C. On the following day, coverslips were washed three times with 0.01M PBS, then secondary antibodies were added onto all coverslips for 1 hour at RT, and the dishes were protected from light. After 1 hour, cells were washed three times with 0.01M PBS and air dried at RT for 5-10 minutes whilst protected from light. Coverslips were then carefully

removed from the 6 well plate with a tweezer, washed with distilled water (ddH₂O), removing excess water with a gentle dab on tissue and mounting onto glass slides prepared with one drop of Fluorishield Mounting Medium with DAPI (blue fluorescent DNA stain) per coverslip for 15 minutes protected from light. Cells were then imaged in the dark within 3 days using, the confocal microscope, then slides were stored in the dark at 4°C.

Table 2.3-1 Antibodies used for Immunocytochemistry

Primary Antibody	Dilution	Secondary Antibody	Dilution
GFAP (Merck Millipore: mab360)	1:1000 in 1% NDS in PBST	Anti Mouse AlexaFluor-488 (Invitrogen: A- 21202)	1:500, 1% NDS in PBST
IBA1 (Abcam: AB5076)	1:1000 in 1% NDS in PBST	Anti Goat Alexafluor-594 (Invitrogen: A- 11058)	1:500, 1% NDS in PBST

2.4 Human U373 astroglioma cell line culture

Human astroglioma U373 cells were sourced from ECACC, Uppsala (European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (U-373 MG [Uppsala] [ECACC 08061901). These cells have been “designated U-373 MG (Uppsala) to distinguish it from U-373 MG (ECACC catalogue number 89081403), which is now known to be identical (as determined by Short Tandem Repeat (STR)-PCR profiling) to another glioblastoma cell line, U-251 MG”. Following thawing from liquid nitrogen cells were continuously cultured in T75 sterile flasks between passage (p) 17 and up to p30 in stock Dulbecco’s modified Eagle’s Medium (DMEM composition: 25 mM glucose and supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine). The DMEM on the cells was changed every 2-4 days, and the cells were passaged when at approximately 80-90% confluence.

For passaging, U373 cells were washed with 0.01 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) before being dissociated from the plastic with trypsin-EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) 0.5% w/v for 3-5 minutes at 37 °C 5% carbon dioxide incubator. Cells were centrifuged at 1000 revolutions per minute (RPM) for 5 minutes at room temperature. The supernatant was aspirated, and cells were neutralised and resuspended with stock media: supplemented 25mM glucose DMEM or 7.5mM glucose DMEM (both DMEMs supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin-streptomycin, 8 mM L-glutamine). Cells were counted using the Cell Drop (DeNovix) (and seeded on cell culture plastic dishes or plates at an appropriate density relevant to the experiment in either 7.5mM glucose or stock 25mM glucose (both DMEMs supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin-streptomycin, 8 mM L-glutamine) a day prior to experimentation. The remaining cells were seeded into a sterile T75 flask to continue maintenance in a 37 °C 5% carbon dioxide (CO₂) incubator. The next day prior to experimentation, the DMEM was removed, and cells were washed with PBS and then cultured in serum-free DMEM (containing 2.5 mM glucose or 25mM glucose) for 2 hours.

2.5 RNA extraction

Ribonucleic acid (RNA) was extracted from human U373 cells, mouse primary cortical astrocytes and mouse brain tissue. Prior to RNA extraction from cells, the cells were seeded in plastic cell culture dishes and maintained in stock DMEM (supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin-streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) at 37 °C 5% CO₂ incubator. When cells reached the desired confluency of 80-90%, RNA was extracted from both cell types using the RNeasy Plus Mini Kit. RNA was collected and quantified using the Nanodrop 2000c Spectrophotometer. Similarly, cortical and hypothalamic brain tissue was briefly sonicated to disrupt the tissue and then homogenised for RNA extraction using the RNeasy Plus Mini Kit (**Table 2.18-2**). The quality of RNA was assessed using Nanodrop 2000c Spectrophotometer to meet a minimum threshold and confirm there was no contamination (260/280, RNA above 2.0), before continuing the conversion of RNA to cDNA.

2.6 Cell viability assay

To measure cell viability, U373 astrogloma cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 cells per well in DMEM supplemented with 7.5mM glucose, 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine in a 24 well plate and incubated at 37 °C, 5% carbon dioxide (CO₂) overnight. The next day, the media was aspirated, and cells were washed with 0.01 M PBS, then 2.5mM glucose serum free DMEM was added, and cells were incubated for 2 hours at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. Melanotan II (MTII; 0.1nM to 100nM) and Vehicle (ddH₂O) were made up in 2.5mM glucose DMEM in the cell culture hood. After two hours, DMEM was aspirated from cells and 100µL of trypsin-EDTA was added to cells for 3 minutes to dissociate from the plate. Cells were transferred into flow tubes and neutralised with 100 µL fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) buffer (2% v/v FBS in 0.01 mol/L PBS) then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1000 RPM, 4°C. The supernatant was aspirated, and cells were resuspended in 100 µL 2.5mM glucose DMEM and 100 µL FACS buffer containing 2 µg/mL propidium iodide (PI). PI is used as an indicator of cell death as it is not permeant to live cells. Cells were stained with PI for 10 minutes at 4 °C. For the negative control, cells did not contain PI, for the positive control cell death was induced with a heat shock for 60 °C for 20 minutes on a heat block. Samples were then vortexed briefly, and the proportion of PI-stained cells determined using flow cytometry with 488 nm wavelength laser with 585/40 nm filter. Data analysis/gating was performed as demonstrated below.

Figure 2.6-1 Example of cell viability FSC/SSC density plots

The forward scatter (FSC; plot 1) and side scatter (SSC; plot2) density plots were used to define cell sized objects. Cell events (cell count) from gate P1 Plot1 is shown on Plot2. Plot2 is a histogram that display a single measurement parameter (relative fluorescence) on the X-axis and the number of events on the Y-axis. Increased Events with a size smaller than normal cells were excluded as debris. The gating V1 was set on plot2 in between the peak of negative and positive control in the plots and then used to identify the number of alive or dead cells. The events with high fluorescence situated on the right side of the Plot2 gate V1 relative to cell size was determined using the 488 nm laser combined with FSC classified these events as dead or dying cells. Events with low fluorescence, located within the left side of the Plot2 gate, were determined as viable cells. The percentage of V1-R represents the dead cells in the whole sample whilst V1-L represents viable cells.

2.7 Primer design

Prior to the conversion of RNA to cDNA, primers were designed against neuroendocrine receptors, melanocortin receptors (MCRs), inward rectifying potassium channels and housekeeping genes (positive controls) using multiple PCR tools. Ensemble was first used to find the gene/species of interest and its transcripts; the most common transcript was selected. Transcripts were then imported into Benchling where I chose the appropriate transcript, specie and selected "import cDNA only." Following this, I chose regions with conserved exons. Then the target region was copied into *primer3plus* and a search was performed by the software to produce primer sets. I chose the most suitable primers that have a GC content between 40-60% and melting temperatures (T_m) close between forward and reverse primers (around 59-60 °C). The primer pairs per gene of interest were within an amplicon length from 202 base pairs (bp) to 530 bp. Following this, I mapped out the forward and reverse primer on Benchling to see where they are positioned in the target region of the gene. Using UCSC *in-silico* PCR I validated the primers by checking for potential amplicons and ensuring the results matched the species and gene of interest. Primers were ordered from IDT integrated DNA technologies and resuspended with ddH₂O to make 100 μM stock and then stored in -20 °C until further use.

Table 2.7-1 Primers designed against mouse and human target genes of interest

Mouse Primers

Gene target	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')	Product size (base pairs)
<i>CCKAR</i>	GATGTGGTGCAGCCTTCT	ATGTTGGTGCAGTCCGCAT	230
<i>CCKBR</i>	TCTAAATCTCGCGGCCATCG	GCACGGACCACATTTGTTGG	236
<i>GHSR</i>	AAGATGCTTGCTGTGGTGGT	ATGCTCGACTTTGTCCAGGC	305
<i>LEPR</i>	ACTGAAGGGAAGACACTGGC	AAGGGTGGATCGGGTTTCAC	404
<i>MC1R</i>	ATGGCCTCTTCCTCAGCCTA	AGAAAGTGACGAGGCAGAGC	462
<i>MC2R</i>	TGATTGTCCTCCTGGCTGTG	TGGTTAGTGTCATGGCACCC	540
<i>MC3R</i>	TGGGCATCGTCAGTCTGATG	CCTGGCGAAGAGGAACATGT	503
<i>MC4R</i>	P1:CCCACCACCATGGCATGTAT	P1:CATGGGTGAGTGCAGGTTCT	227
<i>MC4R</i>	P2:TGATGGCGAGGCTTCACATT	P2:ACTCACAGATGCCTCCCAGA	333
<i>MC5R</i>	TGTACTIONTTTGTGGGCAGCT	TGAAAACAATGCCGCAGCTT	321
<i>KIR 7.1</i>	CGCTGGATGATGCTGGTCTT	CGTGCAATCTTCGCCACAAA	326
<i>KIR 4.1</i>	CCTCTTTGGTGTGGTGTGGT	TCATAAGGCAAGGCTTCCCG	353
<i>GFAP</i>	TGGAGCTCAATGACCGCTTT	CCTGTCTATACGCAGCCAGG	303
<i>GAPDH</i>	CCATGACAACCTTTGGCATTG	CCTGCTTCACCACCTTCTTG	302

Human Primers

Gene target	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')	Product size (base pairs)
<i>MC1R</i>	CTACCACAGCATCGTGACCC	GCCCCAGCAGAGGAAGAAAA	313
<i>MC2R</i>	TCCCTGTTTGTCTCTCCCT	GAAGGTGATCACTGTGGGCA	213
<i>MC3R</i>	AGCAGGTCTTCATCAAGCCC	CTGTGGACGATGGCGATCAT	202
<i>MC4R</i>	AGTGAGTCCCTTGGAAGGC	CCATTTGAAACGCTCACCAGC	212
<i>MC5R</i>	TCTCAACCTGAATGCCACAGA	CACAAAGGCGTCTGCTATCAC	301
<i>KIR 7.1</i>	TCCTAATGGACATGCGCTGG	GCACTTGGACAGTCACCACT	262
<i>KIR 4.1</i>	ACCACTCAGACAGAAAGCCG	CATGTGCCACAGCTACCAGA	247
<i>GFAP</i>	TGATGGAGCTCAATGACCGC	CCTGTGCCAGATTGTCCCTC	222
<i>GAPDH</i>	AGCTGAACGGGAAGCTCAC	GTCAAAGGTGGAGGAGTGGG	221

2.8 Conversion of RNA to cDNA using reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR)

Ribonucleic acid (RNA) was converted to complementary deoxyribose nucleotide (cDNA) using the High-Capacity RNA-to-cDNA Kit (Table 2.18-2). The reverse transcription was performed, according to manufactures instructions, on the product. Samples were spun down briefly and incubated at 37 °C for 60 minutes, then 95 °C for 5 minutes and stopped at 4 °C using the SimpliAmp Thermal Cycler. cDNA was stored in -20 °C pending PCR.

2.9 Detection of genes of interest using polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

To confirm expression of genes of interest PCR was used. The PCR reaction was composed of 2X ThermoFisher Maxima Hot Start Green PCR master mix, 10 µM of each forward primer and reverse primer (diluted from 100µM stock in ddH₂O) of the genes of interest, DNA-free water, and the cDNA. For the negative controls, no template cDNA and ddH₂O were used. The no template control is used to determine that there is no genomic DNA contamination in reagents in both reverse transcription and PCR. The ddH₂O further checks that there is no DNA contamination in PCR reagents. The PCR cycling conditions are shown in the table below. PCR samples were then stored at 4 °C pending gel electrophoresis or used for gel electrophoresis on the same day.

Table 2.9-1 PCR cycling conditions

Temperature	Time	Cycles
95 °C	3 mins	1
95 °C	30 secs	35
58 °C	30 secs	35
72 °C	1 min	
72 °C	2 min	
4 °C	Hold	1

2.10 PCR product detection using agarose gel electrophoresis

For detection of the PCR products of the genes of interest, 1.5% agarose gels were made in 1X Tris acetate EDTA (TAE) buffer. 5 μ L of the DNA stain GelRed Nucleic Acid Gel Stain, was added to the mixture prior the gel setting. GeneRuler 1 kb Plus was loaded onto the gel as a DNA Ladder for size reference. One PCR sample were loaded per lane and electrophoresis was performed at between 90 volts (V) to 120V for 60 minutes to 1.5 hours until the yellow dye front reaches the bottom of the gel.

2.11 Cell treatments and protein isolation

To measure changes in some of the signalling pathways in the human astrogloma cell line and mouse cortical astrocytes, cells were pre-treated with melanocortin receptor (MCR) ligands. The synthetic MCRs ligands, melanotan II (MTII; agonist) and SHU9119 (antagonist) were purchased from Tocris, UK. The MCR synthetic agonist Setmelanotide (also known as RM-493) was purchased from Stratech, UK. The positive controls 8-Bromo-cAMP (PKA activator), and m-3M3FBS (PLC activator) were purchased from Tocris, UK. Adenosine triphosphate (ATP; positive control) was purchased from Merck Sigma-Aldrich. All drugs used are listed in **Table 2.11-1**. Drugs were reconstituted inside of the cell culture hood to maintain sterility. MTII, SHU9119 and ATP were reconstituted in sterile double distilled water (ddH₂O), whilst 8-Bromo-cAMP and m-3M3FBS were reconstituted in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (0.2% DMSO 8-Bromo-cAMP; 0.05% DMSO m-3M3FBS) as per supplier's instructions.

For mouse primary cortical astrocytes, plastic dishes were precoated with 4mg/mL poly-L-lysine (PLL) for 15 minutes at room temperature (RT) then washed with PBS and ddH₂O. Both human U373 astrogloma and mouse primary cortical astrocytes were seeded at a density of 4x10⁵ in plastic dishes a day prior to experimentation and maintained in supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) containing either 7.5mM glucose or 25mM glucose depending on the experiment. On the day of experimentation DMEM was removed from the dishes, and cells were washed

with 0.01M phosphate buffered saline (PBS) then incubated with either 2.5mM or 25mM glucose serum free DMEM for 1.5 hours at 37 °C 5% CO₂. To ensure cell signalling drops to basal levels, DMEM was removed, and cells are washed again with PBS and media replaced serum-free media of the relevant glucose concentration and incubated again for 30 minutes at 37 °C 5% CO₂. Whilst cells were in the incubator the desired drug dilutions were made in the cell culture hood in preparation for ligand treatments. DMEM was then removed from the dishes and cells were treated with increasing concentrations of MTII or Setmelanotide (0.1nM to 100nM), 1 µM SHU9119, 100 µM ATP, 100 µM 8-Bromo-cAMP, 25 µM m-3M3FBS, or the relevant Vehicle (DMEM with ddH₂O) in serum free 25mM or 2.5mM glucose medium as relevant to the experiment. Cells were then incubated for 15 minutes at 37°C 5% CO₂.

Additionally, human U373 astrogloma cells were treated with 8-Bromo-cAMP for a time course of 0, 30, 60 and 90 minutes at 37°C 5% CO₂ as part of optimisation. For the inhibitory experiments, SHU9119 was added to human U373 astrogloma cells for 30 minutes at 37°C 5% CO₂ prior to the addition of 1nM MTII for 15 minutes at 37°C 5% CO₂.

Following drug treatments, DMEM was removed, and cells were washed with ice-cold 0.01M PBS, which was then aspirated. Dishes were then placed on ice, and 50 µl of freshly made up 1X lysis buffer was added to each dish (lysis buffer with protease inhibitors was made 5-10 minutes before) (**Table 2.12-1**). Cells were manually scraped using a sterile cell scraper and lysates were collected and stored at -20 °C, thawed the next day and centrifuged at 14,800 RPM at 4 °C for 20 minutes. Alternatively, cell lysates were collected directly and centrifuged at 14,800 RPM at 4 °C for 20 minutes. In both cases, after spinning, the supernatant was then collected and lysates stored at -20 °C pending a Bradford Protein Assay.

Table 2.11-1 Synthetic drugs used for cell culture treatments

Drug	Catalogue number	Supplier
MTII	2566	Tocris, UK
SHU9119	4320	Tocris, UK
Setmelanotide (RM-493)	E1002	Stratech, UK
ATP	A9187-100MG	Merck
8-Bromo-cAMP	1140	Tocris, UK
m-3M3FBS	1941	Tocris, UK

2.12 Protein quantification for immunoblotting

Following lysate collection from human U373 astroglioma cell line or mouse primary cortical astrocytes, protein concentration in the samples was quantified using a Bradford Protein Assay. Lysates were thawed on ice. Using a clear 96 well plate, bovine serum albumin (BSA) was added ranging from 0-3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in triplicates with 1 μL of the same lysis buffer used for lysate collection to create a standard curve. 1 μL of lysate samples were then added to unique wells in triplicates. The Bradford reagent was diluted with double distilled water (ddH_2O) according to the manufacturer's instructions and 200 μL was added per well. Plates were shaken at 300 RPM for 300 seconds and absorbance was measured at 595 nm using the Pherastar FS plate reader.

Table 2.12-1 Lysis buffer (1X) composition for cell scraping and protein quantification

Compounds	Concentration/L
Tris HCL pH 7.4	25 mM
NaF	50 mM
NaCL	0.1 mM
EDTA pH 8	1 mM
EGTA pH 8	5 mM
Triton 100X	1%
NaPPi	10mM
Sucrose	268.8 mM
β -Mercaptoethanol	Stock 0.1%
NaVO_4 heat 95°C for 5 minutes before	0.5 M
Benzamidine	0.5 M
PMSF add 5 minutes before lysis	50 mM

2.13 Western Blotting

Samples were prepared for Western Blotting after protein quantification of cell lysates from drug treated U373 astrogloma cells and mouse primary cortical astrocytes. All samples for Western Blotting were made in β -Mecaptoethanol, 4X sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis sample buffer (SDS-PAGE) (**Table 2.13-1**) and the same lysis buffer (**Table 2.12-1**) used for scraping cells. Samples were diluted to 10 μ g protein/sample for the detection of phosphorylated extracellular regulated kinase 1/2 (p-ERK1/2), total ERK1/2 (ERK1/2), phosphorylated protein kinase (p-PKA) or total PKA (PKA), and 20 μ g protein/sample for the detection of phosphorylated protein lipase C (p-PLC). Prior to loading onto the gel, samples were then heated at 95 °C for 5 minutes using a heat block. Samples were then run on hand-cast gels (**Table 2.13-2**) made on the same day or 1-3 days before (stored at 4 °C wrapped in cling film and moist tissue to avoid dryness). 12% SDS-acrylamide gels were used for the detection of phosphorylated and total ERK1/2 (42-44 kilo Dalton; kDa), PKA (42 kDa) and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH; 38 kDa), and 7% SDS-acrylamide gels were used for the detection of phosphorylated and total PLC (150 kDa) (**Table 2.13-3**). Samples were then loaded into the wells of the gel in a tank which contained 1X running buffer (Tris, Glycine and SDS diluted in ddH₂O). In the same species of antibodies, two gels were made, and the same samples were loaded onto each gel, with both run under the same conditions for detection. 3-5 μ L of the Precision Plus Protein Dual Colour Standards was loaded into the first well and used as a size reference for protein molecular weight estimation. Gels were than run at 90 volts (V) for 15 minutes, then 150 V for 1.5 hours.

Gels were then transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes using the wet transfer method using (Tris, Glycine and methanol diluted in ddH₂O) transfer buffer, an ice pack was added into the tank to prevent overheating, a current of 100 V was applied for 1 hour 15 minutes. To prevent non-specific binding of the antibodies to proteins with similar recognition sites, membranes were blocked with 5% dried semi-skimmed milk in Tris-buffered saline with 0.1% Tween 20 detergent (TBST) for 1 hour at room temperature (RT) on a rocker. Membranes were then washed with TBST for 5 minutes up to 3 times, followed by adding

the desired primary antibodies (**Table 2.13-3**) of interest and incubated overnight at 4 °C on a rocker. Primary and secondary antibodies for GAPDH detection were then incubated sequentially for 1 hour at RT on a rocker with three TBST washes (5 minutes each) between antibodies. Membranes were then imaged using the LI-COR Odyssey Imaging system to detect fluorescence intensity at 680nm and 800nm.

Table 2.13-1 4X SDS-PAGE sample buffer

Compounds	Concentration
Tris-HCL (pH 6.8)	125mM
SDS	4% w/v
Glycerol	20% v/v
Bromophenol blue	>1%

Table 2.13-2 Handmade SDS-polyacrylamide gel composition

2 x gels	Stacking gel		Running gel	
	4% gel	7% gel	12% gel	
ddH2O	2.8mL	5.28mL	3.42mL	
1.5 M Tris (lower buffer)		3.15mL	3.15mL	
0.5 M Tris (upper buffer)	1.25mL			
30% Acrylamide	850µL	2.63mL	4.48mL	
10% SDS	50µL	110µL	110µL	
20% APS	50µL	55.4µL	55.4µL	
TEMED	5.35µL	11µL	11µL	

Table 2.13-3 List of antibodies used for Western Blotting

Primary Antibodies	Dilution	Species	Supplier	Catalogue number
Phospho-p44/42 MAPK (Erk1/2) (Thr202/Tyr204) (polyclonal)	1:1000 In 5% BSA/TBST	Rabbit	Cell Signalling	9101S
p44/42 MAPK (Erk1/2) (L34F12) (monoclonal)	1:1000	Mouse	Cell Signalling	4696S
Phospho-PKA C (Thr197) (D45D3) (monoclonal)	1:1000	Rabbit	Cell Signalling	5661S
PKA C- α (D38C6) Rabbit (monoclonal)	1:1000	Rabbit	Cell Signalling	5842S
PLCbeta3 (D9D6S) Rabbit (monoclonal)	1:1000	Rabbit	Cell Signalling	14247
Phospho-PLCbeta3 (Ser537) (D8K2R) (monoclonal)	1:1000	Rabbit	Cell Signalling	29021
GAPDH (polyclonal)	1:10,000	Rabbit	Merck Millipore	G9545
Secondary Polyclonal Antibodies	Dilution	Species	Supplier	Catalogue number
IGG (H&L) antibody DYLIGHT™ 800 Conjugated pre-adsorbed	1:10,000 in TBST	Rabbit	Rockland	ROCK611- 145-122
IgG (H+L) Cross- Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 680	1:10,000 in TBST	Goat anti- Mouse	Invitrogen	A-21057

2.13.1 Densitometry analysis

To semi-quantify (a relative comparison of protein levels, but not an absolute measure of quantity) the intensity of fluorescence signals, densitometric analysis was conducted using the Image Studio Lite (Ver 5.2) software. Signals were assessed using pixel intensity within regions of interest, boxes were drawn around the relevant bands which include background signals. Phosphorylated protein signals were normalised to the signal of its total protein (phospho/total). Samples were then normalised to the average of the Vehicle (control). Relative levels of protein phosphorylation were then analysed. GAPDH was used as a loading control, when possible, to account for errors in protein quantification and sample loading. Data analysis was performed as described in **section 2.17**.

2.14 Measurement of intracellular calcium ion changes

Cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 7.5mM glucose, 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine in 96 well plates and incubated overnight at 37 °C, 5% carbon dioxide (CO₂). On the day of experimentation, the DMEM was removed, and cells were washed with 0.01 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS); PBS was aspirated, then cells were incubated in 2.5mM glucose serum-free DMEM for 2 hours at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. During the incubation period, the kit was opened in the cell culture hood to ensure sterility of products to avoid cell contamination. The Fluo-4 AM dye was diluted to 1X according to the manufacturer's instructions with 20mL phenol red-free (PRF) DMEM supplemented with 25mM HEPES and 2.5mM glucose. The prepared Fluo-4 AM dye was protected from light using foil and then mixed thoroughly. After the two-hour serum-free incubation period, DMEM was aspirated, and cells were washed with 0.01 M PBS; PBS was aspirated, and then cells were incubated with 1X Fluo4 AM for 1 hour at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. During this time, ligands were made up to the desired working stock. Melanotan II (MTII), Setmelanotide, Vehicle (ddH₂O) and adenosine triphosphate (ATP) were made up in PRF media supplemented with 25mM HEPES and 2.5 mM glucose. For the optimised protocol, U373 cells were incubated in serum-free 2.5mM glucose

media for two hours at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. Then, the media was aspirated, and cells were washed with 0.01 M PBS, and then the PBS was aspirated. Cells then were incubated with 1X Fluo-4 AM (diluted with the manufacturer's assay buffer and supplemented with 2.5mM probenecid) for 1 hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Ligands were diluted in an assay buffer. The PHERAstar FS microplate reader (with two ports for injectors) was primed (withdraws compounds and prepares the machine for injections) with ethanol, water, and then air to avoid contamination of substances primed into the machine. This step is usually performed before and after each experiment or using different compounds during an experiment. The PHERAstar was then primed with ligands and cleaned between different concentrations and drugs when reprimed (**Table 2.14-1**). Basal relative fluorescence units (RFU) were first measured (Excitation 485nm and Emission 520nm) followed by a drug injection; RFU was then measured continually for 90 seconds or 120 seconds. Raw data was imported from the machine and processed in Excel; data were normalised to the first baseline measurement set to a value of 1. Data analysis was performed as described in **section 2.17**.

Table 2.14-1 Ligands used to measure iCa²⁺ levels in U373 astroglioma and cells and mouse primary cortical astrocytes

Compounds injected into wells	Final well concentration
MTII	0.1 nM to 100 nM
Setmelanotide	0.1 nM to 100 nM
ATP	20, 50, 100 µM

2.15 Measurement of potassium ion uptake

Human U373 astrogloma cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 in a clear 96 well cell culture plate with Dulbecco's modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (supplemented with 7.5mM glucose, 10% v/v FBS, 2 % v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) and incubated overnight at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. The next day, DMEM was removed, and cells were washed with 0.01 M phosphate buffered saline (PBS) which was then replaced with 2.5mM glucose serum free DMEM for 30 minutes at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. Following this, as per the manufacturer's instructions, the loading buffer was made 20 minutes before use and cells were incubated with 50µL of loading buffer for 1 hour at room temperature (RT) in the hood and protected from light with foil. During this time, 1mL of 50mM TI was prepared in a fume hood and primed into the PHERAstar FS microplate reader (priming is described in **section 2.14**). Then the assay buffer, melatonin II (MTII), SHU9119, Vehicle (ddH₂O) and adenosine triphosphate (ATP) working stocks were prepared in the cell culture hood for sterility. After 1 hour, the loading buffer was aspirated from wells and replaced with the assay buffer. Cells were then pre-treated with Vehicle or ligands (**Table 2.15-1**) for 5 or 15 minutes prior to fluorescence measurements. Basal relative fluorescence units (RFU) were first measured (Excitation 485nm and Emission 520nm) for 10 seconds before cells were injected with TI+ (final well concentration 2mM) and RFU measured continually for 70 seconds. Data were exported from the machine into Excel file and normalised to the first baseline measurement (making it 1). The rate of change was then calculated.

Table 2.15-1 Ligands used for U373 astrogloma cell treatments for FluxOR assay

Compounds	Final well concentration
MTII	0.1 nM to 100 nM 500nM and 1 µM
SHU9119	1 µM
ATP	100 µM

2.16 Metabolic measurements

The Seahorse Bioscience XFe96 extracellular flux Analyzer (Agilent) was employed to assess changes in oxygen consumption rate (OCR) as an indicator of mitochondrial function and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) as a measure of glycolytic rate in the human U373 astroglioma cell line. Changes in cell metabolism were evaluated by exploring cell metabolism in different cell culture conditions (2.5mM and 25mM glucose conditions), following acute ligand injections or ligand pre-treatment and/or during induced cellular stress using two metabolic assays; the Mitochondrial Stress Test (MST) and Glycolysis Stress Test (GST), as detailed in **Chapter 5, section 5.4**. The assays were performed following the manufacturer's guidelines. **Figure 2.16-1** demonstrates the assays.

Metabolic Assays

Using Seahorse BioAnalyzers

Figure 2.16-1 Metabolic assays are used to measure mitochondrial and glycolytic activity *in-vitro*

These assays measure oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) as methods proxies to assess key parameters of mitochondrial and glycolytic function in cells. Mitochondrial Stress Test: the dashed line indicates the compounds, oligomycin, FCCP, and a mix of rotenone and antimycin A, serially injected targeting complexes in the electron transport chain to allow calculation of the following parameters: basal respiration, ATP-linked respiration, proton leak, maximal respiration, spare respiratory capacity, and non-mitochondrial respiration. For the Glycolysis Stress Test parameters that can be calculated are glycolysis, glycolytic capacity, glycolytic reserve, and non-glycolytic acidification rate. The dashed lines indicate where drug injections occur. Glucose fuels glycolysis. Oligomycin inhibits ATP synthase in the mitochondria resulting in an increased dependence on glycolysis. 2-DG is a competitive inhibitor of glucose shutting down glycolysis. Figure from Biorender template with some modifications by me.

2.16.1 Seahorse metabolic experiments in different glucose conditions

Human U373 astrogloma cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well in a seahorse XFe96 cell culture microplates in 200 μ L DMEM supplemented with 7.5 mM glucose or DMEM D5671 supplemented with 25 mM glucose (both supplemented 10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine). The four corner wells were not seeded with cells and were left for background measurements with only 200 μ L DMEM. The plate was incubated at 37°C 5% overnight. On the same day, a 1M stock solution of 2DG (from Agilent kit; used as a positive control) was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount in distilled water. The assay medium was prepared using the seahorse assay XF medium and supplemented as appropriate to create each experimental conditioned media (**Table 2.16-1**). Assay media were stored in the refrigerator and used for washing steps, drug preparation, and as vehicle controls on the day of experimentation. The seahorse XFe96 sensor cartridges were hydrated with sterile water and placed overnight at 37°C in a non-CO₂ incubator with the seahorse XF calibrant and utility plate. The Seahorse BioAnalyzer was started and set to 37°C a day before the measurement for calibration purposes. On the day of experimentation, the XF calibrant, hydrated cartridge and utility plate were removed from the non-CO₂ incubator, and ddH₂O was aspirated from the plate and replaced with 200 μ L XF calibrant.

For drug pre-treatments: Ligands were prepared in the pre-made seahorse assay medium in either 2.5 mM glucose or 25mM glucose (**Table 2.16-1**) to achieve a final concentration of 1nM, 1 μ M MTII and 50mM 2DG. Then 180 μ L of each was added to cells in wells according to plate layout and incubated for five or twenty-four hours at 37 °C 5% CO₂ (assay medium was added in the 4 wells with no cells). After treatment, conditioned assay media in cell culture was aspirated, and cells were washed with 2.5mM or 25mM glucose-supplemented seahorse assay medium, and wells were topped up with 180 μ L of 2.5mM or 25mM assay media to each group. For measurements of basal metabolism in different glucose conditions, the Vehicle groups were used to compare changes in basal metabolism. The cell culture plate was then placed in the non-CO₂

incubator to de-gas for 1 hour, then placed in the Seahorse Bioanalyzer and OCR and ECAR were measured for 1.5 hours (10 cycles).

For acute drug injections and basal metabolic measurements: The same method was applied as above for basal metabolism experiments except with the addition of ligand treatments. In these experiments, the seahorse injection ports were loaded with ligands to achieve the final desired concentrations (**Table 2.16-2**). Basal metabolism was measured for five cycles, before ligands were injected into their corresponding wells with continuous real time measurement for up to 10 cycles. Once the measurements were complete for basal and acute metabolic experiments, the assay media was carefully removed and 100 μ L of 50mM sodium hydroxide was added per well, the plate was wrapped with parafilm and kept overnight for cell lysis in 4°C.

Table 2.16-1 Seahorse XF Media composition for the two glucose concentrations used

Substrates	Final concentration in plate	
Glucose	2.5mM	25mM
Sodium Pyruvate	2.5mM	2.5mM
L-glutamine	2mM	2mM

Table 2.16-2 Final concentrations of ligands made up in supplemented XF assay media for pre-treatments and acute drug injections

Ligands: Final Concentrations in wells	2.5mM glucose or 25mM glucose XF media
Vehicle	Assay media
MTII	1 μ M or 1nM
2DG	50M

2.16.1.1 Protein quantification for normalisation of metabolism studies

Following metabolic measurements and cell lysate collection from the human U373 astrogloma cell line, the protein was quantified using a Bradford Protein Assay. Cell lysates were thawed on ice. Using a clear 96 well plate, bovine serum albumin (BSA) was added ranging from 0-3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in triplicates along with 1 μL of the same lysis buffer (sodium hydroxide) used for cell lysate collection to create a standard curve. 50 μL of cell lysate samples were then added per well in triplicate. The Bradford reagent was diluted with double distilled H_2O (ddH_2O) at a ratio of 1:5, and 200 μL was added per well. Plates were shaken at 300 RPM for 300 seconds, and absorbance was measured at 595 nm using the Pherastar FS plate reader. Data were then normalised on the Seahorse Wave software.

2.16.2 Cell culture and preparation of the Mitochondrial Stress Test (MST)

Human U373 cells were seeded at 4×10^4 in 7.5mM glucose supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) in the Seahorse 96 well plates and incubated overnight at 37°C 5% CO₂. The cartridge was hydrated with ddH₂O and placed in the no-CO₂ incubator with the XF calibrant to degas overnight. The Seahorse BioAnalyzer was opened and set to 37°C to calibrate overnight. The next day, cell DMEM was aspirated, and cells were pre-treated with ligands (Vehicle or 1nM MTII or 1nM Setmelanotide) prepared in 2.5mM glucose serum free DMEM (D11966) and incubated for 5 hours. Then, DMEM was aspirated, and cells were washed with 2.5mM supplemented assay media and loaded with fresh 2.5mM glucose assay media. The cell plate was then placed in the non-CO₂ incubator to degas for one hour. The water from the cartridge was aspirated and replaced with XF calibrant. The MST compounds were resuspended in XF supplemented assay media and loaded into cartridge ports. The cartridge was then calibrated in the Seahorse Bioanalyzer. Then, the assay was ran as detailed in **Chapter 5, section 5.4**. After the assay was complete, 50mM sodium hydroxide was added per well and plate was stored in -20°C pending Bradford assay and data normalisation.

2.16.3 Cell culture and preparation of the Glycolysis Stress Test (GST)

Human U373 cells were seeded at 4×10^4 in 7.5mM glucose supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) in the Seahorse 96 well plates and incubated overnight at 37°C 5% CO₂. The cartridge was hydrated with ddH₂O and placed in a no-CO₂ incubator with the XF calibrant to degas overnight. The Seahorse BioAnalyzer was opened and set to 37°C to calibrate overnight. The next day, cell DMEM was aspirated, and cells were pre-treated with ligands (Vehicle or 1nM MTII or 1nM Setmelanotide) prepared in 2.5mM glucose serum-free DMEM (D11966) and incubated for 5 hours. Then, DMEM was aspirated, and cells were washed with 2.5mM

glucose-supplemented assay media and loaded with fresh assay media; the cell plate was placed in the non-CO₂ incubator to degas for one hour. The water from the cartridge was aspirated and replaced with an XF calibrant. The GST compounds were resuspended in XF-supplemented assay media and loaded into cartridge ports. The cartridge was then calibrated in the Seahorse BioAnalyzer. Then, the assay was ran as detailed in **Chapter 5**. After the assay was complete, 50mM sodium hydroxide was added per well and plate was stored in -20°C pending Bradford assay and data normalisation as in **section 2.16.1.1**.

2.16.4 Intracellular ATP measurements

Using the ATPlite Luminescence Assay System, intracellular ATP was measured in human U373 astrogloma cells. Cells were seeded at 4×10^3 per well in a white 96-well plate in 7.5mM glucose-supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) overnight at 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator. On the day of experimentation, the DMEM was aspirated, and cells were washed with 0.01% M PBS and replaced with 2.5mM glucose serum free DMEM. Cells were then treated with ligands (Vehicle, 1nM MTII or 50mM/1 μ M 2DG/Oligo) for 15 minutes or 5 hours, then cells were washed with PBS and replaced with lysis buffer and DMEM. Then the assay was performed as per manufacturers protocol with an ATP standard curve. The light produced was measured using the PHERAstar FS microplate reader with luminescence detection for 10 minutes. iATP levels were then measured as the concentration of ATP.

2.16.5 Extracellular L-Lactate quantification

Human U373 astrogloma cells were seeded at a density of 2.1×10^5 cells per well in 6-well plates in 7.5mM glucose supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine). The following day, cells were washed once with XF assay media, then were pre-treated with ligands (Vehicle, 1nM MTII or no glucose – positive control) in 2.5mM glucose serum free DMEM for 5 hours in 37°C 5% CO₂. Cells were then washed with assay media and replaced with fresh assay media then incubated in a non-CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 1 hour. Assay media samples were collected, and lysis buffer was added, samples were then deproteinised according to the manufacturer's instructions (from Cayman Chemical). One volume of ice cold metaphosphoric acid was added to one volume of sample and incubated on ice for 5 minutes. Samples were centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 5 minutes at 4°C. Then, 50 µL of potassium carbonate was added to neutralise the acid, and the samples were centrifuged again at 10,000 x g for 5 minutes at 4°C to remove the resulting salts. The supernatant was collected to run the assay. The L-lactate standards were prepared, and the assay was performed per the manufacturer's instructions. Samples and standards were run in duplicates to enhance the accuracy of the results. After incubation, fluorescence was measured at 530-540 nm (excitation) and 585-590 nm (emission). Data were normalised by subtracting the blank standard from itself/other values and data were plotted against normalised standards of known concentrations. Extracellular L-lactate concentration was measured in µM.

2.16.6 TMRE Mitochondrial Membrane Potential Assay Kit (fluorometric)

The TMRE Mitochondrial Membrane Potential Assay Kit (Abcam, ab287864, fluorometric) from Abcam was used to assess mitochondrial membrane potential in human U373 cells. Cells were seeded at 4×10^4 cells per well in a 96 well plate in 7.5mM glucose-supplemented DMEM (10% v/v FBS, 2% v/v penicillin/streptomycin and 8 mM L-glutamine) and incubated overnight at 37°C 5% CO₂. On the day of experimentation, ligands were prepared in 2.5mM glucose serum-free media. TMRE was made up in the provided assay buffer. Cells media was aspirated, and cells were pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for 15 minutes or five hours. FCCP (10 μM), was added 15 minutes before then all wells were added with TMRE (200nM) (except no TMRE stain control) for 15 minutes at 37°C 5% CO₂. Cells were then washed with assay buffer and replaced with fresh assay buffer as per manufacturers protocol and fluorescence (excitation/emission 549/575nm) was measured using the PHERAstar plate reader.

2.17 Statistics and data analysis

Experimental replicates were considered independent cell cultures. For example, n=3 is from three independent cell cultures. Technical replicates were considered experimental replicates of the same sample.

Data were analysed using the GraphPad Prism 6 program (Graph Pad Software, San Diego, CA, USA) and shown as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). To determine the statistically significant differences between groups or time points, an Unpaired t-test was used for two groups, and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess statistical significance between two or more groups with one experimental parameter; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001, ****p< 0.0001, ns; not significant. The threshold for statistical significance was set as p<0.05. Outliers were checked with GraphPad Prism using the robust regression and outlier removal (ROUT) method (Q=1%), and any identified statistically significant outliers were removed from the dataset.

The Agilent Seahorse Analytics was used to analyse the Seahorse experiments. Seahorse data were first normalised in the Seahorse Wave software and then imported into the Agilent Seahorse Analytics to analyse the parameters inferred from the Mitochondrial Stress Test and the Glycolysis Stress Test. Data from the Agilent Seahorse Analytics software were then exported into GraphPad Prism for statistical analysis, as mentioned above.

2.18 Materials

Table 2.18-1 Equipment / machinery used

Instrument	Supplier
PHERASTAR FS microplate reader	BMG LABTECH
Leica Microsystems TCS SP8 confocal microscope	Leica
Seahorse XFe96 Analyser	Agilent
Mini-PROTEAN tetra vertical hand-cast protein electrophoresis systems	Bio-Rad
Odyssey CLx imaging system	Li-Cor Biosciences
GelMax Imager	Bio-Rad
CellDrop	DeNovix
SimpliAmp Thermal cycler	Applied Biosystems ThermoFisher Scientific
BD Accuri C6 Plus Flow Cytometer	BD Biosciences
Nanodrop 2000c Spectrophotometer	ThermoFisher Scientific

Table 2.18-2 List of consumables used

Consumables / Assays	Supplier	Catalogue number
0.1% Tween 20 detergent (TBST)	Merck Millipore	P2287
0.2µM filter	Sarstedt	83.1826.001
6 well plates	Sarstedt	83.392
60mm dishes	Sarstedt	83.3901
70 µM sterile cell strainer	Fisher Scientific	11597522
96 well plates	Starlab	E2996-1600
Acrylamide 30%	Fisher Scientific	1548099
Agarose	Fisher Scientific	10688973
APS	Sigma-Aldrich	A3678
ATP LITE 300 Assay Kit	PerkinElmer	6016943
Benzamidine	Merck Millipore	12072
Bio-Rad protein assay dye reagent concentrate	Bio-Rad	5000006
BioTrace Nitrocellulose	VWR	732-3031
Bovine serum albumin (BSA)	VWR	0332-100G
Bromophenol blue	Merck Millipore	B5525
Cryovials	Sarstedt	72.379
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	Merck Millipore	D2650-5X5ML
DMEM High glucose	Merck Millipore	D5671
DreamTaq Hot Start Green Master Mix	Fisher Scientific	15689374
Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) no glucose	Fisher Scientific	D11966
Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)	Merck Millipore	EDA-100G
Fluo-4 Direct Calcium Assay Kit	ThermoFisher Scientific Invitrogen	F10471

Fluorishield mounting medium with DAPI	Abcam	AB104139-20ML
Foetal Bovine Serum	Fisher Scientific	10270106
GelRed Nucleic Acid Gel Stain, 10,000XG	Cambridge Bioscience	88495
GeneRuler 1 kb Plus DNA Ladder	ThermoFisher Scientific	SM1331
Glucose	Merck Millipore	G7021
Glycerol	Merck Millipore	G5516-100ML
Glycine	Melford	G0709
Glycolysis Stress Test	Agilent	103020-100
Hanks Balanced Salt Solution	Fisher Scientific	11530476
HEPES	Merck	H0-887-100ML
High-Capacity RNA-to-cDNA kit	ThermoFisher Scientific	4387406
L-glutamine (200mM)	Fisher Scientific	11500626
L-Lactate assay kit	Cayman Chemical	700510-96 wells
Methanol	Merck Millipore	34860-2.5L-M
Mitochondrial Stress Test	Agilent	103015-100
PBS tablets	Fisher Scientific	10209252
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Fisher Scientific	11528876
Gibco DMEM, no glucose, no glutamine, no phenol red (PRF)	Fisher Scientific	12307263
Phenylmethylsulphonyl Fluoride (PMSF)	Merck	P7626
Precision Plus Protein Dual Colour Standards	Bio-Rad	1610374
Primers	IDT	orders only
Propidium iodide (PI)	Merck Millipore	P4864-10ML

Poly-L-lysine hydrobromide	Merck Millipore	P1274-100MG
RNase-free DNase set	Qiagen	79254
Rneasy Plus Mini Kit (50)	Qiagen	74134
Seahorse XF DMEM medium, pH 7.4	Agilent	103575-100
Seahorse XFe96 FluxPak	Agilent	102416-100
Semi-dried milk		
Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	Melford	B2008
Sodium Hydroxide	Fisher Scientific	S/4920/53
Sodium orthovanadate (NaVO ₄)	Merck Millipore	S6508
Sodium pyruvate	Merck Millipore	P2256-100G
Sterile disposable scalpel	Fisher Scientific	11798343
Sucrose	Melford	S0809
T25 flask	Sarstedt	83.3910.002
T75 flask	Sarstedt	83.39.11.002
TEMED	Merck Millipore	T7024
The FluxOR Potassium Ion Channel Assay	Fisher Scientific	10646474
TMRE Mitochondrial Membrane Potential Assay Kit (fluorometric)	Abcam	Ab287864
Tris base	Melford	B2005
Tris-Acetate-EDTA (TAE) 10X solution	Fisher Bioreagents	BP1335-1
Trypsin 0.05% EDTA	Fisher Scientific	11590626
XF calibrant	Agilent	100840-000
β-Mercaptoethanol	Merck Millipore	M3148

Table 2.18-3 Software use

Software	Supplier
Benchling	Benchling
Ensemble	Ensemble
UCSC <i>in silico</i> PCR	University of California Santa Cruz
Primer3Plus	Primer3
ImageStudio Lite (v 5.2)	Li-COR Biosciences
PowerPoint	Microsoft
Excel	Microsoft
Prism (v10.0.2)	GraphPad
BD C6Plus Software	BD Biosciences
Agilent Seahorse Analytics	Agilent
Wave Analysis Software	Agilent
Biorender	Biorender
Leica Acquisition Suite X	Leica

3 MELANOCORTIN RECEPTOR EXPRESSION AND DOWNSTREAM SIGNALLING PATHWAYS IN ASTROCYTES

From this chapter onward, all melanocortin receptors (MC1R to MC5R) will be abbreviated as MCRs or referred to their individual abbreviated name, and the ligand Melanotan II will be abbreviated as MTII.

3.1 Introduction

Melanocortin receptors (MCRs) are G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) that regulate a wide range of physiological processes, including energy homeostasis, inflammation, and neuroprotection, dysfunction in MCR signalling has been implicated in various pathophysiological conditions (Fatima et al., 2022; Yeo et al., 2021). It has long been accepted that MC3R and MC4R are the predominant MCRs expressed in the CNS (Liu et al., 2003; Cone, 2005; Tao, 2010; You et al., 2016; Lotta et al., 2019). However, emerging evidence has demonstrated the presence of MC5R (Gantz et al., 1994; Simamura et al., 2011; Shukla et al., 2015; Kamermans et al., 2019) and MC1R in the brain (Bittencourt et al., 1992; Saito et al., 1999; Hervieu et al., 2000; Kamermans et al., 2019), expanding the scope of melanocortin receptor research in neurophysiology. These discoveries suggest a more complex role of MCRs in CNS regulation than previously understood, warranting further exploration into their specific cellular roles.

3.1.1 MCR signalling pathways: known mechanisms

MCRs signal through diverse pathways, including canonical G protein-mediated signalling as mentioned in **Chapter 1**. However, they also have biased signalling where they can signal via multiple pathways, and G protein-independent mechanisms. These pathways regulate intracellular processes such as metabolism, calcium dynamics, and transcriptional activation. In addition, MCR ligands have different affinities and potencies at each receptor,

and ligand binding results in activation of diverse signalling pathways (Yeo et al., 2021; Laiho and Murray, 2022).

Basal signalling: There is some published evidence that human and mouse MC1R, MC4R and MC5R exhibit constitutive cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) activity in the absence of ligands *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* (De Jonghe et al., 2011; Kay et al., 2013; Link et al., 2020; Nijenhuis et al., 2001; Ollmann et al., 1997; Slominski et al., 2005; Srinivasan et al., 2004). Some report basal cAMP activity on human MC3R (Tao, 2007) whilst others report no activity (Yang and Tao, 2016). This constitutive basal cAMP activity was first demonstrated when investigating the mechanism of hair pigmentation in the absence of POMC peptides: POMC knockout mice maintain a normal coat colour even without endogenous ligands, whereas MC1R knockout mice had yellow fur (Slominski et al., 2005). This suggests that the constitutive activity of MC1R in the absence of endogenous ligands is sufficient to maintain coat colour. Subsequently published evidence demonstrated MC1R, MC3R, MC4R and MC5R have constitutive cAMP receptor activity without application of MCR ligands (Ollmann et al., 1997; Nijenhuis, Oosterom and Adan, 2001; Srinivasan et al., 2004; Slominski et al., 2005; Manuscript, 2012; Kay et al., 2013; Link et al., 2020; De Jonghe et al., 2011; Kay et al., 2013; Link et al., 2020; Nijenhuis et al., 2001; Ollmann et al., 1997; Slominski et al., 2005; Srinivasan et al., 2004; Tao, 2007). However, the constitutive cAMP activity remains debated due to conflicting findings regarding some MCRs in their wild type versus mutant states (Kay et al., 2013; Tao, 2007; Yang & Tao, 2016). These discrepancies may be attributed to species, cell types, and context dependency differences.

Other signalling pathways: MCR ligands acting on MCRs are well known for their activation of the Gs-PKA (protein kinase A) pathway through cAMP production, but they also couple to a variety of other signalling pathways, including Gq-PLC (phospholipase C), Gi/O, AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase), and ERK1/2 (extracellular-regulated kinase 1/2), as well as other biased signalling and G protein independent processes (Breit et al., 2011; Büch et al., 2009; Damm et al., 2012; Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2021; Mountjoy et al., 2001; Newman et al., 2006). ERK1/2 is a key kinase downstream of GPCRs, playing critical roles in cellular processes such as

proliferation, migration, stress, and metabolism (Patten et al., 2007; Sutton et al., 2005). Evidence from multiple studies report ERK1/2 phosphorylation downstream of MC4R (Chai et al., 2006; Damm et al., 2012; Daniels et al., 2003; Glas et al., 2016; Patten et al., 2007; Sutton et al., 2005; Vaglini et al., 2018; Vongs et al., 2004), MC1R and MC3R (Begrache et al., 2012; Chai et al., 2007; Montero-Melendez et al., 2015), and MC5R activity (Rodrigues et al., 2009, 2012). As detailed in **Chapter 1**, SHU9119 is a synthetic potent antagonist of MC3R and MC4R (Hruby et al., 1995) (TOCRIS: IC₅₀ values are 0.23 and 0.06 nM respectively) with equal potency at both receptors (Schiöth et al., 1999). SHU9119 has partial agonist activity at MC5R (EC₅₀ = 0.12 nM) and MC1R (Hruby et al., 1995; Schiöth et al., 1999). Recent data suggest that in addition to partial agonism at MC1R and MC5R, SHU9119 has weak agonism at MC3R and MC4R, correlating with the absence of complete antagonism (Gimenez et al., 2022). Sutton et al report increases in ERK1/2 phosphorylation induced by MTII, which SHU9119 blocks as a result of receptor inhibition in brain rat tissue (Sutton et al., 2005). In addition, pre-treatment with the agonist NDP-MSH induces ERK1/2 phosphorylation that was then blocked with SHU9119 pre-treatment in HEK293 cells overexpressing MC3R, and GT1-1 cells expressing endogenous MC4R (Chai et al., 2006, 2007). A highly simplified illustration of ERK1/2 signalling can be seen in **Figure 3.1.1-1**.

Figure 3.1.1-1 Highly simplified schematic of the ERK1/2 signalling pathway

The four classes of G proteins, defined by the Gs, Gi, Gq11 and G11/12 families, of which one or more may regulate the MAPK ERK1/2 cascade following MCR activation (ERK1/2 mitogen-activated protein kinase MAPK). However, when melanocortin receptor agonists bind to MC1R, MC3R, MC4R or MC5R to modulate the ERK1/2 signalling pathway, it is unclear whether this is via direct Ras-Raf-MEK1/2 and ERK1/2 MAPK. Activation of ERK1/2 is implicated in physiological and pathophysiological conditions. ERK1/2 is a target for many neurodegenerative diseases, as well as inflammation and obesity.

Beyond ERK1/2, the PLC signalling pathway is also of importance for modulation of intracellular calcium levels (iCa^{2+}) in astrocytes. Calcium mobilisation influences astrocytic functions such as neurotransmitter uptake and neuroinflammatory responses (Navarrete et al., 2012). While PLC signalling downstream of MC4R has been demonstrated in neurons, its relevance in astrocytes remains underexplored. Setmelanotide is reported to be biased towards MC4R, activating PLC likely via Gq/11 coupling (Clément et al., 2018; Collet et al., 2017; Heyder et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2009), yet some report it to have higher potency for cAMP formation, and weaker effect on ERK1/2 phosphorylation (Clément et al., 2020; Hammad et al., 2022). These studies have focused solely on MC4R in non-astroglial cells. Setmelanotide formerly known as RM-493 or BIM-22493 is a synthetic cyclic peptide that binds to human MC4R with high affinity and with lower affinity at MC1R, MC3R and MC5R (Durek et al., 2018; Kanti et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2009; Palmer et al., 2017). Multiple mechanisms of calcium mobilisation in astrocytes are known, yet the key mechanism known is via the PLC-IP3 (inositol 1, 4, 5-trisphosphate) signalling pathway leading to release of calcium stores in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) (Durkee et al., 2019; Navarrete et al., 2012; Parpura et al., 2011; Petravicz et al., 2008; Takata et al., 2011). Increases in calcium via the ER can occur spontaneously or through G protein-coupled receptors (GPCR) such as Gq and Gi/O mediated pathways (Durkee et al., 2019). In astrocytes, stimulation of GPCRs through the Gi/O G protein activates astrocytes and lead to increases in Ca^{2+} levels in-vivo (Durkee et al., 2019). Multiple studies report increases in iCa^{2+} downstream of MCRs in rodent cell lines, mast cells and human HEK293 cells in response to melanocortin ligands (Berger, 1986; Jain et al., 2018; Kim et al., 1997; Konda et al., 1994; Kumar et al., 2021; Langouche et al., 2001; Mountjoy et al., 2001; Newman et al., 2006; Roudbaraki et al., 1999). Newman et al. reported increases of iCa^{2+} levels through Gq-PLC when MC4R was activated in GT1-1 cell (Newman et al., 2006). Setmelanotide formerly known as RM-493 or BIM-22493 is a synthetic cyclic peptide that binds to human MC4R with high affinity and with lower affinity at MC1R, MC3R and MC5R (Durek et al., 2018; Kanti et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2009; Palmer et al., 2017).

whilst PKA has been associated with the upregulation of various transcription factors as mentioned in **Chapter 1** (Caruso et al., 2012; Ramírez et al., 2015; Saba et al., 2019).

3.1.1.1 Biased and G Protein-Independent Signalling:

MCRs signal through non-canonical pathways, including regulation by β -arrestin-mediated mechanisms (Abrisqueta et al., 2013; Fatima et al., 2022; Natarajan & Berk, 2006; Nyan et al., 2008; Rodrigues et al., 2012; S. Sharma et al., 2020; Shenoy & Lefkowitz, 2005). MC4R can also couple, independent of G proteins, to the inwardly rectifying potassium channel Kir 7.1 (Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; Litt et al., 2018). To date, no other investigations on other MCR subtype coupling to Kir channels have highlighted a gap in knowledge, and the role of these pathways in astrocytes is largely unknown but may offer additional layers of regulatory complexity.

3.1.1.2 ERK1/2 signalling following MCR activation

The alpha (α) and beta gamma-subunits ($\beta\gamma$) of G proteins mainly regulate MAPK pathways through various intermediates, including receptor tyrosine kinases, β -arrestins, EPAC1/2 (exchange proteins activated by cyclic AMP), and small GTPases (Lotta et al., 2019; Natarajan & Berk, 2006). Although the precise G proteins and downstream effectors leading to ERK1/2 signalling remain unknown, cAMP, primarily believed to activate PKA, also increases ERK1/2 phosphorylation in several MCR contexts (Gantz et al., 1993; Khong et al., 2001; Mo & Tao, 2013). There are differences in ERK1/2 activation across MCR subtypes. Although cAMP increases are observed following activation of MC1R, MC3R, MC4R, and MC5R, cAMP-mediated ERK1/2 signalling is inconsistent. For example, in hypothalamic cells, MC1R and MC5R do not facilitate ERK1/2 cascade activation through cAMP (Glas et al., 2016). Instead, ERK1/2 activation occurs via EPAC1/2 and PI3K-regulated mechanisms in specific cell models (Chai et al., 2007; Ramírez et al., 2015). In various physiological contexts, ERK1/2 signalling can lead to CREB phosphorylation, regulating neuronal circuits and body functions (Chelakkot et al., 2023; Glas et al., 2016). β -arrestins modulate MCR signalling to terminate signalling and promote endocytosis (Abrisqueta et al., 2013; Breit et al., 2006).

3.1.1.3 Implications of MCR mutations on ERK1/2 signalling

Mutations in MCRs can result in signalling bias, affecting physiology or pathophysiology. For instance, some MC4R mutations lead to reduced cAMP production, which is associated with weight gain, whereas gain-of-function MC4R mutations are linked to increased β -arrestin recruitment and lean phenotypes (Lotta et al., 2019). Disruptions in MAPK ERK1/2 signalling due to MC4R mutations can cause obesity (He & Tao, 2014).

3.1.1.4 ERK1/2's role in physiological and pathological conditions

In the CNS, ERK1/2 is vital for synaptic plasticity, brain development, repair, and memory formation (Sun & Nan, 2017). Dysregulation of ERK1/2 is associated with various diseases, including cancer, neurodegenerative diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and inflammatory disorders (Gilbert et al., 2021; Inamdar et al., 2010). The complexity and diverse findings relating to how MCR signalling impacts ERK1/2 activity are summarised in **Figure 3.1.1-2**, which illustrates what is known about MCR ERK1/2 signalling and the potential involvement of the other effectors, respectively.

Figure 3.1.1-2 Schematic of potential pathways leading to ERK1/2 activation based on what is known about MCR signalling

These possibilities are based on evidence from collated evidence on MCR ERK1/2 signalling from published literature. Following melanocortin receptor activation by an agonist, the MAPK pathway (involving ERK1/2) may be directly activated, resulting in Ras, Raf, MEK1/2 activation and increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation which influences physiological and pathophysiological conditions depending on context. It is also possible that upon MCR activation, there is crosstalk with the receptor tyrosine kinase in activation of the MAPK pathway. A possible crosstalk between cAMP and ERK1/2 and a potential β -

arrestin / ERK1/2 complex with Gai or Gas protein. ERK1/2 activation may also impact mTOR signalling. Figure created using Biorender.

3.1.1.5 Other signalling pathways downstream of MCRs

The list of signalling pathways downstream of MCRs is extensive. Beyond the signalling pathways I had already introduced in the previous sections, pathways involved in cell metabolism are of interest, given some of the focus of this thesis is on cell metabolism. The AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1a and mTOR signalling pathways were also reported to be activated downstream of MCRs (AMP-activated protein kinase, silencing information regulator 2 related enzyme 1; peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ co-activator 1 α ; mTOR: mammalian target of rapamycin) (Chai et al., 2010; Chen et al., 2018; Tanaka et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2017). However, the G protein involved in activating these pathways remains unknown, and whether these are mediated separately or interlinked with the other signalling pathways described above is unknown. For example, there is a link between ERK1/2 phosphorylation and mTOR activity in the neuronal MC4R expressing GT1-1 cell line (Chai et al., 2010).

3.1.2 Importance of MCR signalling in astrocytes

Despite their centrality in CNS functions, the specific roles and signalling pathways of MCRs in astrocytes remain poorly understood.

Astrocytes play a pivotal role in maintaining CNS homeostasis, supporting neuronal function, and modulating neuroimmune responses. Identifying how MCRs influence astrocytic functions is crucial to understanding their contribution to CNS health and disease. Published evidence suggests that MCR activation in astrocytes may regulate intracellular signalling cascades, including those associated with cAMP/PKA, MAPK/ERK1/2, and PLC pathways (Ramírez et al., 2015; Evans et al., 1984). However, there is limited data on the specific mechanisms and physiological consequences of MCR signalling in astrocytes, representing a significant gap in knowledge.

Understanding MCR signalling in astrocytes is critical for several reasons: **CNS Homeostasis:** Astrocytes are key regulators of CNS homeostasis, and their interactions with MCRs may influence metabolic and neuroimmune responses. **Dysregulation of MCR signalling in astrocytes could contribute to conditions such as neuroinflammation and metabolic disorders.** **Therapeutic Potential:** MCR ligands have shown promise in treating obesity, inflammation, and neurodegenerative diseases. Defining their effects on astrocytes could expand their therapeutic applications and inform drug design strategies targeting MCRs.

3.1.3 What is known about MCR expression in astrocytes

Astrocytes play a pivotal role in maintaining CNS homeostasis and supporting neuronal function, but their interaction with MCRs remains underexplored. Published evidence has shown the presence of endogenous MCRs in astrocytes, particularly in rodent models, human glioblastoma cells, and human brain tissue (Caruso et al., 2007, 2012; Selkirk et al., 2007; Kamermans et al., 2019; Xu, Yan, et al., 2020). Among these, MC4R has been the most extensively studied in astrocytes, although discrepancies exist regarding its exact role and signalling pathways (Carniglia et al., 2013; Ramírez et al., 2015). Evidence for MC1R expression in astrocytes is also emerging but remains limited (Xu et al., 2020).

3.1.4 What is known about MCR signalling in astrocytes

Although several studies have examined MCR signalling in neurons, data on MCR signalling in astrocytes remains sparse and somewhat inconsistent. For instance, Ramírez et al. (2015) demonstrated ERK1/2 phosphorylation in astrocytes following stimulation with MC4R ligands NDP-MSH and α -MSH, yet their study did not explore the expression of other MCR subtypes (Ramírez et al., 2015). Additionally, early studies demonstrated modulation of cAMP activity by melanocortin peptides in cultured astrocytes (Evans et al., 1984; van Calker et al., 1983), while more recent work has indicated PKA activation in response to endogenous MC4R signalling (Caruso et al., 2012). There is no evidence linking MCR-mediated PLC signalling to increases in intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}), which is significant because PLC signalling is known to elevate iCa^{2+} levels, a key regulator of astrocyte function. (Henneberger et al., 2010; Khakh & McCarthy, 2015; Lia et al., 2021; Volterra et al., 2014). Although, a study in rat astrocytes demonstrated increases in iCa^{2+} are regulated via MC4R activation (Climent et al., 2000). However, PLC phosphorylation upstream of iCa^{2+} modulation was not investigated in astrocytes.

Therefore, comprehensive investigations into how melanocortins activate signalling pathways such as PKA, PLC and ERK1/2 in astrocytes are still needed. Importantly, the diversity of MCR signalling pathways highlights their functional versatility and suggests that astrocytic MCR signalling may contribute to various CNS processes, including stress response and neuroinflammation

3.2 Rationale and Hypothesis

Understanding MCR signalling in astrocytes is critical, given their central role in brain physiology and neuroinflammation. The diverse coupling of MCRs to multiple G protein pathways, and their subsequent modulation of intracellular calcium levels (iCa^{2+}), suggest that astrocytes may respond dynamically to MCR ligands. However, most previous studies have relied on overexpression systems in non-astrocytic cells, leaving the native signalling profiles of MCRs in astrocytes largely unexplored.

3.3 Aims

- 1) Investigate endogenous melanocortin receptor one to five (*MC1R-MC5R*) gene expression in the human U373 cancer cell line, known as the U373 astroglioma or astroglia cell model, and in neonatal mouse primary cortical astrocytes.
- 2) Determine if downstream signalling pathways (ERK1/2, PKA and PLC) are activated in astrocytes following pharmacological treatment with melanocortin ligands

A diagram below outlines the initial hypothesis of this study (**Figure 3.3-1**): that all MCRs are expressed in astrocytes in culture and their activation results in increases in ERK1/2 and/or PKA/PLC signalling.

Figure 3.3-1 Simplified hypothetical model of some effectors involved in signalling pathways downstream of MCR pharmacological modulation in astrocytes. The upstream effectors were not investigated. Figure created in Biorender.

3.4 Methods

1) Gene expression: Mouse and human primers (respectively) against *mc1r* to *mc5r* were designed using Benchling (**Chapter 2, section 2.7**) targeting each gene. Prior to exploring MCR gene expression in astrocytes, I validated the PCR primers I designed using mouse brain tissue. I initially explored gene expression of neuroendocrine receptors in the mouse brain and primary mouse cortical and hypothalamic astrocytes using reverse transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR). Endogenous gene expression of *mc1r* to *mc5r* was then performed using reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) in the human U373 astrogloma cell line, mouse brain tissue and primary cortical and hypothalamic astrocytes obtained from neonatal mouse pups. Mouse and human primers (respectively) against *mc1r* to *mc5r* were designed using Benchling (**Chapter 2, section 2.7**) targeting each gene.

2) Signalling pathways: To assess signalling pathways downstream of endogenous MCRs in astrocytes, U373 astrogloma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes were pre-treated for 15 minutes with increasing concentrations of MTII or Setmelanotide (0.1 – 100nM) cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM) or standard DMEM high glucose concentrations (25mM) (**Chapter 2, section 2.11, 2.12 & 2.13**). Cells were then lysed for protein collection, followed by immunoblotting of phosphorylated and total ERK1/2. Some of the same samples were used as for ERK1/2 detection for PKA and PLC. To investigate whether SHU9119 can inhibit any phosphorylation of ERK1/2 and PKA associated with receptor constitutive activity and potentially inhibit phosphorylation of ERK1/2 induced by MTII, U373 astrogloma cells were pre-treated with 1µM SHU9119 for 30 minutes before addition of MTII (1nM) for 15 minutes. Vehicle and ATP (100µM) were used as negative and positive controls, respectively. Cells were then lysed for protein collection, followed by immunoblotting. GAPDH was used as a loading control in experiments.

3) Optimisation of positive controls for signalling experiments: ATP pre-treatment (100µM) was used successfully as a positive control to induce phosphorylation of ERK1/2 but did not result in increased phosphorylation of

PKA in U373 astroglioma cells (data not shown). To help ensure the validity of the results, a positive control was required to determine whether U373 astroglioma cells can signal via the PKA pathway. In addition, since I also investigated protein lipase C β 3 at Ser537 (PLC β 3) phosphorylation downstream of melanocortin signalling, I explored potential pharmacological positive controls for both pathways (**Chapter 2, section 2.11, 2.12 & 2.13**).

8-Bromo-cAMP (TOCRIS) is a cell-permeable cAMP analogue activating PKA. m-3M3FBS (TOCRIS) is an activator of phospholipase C (PLC), and both were tested as potential positive controls for pathway activation in U373 astroglioma cells. Cells were treated for 15 minutes with 8-Bromo-cAMP (100 μ M), Vehicle (0.02% DMSO), m-3M3FBS (25 μ M), Vehicle (0.05% DMSO) followed by lysate collection and immunoblotting to detect phosphorylated PKA and PLC (**Chapter 2, section 2.11, 2.12 & 2.13**).

4) Cell viability: There are indications that conditioned medium in glioblastoma cell lines decreases their viability by modulating gene expression profiles (Torsvik et al., 2014; Yavuz, 2022). To ensure that U373 astroglioma cell viability was not decreased by the culture conditions or the concentrations of MTII, cell viability was measured by propidium iodide staining followed by flow cytometry (**Chapter 2, section 2.6**).

5) Purity of mouse cortical astrocytes: Before experimenting with mouse cortical astrocytes, it was essential to confirm the cells in the culture were astrocytes. Astrocytes express glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), a type III intermediate filament which forms part of the cell cytoskeleton. GFAP is a standardly used astrocyte marker in the context of *in-vitro* cell culture (Eng et al., 2000), so I validated the purity of the cells in culture with immunocytochemistry (ICC) for GFAP immunoreactivity. The cells were subjected to staining with DAPI, a nuclear stain for DNA, and antibodies against GFAP (for astrocytes) and IBA1 (for microglia). Following the ICC process, the immunoreactivity was visualised using a confocal microscope (**Chapter 2, section 2.3**).

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Validation of primers designed to detect neuroendocrine hormone receptors in the mouse brain

Neuroendocrine receptors cholecystokinin A and B receptor (*cckar-cckbr*), growth hormone secretagogue receptor (*ghsr*), leptin receptor (*lepr*) and melanocortin receptor 4 (*mc4r*) were expressed in mouse cortical and hypothalamic brain tissue, and primary mouse hypothalamic and cortical astrocytes (**Figure 3.5.1-1 A-D**). Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*gapdh*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*gfap*) were used as positive controls and were expressed in mouse brain tissue and mouse primary cortical astrocytes (**Figure 3.5.1-1 A-D**). All the PCR bands on the gels were of the predicted sizes based on their target binding sites (**Chapter 2, section 2.7**).

Figure 3.5.1-1 Expression of neuroendocrine hormone receptors in mouse brain tissue and mouse primary cortical and hypothalamic astrocytes

Reverse transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR) was used to detect amplified complementary deoxyribose nucleotide (cDNA) products from mouse **A**: hypothalamic brain tissue. **B**: mouse cortical brain tissue. **C**: mouse hypothalamic astrocytes. **D**: mouse cortical astrocytes, using PCR primers designed to detect central nervous system (CNS) receptors: cholecystikinin A/B receptor (*cckar-cckbr*), growth hormone secretagogue receptor (*ghsr*), leptin receptor (*lepr*) and melanocortin 4 receptor (*mc4r*). Positive controls were PCR primers for glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*gapdh*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*gfap*). L represents DNA ladder of 1Kb (Kilobases). H₂O and -CTRL represent negative controls; H₂O; distilled water; -CTRL consists of a master mix, random primers, and water without cDNA template (no template control). Representative images **A** and **B** are of three technical PCR replicates from the same brain tissue. **C** and **D** represent two independent repeated experiments from two independent cell cultures and two additional technical PCR replicates from the same cDNA.

3.5.2 MCRs were expressed in mouse brain tissue, cultured primary mouse cortical and the human U373 astroglioma cell line

U373 astroglioma cells expressed *mc1r*, *mc2r*, *mc3r* and *mc4r* but not *mc5r* (**Figure 3.5.2-1 D**). Positive controls glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*gapdh*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*gfap*) were also detected in mouse brain tissue, mouse primary cortical astrocytes and human U373 astroglioma cell line (**Figure 3.5.2-1 A-D**).

Figure 3.5.2-1 Expression of melanocortin receptors (MCRs) in mouse cortical and hypothalamic brain tissue, mouse primary cortical astrocytes, and the human U373 astroglioma cell line

Reverse transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR) was used to detect amplified cDNA products from **A**: mouse cortical brain tissue. **B**: mouse cortical astrocytes. **C**: mouse hypothalamic tissue. **D**: U373 astroglioma cell line, using primers designed to detect *mc1r-mc5r*, and positive controls glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*gapdh*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*gfap*). L represents DNA ladder of 1Kb (Kilobases). H₂O and -CTRL represent negative controls; H₂O; distilled water; -CTRL consists of a master mix, random primers, and water without cDNA template (no template control). Representative images **A** and **C** are of three PCR technical replicates from brain tissue. **B** and **D** represent two independent repeated experiments from two independent cell cultures and two additional technical PCR replicates from the same cDNA. Of note, the band sizes appear different in panel D as these were different primers used from those in panels A-C, designed against the human receptor sequences.

3.5.3 MTII pre-treatment resulted in increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells

MTII induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells compared to Vehicle at all concentrations of MTII tested (0.1nM *p= 0.0396; 1nM **p=0.0017, 10nM **p=0.0026, 100nM **p=0.076). Compared to Vehicle, ATP increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation (100µM ***p=0.0003) (**Figure 3.5.3-1 A&B**). This finding agrees with previously published work on MC4R activation increasing ERK1/2 phosphorylation in rat astrocytes (Ramírez et al., 2015).

Figure 3.5.3-1 U373 astrogloma cells showed increased phosphorylation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK1/2) kinase following Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment

U373 astrogloma cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes before treatment with melanotan II (MTII) (0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM) and adenosine triphosphate (ATP 100 μ M) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed, and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A:** Representative immunoblot of phospho-ERK1/2 (p-ERK1/2; Thr202/Tyr204), total ERK1/2, and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) as a loading control. **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-ERK1/2 (Thr202/Tyr204) and total ERK1/2 normalised as the ratio of p-ERK1/2 to total ERK1/2 and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated group B: One-way ANOVA compared to Vehicle treated cells; MTII 0.1nM *p= 0.0396; 1nM **p= 0.0017, 10nM **p= 0.0026, 100nM **p= 0.076; ATP ***p= 0.0003 (n=11 independent cell cultures). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

3.5.4 The effect of the MC3R/MC4R antagonist SHU9119 on MTII induced ERK1/2 signalling in U373 astroglioma cells

MCRs have constitutive activity, and I have shown that MTII-induced phosphorylation of ERK1/2 in the U373 astroglioma cell line (**Figure 3.5.3-1 A&B**). With visual observations, pre-treatment with SHU9119 (referred to as SHU or S in figures) seems to have returned ERK1/2 phosphorylation to baseline levels when compared with Vehicle (**Figure 3.5.4-1 A&B**). As expected, MTII pre-treatment induced increased phosphorylation of ERK1/2 compared with Vehicle *p=0.0499 and when compared with SHU9119 *p=0.0465 (**Figure 3.5.4-1 A&B**). Pre-treatment with SHU9119 inhibited MTII-induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation (represented as S/M in figures) compared to the effects observed with MTII pre-treatment alone *p=0.0462 (**Figure 3.5.4-1 A&B**). Again, it visually appears to return ERK1/2 phosphorylation to baseline when compared with SHU9119 or Vehicle only.

Figure 3.5.4-1 The effect of SHU9119 on baseline and Melanotan II (MTII) induced extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK1/2) phosphorylation in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to treatment with SHU9119 ($1\mu\text{M}$) for 30 minutes followed by MTII stimulation (1nM), Vehicle (ddH_2O) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP) ($100\mu\text{M}$) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed and protein was collected for immunoblotting.

A: Representative immunoblot of phosphorylated ERK1/2 (p-ERK1/2), and total ERK1/2. **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-ERK1/2 and total ERK1/2 normalised as the ratio of p-ERK1/2 to total ERK1/2 and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group. One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test; MTII * $p=0.0499$ compared to Vehicle, SHU * $p=0.0465$ compared to MTII, SHU/MTII (S/M) * $p=0.0462$ compared to MTII ($n=6-8$ independent cell cultures). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

3.5.5 Protein Kinase A (PKA) phosphorylation at Thr197 was not increased in U373 astroglioma cells following MTII pre-treatment

15 minutes of MTII pre-treatment did not promote phosphorylation of PKA C at Thr 197 at any concentration tested (0.1nM $p=0.9954$, 1nM $p=9890$, 10nM $p=9790$ and 100nM $p=0.9979$) (**Figure 3.5.5-1 A&B**). GAPDH was used as a loading control (**Figure 3.5.5-1 A&B**). This finding does not agree with previously published evidence on endogenous MC4R activation increasing PKA in rat primary astrocytes (Caruso et al., 2012).

Figure 3.5.5-1 Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment did not increase phosphorylation of Protein Kinase A (PKA) at Thr197 in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes before pre-treatment with MTII (0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed, and protein was collected for immunoblotting.

A: Representative immunoblot of Phospho-PKA C Thr197 (p-PKA C), total PKA and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) loading control. **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-PKA C and total PKA C normalised as the ratio of p-PKA C to total PKA C and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group (n=11 independent cell cultures). One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. MTII 0.1nM p=0.9954, 1nM p=0.9890, 10nM p=0.9790 and 100nM p=0.9979, all compared to the Vehicle treated group. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. ns= not statistically significant, p>0.05.

3.5.6 8-Bromo-cAMP and m-3M3FBS optimisation as potential positive controls for signalling experiments in U373 astroglioma cells

8 Bromo-cAMP did not phosphorylate PKA following 15 minutes of pre-treatment in U373 astroglioma cells (**Figure 3.5.6-1 top panel A&B**). To optimise further, I explored additional pre-treatment durations. I treated U373 astroglioma cells for 0, 30, 60 and 90 minutes with 8 Bromo-cAMP (100 μ M). 60 and 90 minutes of 8 Bromo-cAMP pre-treatment resulted in high variation between individual experimental replicates, and visually immunoblots showed 90 minutes appearing to reduce total and phospho-PKA to baseline (**Figure 3.5.6-1 middle panel C&D**). A pre-treatment time of 30 minutes resulted in statistically significant phosphorylation of PKA when analysed with an unpaired t-test * $p=0.0469$ (**Figure 3.5.6-1 middle panel C&E**).

m-3m3FBS (25 μ M) increased phosphorylated PLC β 3 at Ser537 in U373 astroglioma cells following 15-minute pre-treatment (**Figure 3.5.6-1 bottom panel F:G**). Unpaired t-test ** $p=0.0024$.

Figure 3.5.6-1 Positive control optimisation of 8-Bromo-cAMP and m-3MFBS in the U373 astrogloma cell line. U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to treatment with 8-Bromo-cAMP (100μM) or Vehicle (0.02% Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO)) for 15 minutes (top panel); 8-Bromo-cAMP time course (middle panel) and, m-3MFBS (25 μM) or Vehicle (0.05% DMSO) (bottom panel). A&C: Representative immunoblots of phospho protein kinase C (p-PKA C; Thr197) and total PKA. B, D & E: Densitometric analysis of p-PKA C and total PKA C normalised as the ratio of p-PKA C to total PKA C and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle treated control group (n=3 independent cell cultures). F: Representative immunoblot of phospho protein lipase C (p-PLC β3 at Ser537) and total PLC. G: Densitometric analysis of p-PLC and total PLC normalised as the ratio of p-PLC to total PLC and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group (n=4 independent cell cultures). D: One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Unpaired t-test all compared to Vehicle. E: *p=0.0469; G: **p=0.0024. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean. ns= not statistically significant, p>0.05.

3.5.7 The effect of MTII pre-treatment on phosphorylation of phospholipase C β 3 at Ser537 in U373 astroglioma cell line

Visual immunoblots show subtle increases in p-PLC β 3 at Ser537 with MTII compared to Vehicle. However, densitometric analysis of MTII pre-treatment did not show statistical significance in U373 astroglioma cells regardless of drug concentration used (**Figure 3.5.7-1 A&B**). The positive control, m-3M3FBS (25 μ M), phosphorylated PLC (**p=0.0057) compared to Vehicle-treated U373 astroglioma cells (**Figure 3.5.7-1 C**). Due to the variation in the data set as well as the densitometry data not reflecting on the visual immunoblots, no conclusions could be drawn.

Figure 3.5.7-1 Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment effect on Phospholipase C β 3 (PLC) phosphorylation in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to treatment with Vehicle (ddH₂O) or MTII (0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM) for 15 minutes. The experiment using m-3M3FBS PLC activator (25 μ M in 0.05% dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) presented in Panel C was independent of Panel B and was conducted using cells treated with m-3M3FBS for 15 minutes. From these experiments (n=6 independent experiments), one representative sample was selected for visual representation in Panel A. Cells were lysed and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A:** Representative immunoblot of phosphorylated phospholipase c (p-PLC), and total PLC. **B&C** Densitometric analysis of p-PLC and total PLC normalised as the ratio of p-PLC to total PLC and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group. One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. MTII 0.1nM p=0.9621, 1nM p= 0.6146, 10nM p= 0.9947 and 100nM p= 0.9980 and **p= 0.0057, all compared to Vehicle treated cells. (**B:** n=6 independent cell cultures) (**C:** n=4 independent cell cultures). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. ns= not statistically significant, p>0.05.

3.5.8 Setmelanotide effect on phosphorylation of ERK1/2 kinase in U373 astroglioma cells

Setmelanotide induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells when assessing the immunoblots visually (**Figure 3.5.8-1 A**). However, the densitometric analysis was not representative of this so no conclusions could be drawn (**Figure 3.5.8-1 B**).

Figure 3.5.8-1 The effect of Setmelanotide on extracellular regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) phosphorylation in U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to pre-treatment with Setmelanotide (0.1-100nM), Vehicle (ddH₂O) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100uM) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A:** Representative immunoblot of phosphorylated ERK1/2 (p-ERK1/2), and total ERK1/2. **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-ERK1/2 and total ERK1/2 normalised as the ratio of p-ERK1/2 to total ERK1/2 and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group. One-way ANOVA: Dunnett's multiple comparisons test (n=9 independent cell cultures). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. ns= not significant, $p > 0.05$ compared to Vehicle treated group.

3.5.9 The effect of MTII and SHU9119 on ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells at a physiological brain glucose concentration (2.5mM)

Beside their other roles, astrocytes are responsible for glucose uptake for metabolism in the brain and show higher glucose transport and metabolism than neurons (Jakoby et al., 2014).

As per Schildge et al the standard method is to culture mouse primary cortical astrocytes in DMEM (cell culture media) containing high levels of glucose (25mM) (Schildge et al., 2013). The U373 astroglioma cell line exhibits a pronounced reliance on glycolysis to fuel its cellular energy requirements, which is in line with the Warburg effect commonly observed in cancer cells (Heiden et al., 2009; Warburg O, Posener K, 1924). My previous experiments explored MCR signalling in U373 astroglioma cells cultured in standard DMEM containing high levels of glucose (25mM). Similarly, published *in-vitro* data investigating the effect of MCR signalling in astrocytes used DMEM containing high levels of glucose (25mM) as standard. However, there is a possibility that performing studies in media containing high glucose may not be optimally physiologically representative as the “normal” physiological brain glucose concentration is thought to be between 0.7mM – 2.5mM or 5.5mM (Abe et al., 2006; Abi-Saab et al., 2002; De Vries et al., 2003; Dunn-Meynell et al., 2009; Starichaa et al., 2018; Silver & Erecinska, 1994; Silver & Erecińska, 1998). Therefore, to address this issue, a method used in our laboratory is to culture astrocytes in 25mM glucose DMEM to maintain growth, followed by 7.5mM glucose DMEM when seeded for experiments (typically the day before treatment), and on the day of experiments to change the medium to serum free 2.5mM glucose DMEM for 2 hours, to better model the brain physiological glucose concentrations during experimentation.

I have provided evidence earlier in this chapter that MTII pre-treatment induced phosphorylation of ERK1/2 that could be inhibited by SHU9119 in U373 astroglioma cell line cultured in standard DMEM containing high levels of glucose (25mM) (**section 3.5.3 and 3.5.4**). Therefore, to better mimic the

physiological brain glucose concentration in-vitro, I investigated ERK1/2 phosphorylation in response to MTII and/or SHU9119 pre-treatment in U373 cells in 2.5mM glucose DMEM. Visual assessment of immunoblots are suggestive of increases in ERK1/2 phosphorylation after MTII pre-treatment (0.1-10nM) (**Figure 3.5.9-1 A**), however, this was not statistically significant following densitometric analysis (**Figure 3.5.9-1 B**). ATP pre-treatment increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation compared to Vehicle treated controls (*p=0.0062) (**Figure 3.5.9-1 A&B**). Immunoblot images show apparent changes in the band intensity of ERK1/2 phosphorylation with MTII and ATP pre-treatments compared to Vehicle. SHU9119 pre-treatment appeared to reduce ERK1/2 phosphorylation in comparison to MTII, although not statistically significant following densitometric analysis (**Figure 3.5.9-1 C&D**). As the densitometric analysis is not consistent with the immunoblotting data, I do not feel able to make a conclusion from this data.

Figure 3.5.9-1 The effect of melanocortin receptor's (MCR's) ligands on extracellular regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) in U373 astroglia cells cultured in 2.5mM glucose

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to pre-treatment with Melanotan II (MTII; 0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM), Vehicle (ddH₂O) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100μM) for 15 minutes (**A&B**), or pre-treatment with SHU9119 (1μM) for 30 minutes followed by MTII stimulation (1nM), Vehicle (ddH₂O) or ATP (100μM) for 15 minutes (**C&D**). Representative immunoblots of phospho-ERK1/2 (p-ERK1/2) and total ERK1/2 **A&C**. Densitometric analysis of p-ERK1/2 and total ERK1/2 normalised as the ratio of p-ERK1/2 to total ERK1/2 and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated group **B&D**. (**A&B** n=10 independent cell cultures; **C&D** n=8 independent cell cultures). One-way ANOVA; (A-B) Compared to Vehicle; MTII 0.1nM p=0.8047, 1nM p=0.6122, 10nM p=0.2271, 100nM p=0.6826; ATP **p=0.0062. (C-D) MTII p=0.9958, SHU p=0.9969, SHU/MTII p=0.8925, ATP p=0.7415. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean. ns= not statistically significant, p>0.05 compared to Vehicle treated cells.

3.5.10 MCR ligand pre-treatments had no effect on PKA phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells cultured at a physiologically relevant brain glucose concentration (2.5mM)

In addition to **section 3.5.9** exploring ERK1/2 phosphorylation downstream of MTII pre-treatment in U373 cells cultured in 2.5mM glucose, I explored PKA phosphorylation in U373 astroglioma cells in the same conditions using some of the same samples for ERK1/2. Consistent with my previous finding in **section 3.5.5**, PKA did not show increased phosphorylation following MTII pre-treatment regardless of medium glucose concentration or drug concentration used (**Figure 3.5.10-1 A&B**). This was consistent between experimental replicates (independent cell cultures) in both glucose conditions; **section 3.5.5 Figure 3.5.5-1**. Interestingly, it appears there was no constitutive receptor activity for this pathway in the Vehicle group (ddH₂O) following visual examination of immunoblot images, which was also consistent with my previous finding **section 3.5.5 Figure 3.5.5-1**. Therefore, the antagonist properties of SHU9119 on PKA signalling, if any, will not be evident using this approach (**Figure 3.5.10-1 C&D**). Pre-treatment with 8 Bromo-cAMP, as a positive control, increased phosphorylation of PKA *p=0.0277 (**Figure 3.5.10-1 C&D**).

Figure 3.5.10-1 Melanocortin receptor's (MCRs) ligands Melanotan II (MTII) and SHU9119 had no effect on Protein Kinase A (PKA) phosphorylation in U373 cells cultured in 2.5mM glucose

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes before pre-treatment with MTII (0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes (**A&B**); or pre-treatment with Vehicle (ddH₂O), MTII (1nM), SHU9119 (1 μ M) for 15 minutes, and SHU9119 (1 μ M) for 30 minutes followed by MTII stimulation (1nM) for 15 minutes, or 8 Bromo-cAMP (100 μ M) for 30 minutes (**C&D**). Cells were lysed, and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A&C** Representative immunoblot of Phospho-PKA C Thr197 (p-PKA), and total PKA C. **B&D** Densitometric analysis of p-PKA C and total PKA C normalised as the ratio of p-PKA C to total PKA C and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated control group (n=6 independent cell cultures). One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. D: *p=0.0277 compared to Vehicle treated group. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. ns= not significant, p>0.05 compared to Vehicle treated group.

3.5.11 MTII pre-treatment and conditioned medium did not affect cell viability in human U373 astroglioma cell line

U373 astroglioma cells cultured in 2.5mM glucose DMEM treated with MTII for 15 minutes did not show decreased cell viability, with over 98% viable cells in both the Vehicle and MTII-treated groups (**Figure 3.5.11-1 A**).

Figure 3.5.11-1 Melanotan II (MTII) treatment and 2.5mM glucose medium did not affect cell viability in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 cells per well in a 24 well plate. Day of experiment cells were treated with varying concentrations of MTII (0.1-100nM) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes in 2.5mM glucose serum-free DMEM followed by propidium iodide staining and flow cytometry with the BD Accuri C6 Plus flow cytometer. **A:** Cell viability percentage. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. n=3 independent cell cultures.

3.5.12 Confirmation of purity of mouse cortical astrocytes *in-vitro*

87 ± 0.6% of cells (indicated by DAPI-positive nuclei) expressed GFAP-immunoreactivity (indicated by white arrows); there were no IBA1 immunoreactive cells observed, confirming the absence of microglia (**Figure 3.5.12-1 A&B**).

Figure 3.5.12-1 Mouse cortical astrocytes express glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP)

Cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^4 cells per well on glass coverslips in 24 well plates before fixation with methanol and immunostaining. **A:** GFAP and IBA-1 immunostaining of primary mouse cell culture. 87 ± 0.6 % of nuclei (DAPI; blue) were associated with GFAP-immunoreactivity (**A:** white arrows) ($n=3$ independent cell cultures). **B:** Negative control with a secondary antibody was used only to confirm that the immunofluorescence observed was not due to the non-specific binding of the secondary antibody. Scale bars = 100 μm

3.5.13 MTII did not induce ERK1/2 phosphorylation in mouse cortical astrocytes cultured in high glucose

I have shown that MCRs are expressed in the whole mouse brain, hypothalamic tissue, and cultured cortical astrocytes (**section 3.5.2**). I have observed that U373 astroglioma cells respond to increasing concentrations of MTII, resulting in the phosphorylation of ERK1/2 (**section 3.5.3**). I then wanted to determine if the same MTII induced downstream signalling pattern could be observed in mouse primary cortical astrocytes. I cultured mouse primary cortical astrocytes and hypothalamic astrocytes. I experienced success in culturing mouse cortical astrocytes, and cells could grow and proliferate, reaching 90-100% confluency. However, I had trouble in culturing hypothalamic astrocytes as this tissue was extremely small from mouse pups, and the limited number of cells that grew did not reach the confluence desired to perform experiments; as a result, I proceeded with experiments using the cortical astrocytes only.

MTII treatment did not show statistical significance for phosphorylated ERK1/2 in mouse cortical astrocytes independent of drug concentration (**Figure 3.5.13-1 A&B**). However, I observed some increases in ERK1/2 phosphorylation when assessing the immunoblots visually. This may be attributed to the variation in ERK1/2 signalling depending on the age of pups when cells were isolated, as it was published that ERK1/2 signalling is increased in mature astrocytes compared to that of immature astrocytes (Zsarnovszky & Belcher, 2004). Nonetheless, ATP (100 μ M) as a positive control phosphorylated ERK1/2 (* $p=0.0166$) (**Figure 3.5.13-1 A&B**). This may indicate that MTII treatment has a smaller effect on ERK1/2 signalling in immature astrocytes compared with ATP.

Figure 3.5.13-1 Melanotan II (MTII) treatment did not induce extracellular regulated Kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) phosphorylation in mouse cortical astrocytes

Mouse cortical astrocytes were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes prior to treatment with MTII (0.1nM, 1nM, 10nM, 100nM), adenosine triphosphate (ATP 100 μ M) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A:** Representative immunoblot of phospho ERK1/2 (p-ERK1/2; Thr202/Tyr204), total ERK1/2, and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) loading control. **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-ERK1/2 (Thr202/Tyr204) and TOTAL ERK1/2 normalised as the ratio of p-ERK1/2 to total ERK1/2 and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated group (n=6 independent cell cultures). **B:** One-way ANOVA; Dunnett's multiple comparisons test MTII compared to Vehicle: MTII 0.1nM p=0.7971; 1nM p=0.9275, 10nM p=0.4148, 100nM p=0.9983; ATP *p=0.0166. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. ns= not significant, p>0.05.

3.5.14 MTII did not induce PKA phosphorylation at Thr197 in mouse cortical astrocytes cultured in brain physiological glucose (2.5mM) level

As mentioned in **Chapter 1**, the conventionally known pathway activated downstream of MCR signalling is the Gs-cAMP-PKA pathway. However, data implicates different biological responses in various cell types and receptor expression levels. Consistent with the data I generated in U373 astroglioma cells in both glucose conditions in **sections 3.5.5 and 3.5.10**, MTII pre-treatment did not induce phosphorylation of PKA at Thr197 in mouse cortical astrocytes independent of drug and glucose concentration when compared to Vehicle (**Figure 3.5.14-1 A&B**).

A

B

Figure 3.5.14-1 Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment did not increase Protein Kinase A (PKA) phosphorylation in mouse cortical astrocytes

Mouse cortical astrocytes were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^5 cells per dish in 60 mm dishes before pre-treatment with MTII (1nM, 10nM, 100nM, 1μM) or Vehicle (ddH₂O) for 15 minutes. Cells were lysed, and protein was collected for immunoblotting. **A:** Representative immunoblot of phospho-PKA C (p-PKA C; Thr 197) and total PKA C **B:** Densitometric analysis of p-PKA C and total PKA C normalised as the ratio of p-PKA C to total PKA C and represented as fold change from the mean of the Vehicle-treated group (n=4 independent cell cultures). **B:** One-way ANOVA; MTII 1nM p=0.9230, 10nM p=0.6224, 100nM p=0.9843; 1μM p=0.323. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean. ns= not significant, p>0.05.

3.6 Discussion

In this chapter, I have demonstrated, using PCR, that mouse cortical astrocytes and the human U373 astrogloma cell line express mRNA for melanocortin receptors (MCRs). My data show that the MCR agonist MTII increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 cells, an effect inhibited by pre-treatment with the antagonist SHU9119. These findings support the hypothesis that MCRs are expressed in astrocytes and can actively induce downstream signalling following pharmacological modulation. Data from mouse cortical astrocytes were inconclusive but suggest no statistically significant effect of MTII on downstream signalling, despite detection of MCR gene expression and visual indication of the presences of ERK1/2 phosphorylation.

3.6.1 Key findings

- **Expression of MCRs:** Mouse cortical astrocytes express MC1R to MC5R, while human U373 cells express MC1R to MC4R but not MC5R. This differs from the literature, which primarily reports MC4R expression in astrocytes (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2007, 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lasaga et al., 2008; Ramírez et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2009, 2012; Saba et al., 2019; Vaglini et al., 2018; Wong K & N, 1997; Weilin Xu et al., 2020).
- **ERK1/2 activation:** MTII induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 cells cultured in-high glucose conditions, but not in mouse primary astrocytes. SHU9119 inhibited MTII's effect on ERK1/2 phosphorylation in U373 cells.
- **Basal PKA activity and phosphorylation:** Constitutive basal PKA activity was not observed in either cell model under the different glucose conditions. MTII did not increase PKA phosphorylation in either model.
- **Cell viability:** MTII treatment and conditioned medium did not affect U373 cell viability.

3.6.2 Mouse cortical astrocytes and human U373 astrogloma cells express MCRs

The PCR data shown in this chapter indicate that human U373 cells and mouse cortical astrocytes express MCRs. My findings are in contrast with published data indicating that only MC4R is expressed in rat and human astrocytes (Caruso et al., 2007, 2012; Kamermans et al., 2019; Ramírez et al., 2015, 2019; Saba et al., 2019; Selkirk et al., 2007; Vaglini et al., 2018), although MC1R expression was also demonstrated in astrocytes in a separate study, which did not show expression of the other receptor subtypes (Xu, et al., 2020). The limited evidence for MC1R expression in astrocytes (Xu et al., 2020) aligns partially with my results but does not account for the broader receptor profile I observed.

My findings are somewhat consistent with prior observations of the expression of *MC1R* to *MC5R* mRNA in the white matter of human brain samples (Kamermans et al., 2019). Although not examined directly for all MCRs, in the same study, they demonstrated the expression of MC4R in GFAP-positive cells using *in situ* hybridisation (Kamermans et al., 2019). Selkirk et al showed that low yet detectable levels of *MC4R* mRNA were observed in neonatal rat cortical astrocytes using quantitative RT-PCR with a specific qPCR threshold of 35 cycles (Selkirk et al., 2007). However, this approach did not detect the mRNA of *MC1R*, *MC2R*, *MC3R*, and *MC5R* (Selkirk et al., 2007). Caruso et al investigated *MC3R* and *MC4R* mRNA expression in astrocytes, where they showed only MC4R expression but did not investigate expression of the other MCRs (Caruso et al., 2007).

Methodological variations such as the use of RT-PCR may have detected low-abundance mRNA missed in other studies using qPCR or *in situ* hybridisation, although my methodology was not quantitative.

Cellular heterogeneity in primary cultured astrocytes may have contributed to the differences observed in astrocytes as they are highly heterogeneous, and differences in culture conditions, such as cell passaging, could influence receptor expression profiles (Schildge et al., 2013; Taciak et al., 2018). The

broader receptor profile observed in my study suggests that mouse astrocytes may exhibit greater functional diversity in response to melanocortin ligands than previously thought, although this should be replicated with additional experimental approaches. These results highlight functional implications and the need for further investigation into the functional relevance of astrocytic MCR expression.

3.6.3 Impact of melanocortin ligands on the activity of downstream signalling pathways in human U373 astroglioma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes

MTII induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation, and SHU9119 inhibited this effect in human U373 cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25 mM). However, this response was not observed in mouse cortical astrocytes. Setmelanotide also appeared to increase ERK1/2 phosphorylation in human U373 cells, albeit without statistical significance being reached. MTII did not induce PKA phosphorylation in U373 cells nor mouse astrocytes cultured in either glucose condition. Through visual examination of the immunoblots, I observed MTII-induced PLC β 3 phosphorylation in human U373 cells cultured in high glucose conditions, but densitometry analysis did not indicate statistical significance.

The observation of ERK1/2 phosphorylation following treatment with MCR agonists was consistent with existing literature on astrocytes (Caruso et al., 2012; Ramírez et al., 2015; Vaglini et al., 2018) and this effect was inhibited by the antagonist SHU9119, supporting prior work (Kamermans et al., 2019). However, these published studies reported only MC4R mediated these effects, as it was believed to be the only receptor subtype expressed in astrocytes. In contrast, my expression data suggest the possible involvement of other MCR subtypes, such as MC1R, MC3R, and MC5R in U373 cells. Since MTII binds to all MCRs (except MC2R) with varying affinities, it is possible that MTII interacted with multiple receptor subtypes to mediate the observed impact on downstream signalling.

Setmelanotide exhibits a higher affinity for MC4R than the other MCRs (Clément et al., 2018; Collet et al., 2017; Hammad et al., 2022), and the observed increase in ERK1/2 signalling following Setmelanotide pre-treatments supports the potential involvement of MC4R. However, its weaker effect via ERK1/2 and higher potency toward cAMP activation may explain the lack of statistical significance observed (Hammad et al., 2022).

Although MCRs can couple to Gq to activate PLC, there are no published studies indicating melanocortin ligands increase PLC phosphorylation in astrocytes. Research suggests that Setmelanotide can activate PLC signalling pathways in other cellular contexts, though this effect is weaker compared to its ability to stimulate cAMP (Clément et al., 2018; Collet et al., 2017). Mutations in the human MC4R gene have been reported to impair PLC β activation (Clément et al., 2018; Heyder et al., 2021). The U373 cells used here may carry such mutations, but this would need to be directly confirmed through gene sequencing. As there is no available published evidence on the impact on melanocortin ligands on PLC signalling pathway, I cannot directly compare or make conclusions, however, the positive control treatment with m-3M3FBS suggest that these cells have an intact PLC signalling pathway.

Although it is reported that MCRs have constitutive activity via cAMP, which is upstream of PKA, MTII treatment was not sufficient to induce PKA phosphorylation in U373 cells or mouse astrocytes. The data from the vehicle group does not indicate constitutive activity of this pathway, in contrast to what is previously published (Kay et al., 2013; Link et al., 2020; Nijenhuis et al., 2001; Ollmann et al., 1997; Slominski et al., 2005; Srinivasan et al., 2004; Tao, 2007). One possible explanation for this discrepancy is the inhibition of adenylyl cyclase (AC), leading to cAMP accumulation and preventing PKA activation (Büch et al., 2009). Without PKA activation, downstream signalling events, including the crosstalk between cAMP and ERK1/2 signalling pathways, may be disrupted (Damm et al., 2012; Stork & Schmitt, 2002; Büch et al., 2009). This could account for the observed absence of PKA-mediated signalling downstream of MCR activation in my data. However, the positive control treatments with 8-Bromo-cAMP and ATP suggest that the cells used for my studies could signal via these pathways. However, I could not conclusively confirm that mouse cortical astrocytes showed an increase in PKA phosphorylation, as during experiments, my positive control, ATP, did not stimulate PKA phosphorylation.

MCRs may engage in crosstalk, a phenomenon commonly observed among GPCRs, where signals from one receptor influence another receptor's pathway. Additionally, MCRs may participate in cross-communication, facilitating

interactions between entirely distinct signalling networks (Natarajan & Berk, 2006). Studies have shown that ERK1/2 activation following MC3R, MC4R, and MC5R can be dependent or independent of PKA, and β -arrestin recruitment, exchange factors directly activated by cAMP (EPAC1/2), PI3 kinase (PI3K), melanocortin accessory proteins (MRAPs) and cAMP (Abrisqueta et al., 2013; Chai et al., 2006, 2007; Glas et al., 2016; Nyan et al., 2008; Rodrigues et al., 2012; Shenoy & Lefkowitz, 2005; Sutton et al., 2005; Vongs et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2022). Overall, the specific receptor subtype through which the observed effects were mediated and the upstream pathways regulating ERK1/2 remain unknown. MC2R is ruled out as neither MTII nor Setmelanotide bind to MC2R (Fridmanis et al., 2017).

The differences in ERK1/2 activation between cell models could be attributed to variations in expression levels and the cellular environment. The relative abundance of MCR subtypes may vary between U373 cells and mouse astrocytes, and quantitative studies, such as qPCR, could help clarify this. Additionally, the cellular environment plays a role, as astrocyte models, particularly glioblastoma-derived U373 cells, may exhibit altered signalling pathways compared to primary mouse astrocytes. This suggests potential species-specific or receptor subtype differences.

This chapter's finding limitations were limited by the sole use of Western blotting for the evaluation of signalling. Western Blotting, is a semi-quantitative technique with pros and cons. During my experiments, the antibodies for the phospho PKA or PLC and total PKA or PLC were from the same species (the supplier only had the same species), resulting the need to load samples on separate gels, transfer them onto separate membranes and immunoblot separately. Although the same conditions were run with the same protein loading, and gels/transfers were run simultaneously, this can still lead to variability. This may have not only had an impact on normalisation and densitometry analysis, but also made the workflow complicated. This is supported, in some cases, by the observed increased phosphorylation of protein, which was not always reflected in the densitometry as analysis (as seen in **Figure 3.5.7-1**, **Figure 3.5.8-1** and **Figure 3.5.9-1**).

The mouse primary astrocyte signalling data focused on ERK1/2 and PKA. Although there were no changes in PKA phosphorylation in response to MTII treatment, there was a lot of variability between signals when observing ERK1/2 phosphorylation (**Figure 3.5.13-1**). It is possible that in these cells, 15 minutes of MTII pre-treatment was insufficient to induce a response and or that the increased phosphorylation was more rapid and was missed; therefore, a time course could be explored to assess this in the future. In addition, it is possible that MTII pre-treatment resulted in other signalling pathways, such as PLC, being activated. However, I was unable to investigate these due to the limited samples available.

Only MTII treatment was assessed in mouse primary astrocytes and further ligand pre-treatments are required to confirm this result. Nonetheless, it is possible that pharmacological stimulation of MCRs in mouse primary cortical astrocytes affects endogenous MCRs subtly, in contrast to the observed effects in U373 cells. This discrepancy could be due to differences in the expression levels of receptor subtypes or downstream signalling pathways between the two cell types. It is important to note that the RT-PCR used in this study to examine MCR expression was not quantitative, so we do not know the relative expression levels of MCRs in U373 cells and mouse primary astrocytes. Although I attempted to quantify MCRs using qPCR, technical issues prevented successful results, so this data was not included in this thesis. Addressing this limitation and successfully quantifying MCR expression in future studies could provide valuable insights into the mechanisms underlying the varied responses to MCR stimulation.

Overall, my results support my hypothesis that MCRs modulate astrocytes via ERK1/2 signalling. This is consistent with existing literature beyond astrocytes (Caruso et al., 2012; Ramírez et al., 2015; Vaglini et al., 2018). Although prior research has indicated activation of ERK1/2 downstream of MC4R in both human and rat astrocytes, my results cannot the involvement of other MCRs, given that I observed expression of MC1R to MC4R by RT-PCR in human astrogloma cells and MC1R to MC5R in mouse cortical astrocytes.

3.6.4 Functional melanocortin signalling responses in astrocytes cultured in physiologically relevant brain glucose concentration (2.5mM)

In astrocyte cell culture experiments, studies commonly use standard high glucose (25 mM) DMEM conditions. However, it is worth noting that these in-vitro conditions do not accurately mirror the physiological glucose levels found in the brain. Additionally, evidence shows that conditioned medium and cell passaging changes genetic profiling of cell lines leading to differences in cell heterogeneity within culture, including changes in signalling responses (Calles et al., 2006; Esquenet et al., 1997; Hongshi Yu et al., 1997; Joosten & Shuler, 2003; Kaur & Dufour, 2012; Lin et al., 2003; O'Driscoll et al., 2006; Sambuy et al., 2005; Taciak et al., 2018; Wenger et al., 2004; Woloschak, 1997). These changes also occur in glioblastoma cell lines, including U373 cells (Dai & Holland, 2001; Diao et al., 2019; Kaur & Dufour, 2012; Torsvik et al., 2014; Yavuz, 2022). Given that U373 cells are highly glycolytic and have elevated glucose use requirements due to them being a cancer cell line (Warburg effect), for the studies in U373 cells described in section 3.4.3 to section 3.4.8, I used the standard high glucose DMEM.

Considering that the physiological brain glucose concentration typically falls within the range of 0.7mM to 2.5 mM, I repeated some of the experiments in U373 astrogloma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes using serum-free DMEM containing 2.5 mM glucose to mimic the brain's glucose concentration more closely. I verified that the viability of U373 cells was not affected by reduced media glucose levels, which could potentially deprive them of energy, causing stress and cell death. I also ensured that the use of 2.5mM serum-free medium and the addition of a drug, when cells are exposed to MTII, did not negatively impact cell viability. The data presented in this chapter indicates that glucose concentration in cell culture conditions did not impact melanocortin ligand responses in U373 astrogloma cells or cell viability.

Assessments of ERK1/2 phosphorylation visually after MTII and ATP pre-treatment suggested increases in ERK1/2 phosphorylation in human U373 cells

cultured in 2.5mM glucose. SHU9119 pre-treatment appeared to reduce ERK1/2 phosphorylation compared to MTII in these cells. However, this data was not statistically significant following densitometric analysis. As discussed above, these discrepancies may stem from the limitations of Western Blotting and the signal intensities of the antibodies used, which can lead to data misinterpretations and issues with reproducibility (Butler et al., 2019).

Besides the Western Blotting caveats, although the 2.5mM glucose cell culture conditions did not affect cell viability, it is still possible that the changes in cell culture medium between 25mM and 2.5mM glucose and the differences in cell passage numbers may have had a subtle impact on ERK1/2 signalling leading to variability. This is supported by evidence of the impact of cell culture medium conditions and cell passaging on glioma cell function (Dai & Holland, 2001; Diao et al., 2019; Kaur & Dufour, 2012; Torsvik et al., 2014; Yavuz, 2022). On the other hand, regardless of glucose concentration, PKA was not phosphorylated in response to treatment with melanocortin ligands in mouse cortical astrocytes cultured in 2.5mM glucose, corroborating my finding that MTII did not induce PKA phosphorylation in human U373 cells cultured in 25mM and 2.5mM glucose conditions. This may suggest that cell culture glucose conditions do not impact cell signalling pathways.

As previously mentioned, although it is reported that MCRs have constitutive cAMP activity, in the vehicle group there was no constitutive phosphorylation of PKA observed when examining the immunoblots. As such, I was unable to detect changes in baseline PKA-phosphorylation following SHU9119 treatment. This could be for the same reasons previously discussed in **section 3.6.3** (Büch et al., 2009). It is worth noting that the monoclonal antibody used in my studies to detect PKA targets only Thr197, and it is possible that downstream of melanocortin ligand treatment in astrocytes PKA was phosphorylated at other sites that were not examined in these studies (Cleverley et al., 1998; Neuberger et al., 2007; Shoji et al., 1983; Xiao et al., 2005; Yonemoto et al., 1993; J. Zheng et al., 1993).

3.6.5 Conclusion

The present study describes the presence of MCRs mRNA in human U373 astrogloma cells and mouse primary cortical astrocytes using RT-PCR. Although mRNA expression does not necessarily reflect protein expression (Kendrick, 2012), my studies did not assess MCR protein expression due to the absence of validated or specific antibodies for MCRs. Nonetheless, treatment with the melanocortin ligand MTII modulated ERK1/2 phosphorylation in astrocytes. This suggests that endogenous MCRs are responsive to ligands displaying changes in downstream signalling. Together these data indicates that U373 astrogloma cells are a potential model for future studies on endogenous MCRs in an astrocyte-like cell. This model provides the advantage of endogenous receptor expression, removing the need for recombinant cell models that may not accurately represent physiological conditions. However, to confirm this, qPCR would be helpful to establish the relative expression of the different MCR subtypes.

Collectively, these findings suggests that MCRs may modulate astrocyte function via ERK1/2 activation to support brain function. The figure below summaries findings of this chapter with a proposed hypothetical model of how ERK1/2 was phosphorylated downstream of MCRs in astrocytes (**Figure 3.6.5-1**).

Figure 3.6.5-1 Summary of Chapter 3 findings and proposed hypothetical downstream signalling mechanisms leading to ERK1/2 activation

The figure illustrates a proposed hypothetical model on MCR signalling pathways and the possible upstream effectors involved in ERK1/2 phosphorylation observed in the human U373 astrogloma cell line. Dashed lines indicate a theoretical model involving the potential mechanism(s) (not tested herein) of how ERK1/2 was phosphorylated following MCR pharmacological modulation with the MCR synthetic agonists MTII or Setmelanotide. Question marks indicate other signalling pathways that were assessed but not conclusive in my studies. The dashed line with an end indicates inhibition of the pathway. Figure created with Biorender.

4 IMPACT OF MCR LIGANDS ON CALCIUM AND POTASSIUM ION DYNAMICS IN ASTROCYTES

4.1 Introduction

Astrocytes' predominant ionic signalling modality is known to be calcium ion (Ca^{2+}) mediated (Lia et al., 2021; Verkhratsky et al., 2012). They extend their highly branched processes that form functionally isolated microdomains to maintain ion homeostasis by facilitating spontaneous increases in Ca^{2+} mediated (Lia et al., 2021; Verkhratsky et al., 2012). Astrocytes can uptake excess ions from the extracellular space, such as potassium and calcium ions, through calcium-dependent mechanisms to maintain ion homeostasis in brain tissue (Kofuji & Newman, 2004; Rimmele & Chatton, 2014). Mechanisms of Ca^{2+} signalling in astrocytes differ between brain regions. Ca^{2+} signalling is essential in astrocytes as they participate in bidirectional communication with neurons through Ca^{2+} signalling. Changes in iCa^{2+} levels in astrocytes can modulate the release of gliotransmitters and neurotransmitters, thus influencing synaptic transmission and neuronal excitability. For example, in cortical astrocyte processes, spontaneous Ca^{2+} signalling occurs from the mitochondria (Agarwal et al., 2017), which may indicate an interplay between the mitochondria and Ca^{2+} signalling in astrocytes. Astrocyte Ca^{2+} signalling regulates metabolic processes, including glucose uptake, glycogen metabolism, and energy substrates' production and release. This is important as these are essential for meeting the energy demands of neurons to maintain CNS function. Dysregulation of Ca^{2+} signalling in astrocytes has been implicated in various neurological disorders, highlighting the importance of Ca^{2+} signalling in astrocytes for physiological coordination and function of the brain.

Stimulation of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) can induce iCa^{2+} mobilisation through multiple pathways not limited to the Gq-PLC (Phospholipase C) and inositol triphosphate (IP3) pathway (Durkee et al., 2019; Navarrete et al., 2012; Parpura et al., 2011; Petravicz et al., 2008; Takata et al.,

2011) and or through Gi/O coupling (Durkee et al., 2019). MCRs are GPCRs, and their activation increases iCa^{2+} levels in non-glia cells (Berger, 1986; Buffey et al., 1992; Jain et al., 2018; Kim et al., 1997; Konda et al., 1994; Kumar et al., 2021; Langouche et al., 2001; Mountjoy et al., 2001; Newman et al., 2006; Roudbaraki et al., 1999). Stimulation of MC1R or MC5R in non-glia cells did not activate the secondary messenger's protein kinase C (PKC) and PLC involved in calcium signalling but activated extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) (Herraiz et al., 2009, 2011; Rodrigues et al., 2009). Information on the melanocortin agonist Setmelanotide and its direct effects on MCRs is limited in the available published literature (Collet et al., 2017; Kamermans et al., 2019). Furthermore, there is no available published data on its effects on astrocytes *in-vitro*. However, it has been documented that Setmelanotide demonstrates biased signalling towards Gq/11 activating PLC β 3 (Heyder et al., 2021), and Gs-adenylyl cyclase (AC) in HEK293 cells (Clément et al., 2018; Hammad et al., 2022). It is also selective towards MC4R having 10-20 fold more potency and possessing 37-fold higher affinity than endogenous α -MSH in transfected HEK293 cells from six various species (Falls & Zhang, 2019; Hammad et al., 2022). Setmelanotide also has agonist activity at MC1R and MC3R, with weak agonism at MC5R and no affinity towards MC2R in CHO-K1 cells (Collet et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2009). This evidence may suggest that increases in iCa^{2+} levels in response to Setmelanotide treatment are more likely to be mediated by MC4R or any other MCR (except MC2R) rather than by MTII treatment in astrocytes. Therefore, I next evaluated the effect of Setmelanotide treatment on changes in iCa^{2+} in mouse cortical astrocytes.

I have demonstrated ERK1/2 phosphorylation following treatment with melanocortin ligands in the human U373 astrogloma cell line (**Chapter 3**), which may, in turn, modulate iCa^{2+} . Published data demonstrated that calcium ions are required as cofactors for MC4R activation (Chaturvedi & Shukla, 2020; Heyder et al., 2021; Link et al., 2020; Salomon, 1990; J. Yu et al., 2020). However, there is no available published data on the impact of modulation of MCR activity on iCa^{2+} flux in astrocytes.

Besides iCa^{2+} modulation, astrocytes modulate potassium ions in the extracellular space to regulate neuronal activity, known as potassium buffering

(Bellot-Saez et al., 2017; Kofuji & Newman, 2004). In contrast to neurons, astrocytes are electrically non-excitable cells with a negative resting membrane potential of about -80mV. Their membrane potential is dependent on changes in cytosolic and extracellular ion concentrations. Potassium ion (K⁺) channels dominate astrocyte membrane permeability. The K⁺ channels abundantly expressed in astrocytes are voltage-dependent and inward rectification potassium channels (Kir channels). Kir channels drive K⁺ ions into the cell, hence the name inward rather than out of the cell. Inward rectification happens due to a voltage-dependent intracellular blockage by Mg²⁺ and polyamines (Guo et al., 2003). Together, this K⁺ conductance and maintenance, known as potassium buffering, defines the homeostatic capability of astrocytes in supporting brain function via the movement of ions. Astrocytes also express other ion channels, such as calcium and sodium channels. Astrocyte potassium ion buffering is believed to be largely mediated by inwardly rectifying potassium channels, including Kir 4.1, which is expressed in the human U373 astroglioma cell line (Olsen & Sontheimer, 2004; Tan et al., 2008; Zurolo et al., 2012). Notably, evidence demonstrates GPCR-independent coupling of MC1R and MC4R via Kir 7.1, and weak coupling to Kir 4.1 in transfected HEK293 cells (Anderson et al., 2019; Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; J. Yu et al., 2020). Ghamari-Langroudi et al reported mRNA co-expression of *Kir7.1* and *MC4R* in neurons from the mouse brain, in particular the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) using *in situ* hybridization RNAscope (Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; Litt et al., 2018). Then they showed MC4R coupling to Kir7.1 modulates potassium ion (K⁺) levels using the FluxOR™ Potassium Ion Channel Assay in transfected HEK293 cells (Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; Litt et al., 2018). Further work by Yu et al confirmed MC4R coupling to Kir7.1 independently of G proteins, revealing Ca²⁺ ions as a cofactor through structural studies and electrophysiology methods (J. Yu et al., 2020). Specifically, the study reports the structure of the MC4R bound to the antagonist SHU9119 and Ca²⁺ ions increases the affinity and potency of the endogenous agonist α-MSH at MC4R by 37- and 600-fold, respectively (J. Yu et al., 2020).

4.2 Rationale and Hypothesis

There is currently no evidence on the effects of MCR modulation with ligands on intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) and potassium (K^+) flux in astrocytes. While the impact of MCR activation on iCa^{2+} and potassium dynamics in astrocytes remains unexplored, investigating this could provide valuable insights, given the essential role of astrocytes in calcium signalling and potassium buffering.

Collectively, there is a knowledge gap in the field on the impact of MCR activation on calcium and potassium ion dynamics in astrocytes. I addressed this by examining whether MCR pharmacological modulation using MCR ligands results in the elevation of iCa^{2+} levels and K^+ influx in astrocytes. First, *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1* mRNA expression was assessed in human U373 astroglioma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes. After that, iCa^{2+} levels and K^+ uptake was measured following MCR ligand treatment in human U373 astroglioma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes.

Before assessing this, it was important to assess a potential positive control to increase iCa^{2+} levels in astrocytes following acute treatments and to confirm gene expression of the inwardly rectifying potassium channels known to couple to MCRs, *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1*. In this chapter, I tested the hypothesis that inwardly rectifying potassium channels *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1* mRNA are expressed in astrocytes *in-vitro* and MCR agonists stimulate increased iCa^{2+} levels and K^+ ion uptake in the human U373 astroglioma cell line and mouse cortical astrocytes. The figure below shows a hypothesis that MCR modulation by MTII or Setmelanotide, results in one, or more of the signalling pathways that lead to increases in iCa^{2+} levels, and MCR couples to the inwardly rectifying potassium channels *Kir 4.1* or *Kir 7.1*, or both, modulating their function and increasing uptake of potassium ions from the extracellular space.

Figure 4.2-1 Hypothetical model of melanocortin receptor (MCR) modulation in astrocytes by MTII or Setmelanotide illustrating potential signalling pathways leading to increased intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels and potassium uptake (K^+).

MCR activation may trigger multiple pathways, including the Gq-PLC pathway, where Gq protein activates phospholipase C (PLC), leading to the production of inositol trisphosphate (IP_3) and diacylglycerol (DAG), subsequently activating protein kinase C (PKC) and promoting calcium release (Ca^{2+}) from the endoplasmic reticulum. Alternatively, the Gs-PKA pathway may be engaged, where Gs protein activation increases cyclic AMP (cAMP) levels, activating protein kinase A (PKA), which can also contribute to calcium signalling through IP_3 . Furthermore, MCR activation could activate the ERK1/2 pathway, which is also implicated in iCa^{2+} modulation. Additionally, MCRs may couple with inwardly rectifying potassium channels, such as Kir 4.1 or Kir 7.1, enhancing potassium ion uptake (K^+) from the extracellular space, potentially via any of these pathways, thus influencing potassium buffering in astrocytes.

4.3 Aims

- 1) Examine iCa^{2+} ion dynamics in astrocytes in response to acute treatment with MCR ligands
- 2) Examine gene expression of inwardly rectifying potassium channels *kir 4.1* and *kir 7.1* in astrocytes
- 3) Assess potassium ion uptake in astrocytes in response to acute treatment with MCR ligands

4.4 Methods

1) Intracellular calcium measurement (iCa^{2+}): To measure changes in intracellular calcium ion (Ca^{2+}) changes in response to melanocortin receptor ligands (MCRs), the Fluo-4 Direct Calcium Assay Kit (ThermoFisher, F10471) was used, as previously described (Vlachaki Walker et al., 2017), using the cell-permeable Ca^{2+} sensitive Fluo-4 acetoxymethyl (AM dye). It was first necessary to establish that the Ca^{2+} assay was working reliably in my hands. To do this, I investigated whether U373 astrogloma cells could increase their intracellular calcium ion (iCa^{2+}) levels in response to adenosine triphosphate (ATP), a molecule that increases iCa^{2+} levels in astrocytes (Salter & Hicks, 1994, 1995). Following baseline fluorescence readings, vehicle or ATP (20, 50 and 100 μ M) was injected into the wells with U373 cells, and changes in iCa^{2+} were assessed by monitoring changes in relative fluorescence units (RFU) over time. Then, iCa^{2+} changes were measured in U373 astroglomas or mouse cortical astrocytes in response to acute treatments with MCR ligands, MTII or Setmelanotide (0.1nM to 100nM) or ATP as a positive control.

2) Gene expression: There are no published studies on the effect of MCR ligands on K^+ flux in astrocytes. Before assessing this, I used RT-PCR to confirm gene expression of the inwardly rectifying potassium channels known to couple to MCRs, Kir 4.1 and Kir 7.1, in mouse cortical astrocytes and the human U373 astrogloma cell line. Mouse brain tissue was used as a positive control tissue. Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) were used as an internal housekeeping gene and markers of astrocytes respectively. Mouse and human primers against human U373 astrogloma cell line and mouse cortical astrocytes were designed against

Kir 4.1 and *Kir 7.1* using Benchling (Chapter 2, section 2.7) targeting each gene.

3) Thallium sulphate (TI) flux measurement: The FluxOR Potassium Ion Channel Assay (Fisher Scientific, 10646474) was used to measure changes in intracellular potassium ion uptake. Thallium sulphate ions (TI⁺), a surrogate to potassium ions enters the cells cytoplasm when ion channels are stimulated, and upon binding to the indicator dye, any fluorescent signal detected serves as a surrogate readout of the activity of any potassium ion channel or transporter.

All kit components were diluted and prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. Human U373 astroglioma cells were pre-treated with vehicle or MTII (various concentrations), or SHU9119 (1 μ M) or ATP (100 μ M), before TI injections into wells.

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Human U373 astrogloma cells increased iCa^{2+} levels *in-vitro* in response to treatment with ATP

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) treatment significantly increased relative fluorescent units (RFU) in a concentration-dependent manner compared to Vehicle treated U373 astrogloma cells (**Figure 4.5.1-1 A&B**).

Figure 4.5.1-1 Intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels were increased in U373 astrogloma cells in response to Adenosine triphosphate (ATP)

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with 1X Fluo4 AM for 1 hour at 37°C prior to the assay. Baseline fluorescence was measured using a plate reader before wells were injected ATP (20, 50 and $100\mu\text{M}$) or Vehicle (ddH_2O), and the relative fluorescence units (RFU) were then measured continually for 120 seconds. **A&B**: Representative line graphs of maximum fold change in fluorescence following injection normalised to baseline. **B**: One way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. ATP * $p=0.0260$; ** $p=0.0011$; *** $p=0.0010$ compared to Vehicle. $n=3$ independent cell cultures from three independent plates. $s=$ seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

4.5.2 Human U373 astroglioma cells did not increase iCa^{2+} in response to MTII injections *in-vitro*

I demonstrated in **section 4.5.1** that I can observe changes in iCa^{2+} levels in human U373 astroglioma cells *in-vitro* using the Fluo-4 AM assay in response to stimulation with the positive control ATP. I then used this assay to evaluate changes in iCa^{2+} levels following MCR pharmacological modulation with the agonist MTII. In comparison to Vehicle treatment, U373 cells did not show increases in iCa^{2+} in response to any of the MTII concentrations used (**Figure 4.5.2-1 A-C**). As expected, ATP increased iCa^{2+} levels compared to Vehicle treated cells (**Figure 4.5.2-1 A&B**).

The minimum RFU was calculated to account for subtle changes in iCa^{2+} ion levels in response to MTII; however, there were no changes (**Figure 4.5.2-1 C**).

Figure 4.5.2-1 Melanotan II (MTII) did not modulate Intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels in the U373 astroglioma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with 1X Fluo-4 AM for 1 hour at 37°C prior to the assay.

Baseline fluorescence was measured before wells were injected with Vehicle (ddH₂O), MTII (0.1-100nM) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100 μM), and the relative fluorescence unit (RFU) was then measured continually for 90 seconds.

A&B: Representative line graphs of maximum fold change in fluorescence following injection normalised to baseline. **C:** Minimum fluorescence following injection normalised to baseline. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. ATP **** $p=0.0001$ compared to Vehicle. $n=6$ independent cell cultures in six independent plates. ns= not significant, $p>0.05$. s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

In **Figure 4.5.2-1**, I demonstrated that U373 astrogloma cells did not increase iCa^{2+} in response to MTII treatment. These experiments were performed without the use of probenecid and the provided assay buffer with the kit (Fluo-4 Direct™ Calcium Assay Kit F10471) and instead were performed using the standard protocol from our laboratory including phenol red free media (PRF) containing 25mM HEPES and 2.5mM glucose to better model physiological cell conditions of U373s. Probenecid is an anion transporter inhibitor commonly used to reduce fluorescence loss in the assay. Probenecid helps retain the Fluo-4 AM dye inside the cell, preventing its extrusion back into the medium via organic anion transporters in the cell membrane. Since my previous experiments did not contain probenecid and injection artefacts were observed in the MTII treated cells (**Figure 4.5.2-1 A**), I repeated the experiment per the manufacturer's protocol to address this issue. On the day of the experiment, U373 cells were incubated in serum-free 2.5mM glucose media for two hours. Then, media was replaced with assay buffer containing probenecid and Fluo-4 AM dye for 1 hour at 37°C before measurements were taken. Ligands were diluted in assay buffer without probenecid. The baseline RFUs were measured, followed by continuous measurement after Vehicle or MTII or ATP acute injections into wells. In agreement with my previous finding, compared to Vehicle treatment, U373 astrogloma cells did not show changes in RFU in response to MTII acute injections, indicative of no changes in iCa^{2+} levels regardless of concentration used (**Figure 4.5.2-2 A&B**). ATP increased iCa^{2+} levels compared to Vehicle, showing consistency in results between both experimental approaches (**** $p=0.0001$ compared to Vehicle) (**Figure 4.5.2-2 A&B**). The addition of probenecid prevented the injection artefacts previously observed. Therefore, this method was applied in subsequent studies.

Figure 4.5.2-2 Optimised intracellular calcium (iCa²⁺) assay protocol: Melanotan II (MTII) did not increase iCa²⁺ levels in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated in 1X Fluo-4 AM in assay buffer and probenecid for 1 hour at 37°C. Baseline fluorescence was measured before wells were injected with Vehicle (ddH₂O), MTII (0.1-100nM) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100μM), and the relative fluorescence unit (RFU) was then measured continually for 90 seconds. **A:** Representative line graph of real time reading change in fluorescence following injection of drugs, calculated as maximum fold change normalised to baseline. **B:** Calculated maximum fold change in fluorescence following injection of drugs, normalised to baseline. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. ATP ****p=0.0001 compared to Vehicle. n=3 independent cell cultures in three independent plates. ns= not significant, p>0.05. s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean.

4.5.3 MTII injections did not increase iCa^{2+} levels in mouse cortical astrocytes *in-vitro*

I next tested if MTII treatment could induce increases in iCa^{2+} in mouse cortical astrocytes. The experiments used the manufacturer's protocol, including probenecid with the Fluo-4 AM dye, to avoid injection artefacts. MTII injections did not increase iCa^{2+} compared to Vehicle; in contrast, ATP treatment increased iCa^{2+} in mouse cortical astrocytes **** $p < 0.0001$ (**Figure 4.5.3-1 A&B**). This concurs with my finding in human U373 astroglioma cells (**Figure 4.5.2-1 and Figure 4.5.2-2**).

Figure 4.5.3-1 Mouse cortical astrocytes did not increase intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels in response to Melanotan II (MTII) treatment

Mouse cortical astrocytes were seeded at a density 2×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated in 1X Fluo-4 AM in assay buffer and probenecid for 1 hour at 37°C . Baseline fluorescence was measured for 10 seconds before cells were injected with Vehicle (ddH₂O), MTII (0.1-100nM) and adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100 μM), and the relative fluorescence unit (RFU) was then measured for 90 seconds. **A**: Representative line graph of real time reading change in fluorescence following injection of drugs, calculated as maximum foldchange normalised to baseline. **B**: Calculated maximum fold change in fluorescence following injection of drugs, normalised to baseline. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. ATP **** $p=0.0001$. $n=3$ independent cell cultures in three independent plates. ns= not significant, $p>0.05$. s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

4.5.4 Setmelanotide treatment did not increase iCa^{2+} levels in mouse cortical astrocytes

Setmelanotide treatment appears to not increase iCa^{2+} levels in mouse cortical astrocytes *in-vitro* (**Figure 4.5.4-1 A&B**). ATP appears to increase iCa^{2+} levels compared to Vehicle (**Figure 4.5.4-1 A&B**). Although One-Way ANOVA was used, no statistical conclusions could be drawn due to the low experimental number. Therefore, the intentions of these results are to describe the data and demonstrate pilot data to warrant further investigations in the future.

Figure 4.5.4-1 Setmelanotide did not increase intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels in mouse cortical astrocytes

Mouse cortical astrocytes were seeded at a density 2×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated in 1X Fluo-4 AM in assay buffer and probenecid for 1 hour at 37°C . Baseline fluorescence was measured for 10 seconds before wells were injected with Vehicle (ddH₂O), Setmelanotide (0.1-100nM) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100 μM), and the relative fluorescence unit (RFU) was then measured for 90 seconds. **A**: Representative line graph of real time changes in fluorescence following drug injections, calculated as maximum fold change normalised to baseline. **B**: maximum fold change in RFU following injection of drugs, normalised to baseline. $n=2$ independent cell cultures in two independent plates. s =seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

4.5.5 Inwardly rectifying potassium channels Kir 4.1 & Kir 7.1 were expressed in the mouse brain, mouse cortical astrocytes and the human U373 astrogloma cell line

Mouse brain tissue was used as a positive control tissue (**Figure 4.5.5-1 A**). Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*GAPDH*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*GFAP*) were used as an internal housekeeping gene and markers of astrocytes, respectively (**Figure 4.5.5-1 A-C**). In support of published data indicating expression of *Kir 7.1* in the mouse brain (Papanikolaou, Lewis and Butt, 2019) and *Kir 4.1* in U373 cells (Olsen & Sontheimer, 2004; Tan et al., 2008; Zurolo et al., 2012), I demonstrated that both the human U373 astrogloma cell line and mouse cortical astrocytes express *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1* (**Figure 4.5.5-1 B&C**).

Figure 4.5.5-1 Gene expression of inwardly rectifying potassium channels Kir 4.1 and Kir 7.1 in mouse cortical brain tissue, mouse cortical astrocytes and human U373 astroglioma cells

Reverse transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR) was used to detect amplified cDNA products from mouse cortical brain tissue **(A)** mouse cortical astrocytes **(B)** and the human U373 astroglioma cell line **(C)** using primers designed to target mouse and human *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1*, and positive controls glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*gapdh*), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (*gfap*). L represents the DNA ladder of 1Kb (Kilobases). H₂O and -CTRL represent negative controls; H₂O; distilled water; -CTRL consists of a master mix, random primers, and water without cDNA template (no template control). n=3 independent cell cultures and two independent brain cDNA samples.

4.5.6 Impact of MCRs modulation with MTII on TI uptake in human U373 astroglioma cells

MTII pre-treatments of 5 minutes did not alter thallium uptake compared to Vehicle in U373 cells (**Figure 4.5.6-1 A-D**). A positive control was assessed at the time but had no effect on K⁺ flux (data not shown). Without a positive control, I am unable to conclude. Panel D of 15 minutes MTII pre-treatments demonstrates the data, but no statistical tests were applied due to the low experimental number.

Figure 4.5.6-1 Melanotan II (MTII) did not alter thallium sulphate (TI) uptake in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with thallium-sensitive FluxOR dye in a loading buffer for 1 hour at room temperature. Prior to measurement readings, cells were pretreated with Vehicle (ddH₂O) or MTII for 5 minutes (**A&B**) or 15 minutes (**C&D**). Baseline relative fluorescence units (RFU) was measured for 10 seconds before wells were injected with TI and measured continually for 70 seconds. **A&C** Representative trace of TI uptake calculated as fold change normalised baseline. **B&D** Representation of rate of change in RFU per second. **B**: Unpaired t-test. B: n=6; D: n=2 independent cell cultures. ns=not significant, $p > 0.05$. s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

As in my initial studies, MTII (1nM) did not elevate TI uptake in human U373 astroglioma cells. Given the absence of a positive control for validating TI uptake via potassium channel modulation, troubleshooting was essential. Initially, I tested MTII at a higher concentration (1 μ M) to observe its pharmacological response. Typically, there is a dose-response relationship in pharmacology, where increasing the dose of a drug results in a greater response until a plateau is reached. At lower concentrations, such as 1nM, the response might be lower than a higher concentration like 1 μ M, which could provide a more robust activation of the MCRs. Cells were also treated with ATP (100 μ M) as a positive control. ATP is a well-known modulator of potassium channels, and Kir 4.1 is reported as ATP-sensitive in astrocytes (C. Gu, 2016; Hibino et al., 2010; Takumi et al., 1995). Pre-treatment of U373 astroglioma cells for 5 (**Figure 4.5.6-2 A&B**) or 15 minutes (**Figure 4.5.6-2 C&D**) with MTII (1 μ M) or ATP (100 μ M) increased TI uptake following injection, compared to Vehicle, suggesting increased potassium channel opening.

Figure 4.5.6-2 1µM Melanotan II (MTII) increased thallium sulphate (TI) uptake in human U373 astroglioma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with TI-sensitive FluxOR dye in a loading buffer for 1 hour at room temperature. Cells were then loaded with assay buffer and pretreated with Vehicle (ddH₂O) or MTII (1µM) or adenosine triphosphate (ATP; 100 µM) for 5 minutes (**A&B**) or 15 minutes (**C&D**). Baseline relative fluorescence units (RFU) was measured for 10 seconds before cells were injected with thallium sulphate (TI) and measured continuously for 70 seconds. **A&C**: Representative trace of TI uptake calculated as fold change normalised to baseline. **B&D**: Representation of rate of change in RFU per second. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle MTII *p= 0.0249; **p=0.0042; or ATP ***p=0.0007; n=3 independent cell cultures in three independent plates. s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean.

4.5.7 Impact of increasing MTII concentrations and SHU9119 treatment on TI uptake in the human U373 astrogloma cell line

I demonstrated that 1 μ M MTII pre-treatment for 5 or 15 minutes increased TI uptake in human U373 astrogloma cells (**Figure 4.5.6-2 A&D**). However, 1 μ M of MTII is not a concentration reflective of those used in my previous studies in **Chapter 3**, where I demonstrated activation of signalling cascades downstream of MCRs at much lower concentrations of MTII. I decided to test lower concentrations to determine if the same effect could be observed using 100nM and 500nM of MTII. I used treatment with the MCR antagonist SHU9119 to determine if it can reduce TI uptake in these cells. Compared to Vehicle treated controls, it appears both 100nM and 500nM MTII pre-treatment increased TI uptake (**Figure 4.5.7-1 A&B**) and SHU9119 decreased thallium sulphate uptake (**Figure 4.5.7-1 C&D**). However, no statistical analysis can be performed on the data in **Figure 4.5.7-1 B** due to the low number of experiments, although provides preliminary pilot data.

Figure 4.5.7-1 Melanotan II (MTII) at nanomolar concentrations increased thallium sulphate (TI) uptake, while SHU9119 reduced TI uptake in the U373 astrogloma cell line

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with TI-sensitive FluxOR dye in a in loading buffer for 1 hour at room temperature. Cells were washed and loaded with assay buffer then pretreated with Vehicle (ddH₂O) or MTII (100nM, 500nM) or SHU9119 (1µM) for 5 minutes. Baseline fluorescence was measured for 10 seconds before wells were injected with TI. **A&C:** Representative real time trace of TI uptake calculated as fold change normalised to baseline. **B&D:** Representation of rate of change in RFU per second. **D:** One Way-ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. n= 3 independent cell cultures; Compared to Vehicle; **p= 0.0070; s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

With a view to replicating the findings in **section 4.5.6** I repeated the experiments with a further two to three independent cell cultures. Unexpectedly, there was no increase in TI when cells were pretreated with 100nM MTII (**Figure 4.5.7-2 A&B**). Due to this unexpected result the experiments were revisited with fresh reagents. A concentration response of MTII was performed in human U373 astroglioma cell line, with ATP a positive control. ATP pre-treatment increased TI uptake, but MTII pre-treatments (all concentrations) had no effect on TI uptake in U373 cells (**Figure 4.5.7-2 C&D**). These experiments were performed at the end of my doctoral studies, and it is possible that MTII degraded and is no longer effective given long-term storage and contribution of other environmental factors. A need to repeat these experiments with fresh MTII may address this issue. Due to concerns regarding consistency and reproducibility a decision was made to stop these experiments.

Figure 4.5.7-2 MTII did not modulate TI uptake in human U373 astroglioma cells during experimental replication

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 in 96 well plates overnight. Cells were incubated with thallium sulphate-sensitive FluxOR dye in a loading buffer for 1 hour at room temperature. Prior to measurement readings, cells were replaced with assay buffer and then pretreated with Vehicle (ddH₂O) or ATP (100 µM) or MTII (100nM or 1, 10, 100 and 1µM) for 5 minutes (**A-D**). Baseline relative fluorescence units (RFU) per second was measured for 10 seconds before wells were injected with TI. **A&C**: Representative trace of TI uptake calculated as fold change normalised to baseline. **B&D**: Representation of rate of change in RFU per second. **B**: Unpaired t-test; **D**: One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. n=3/7 independent cell cultures. Compared to Vehicle **p=0.011; ns=not significant, p>0.05; s=seconds. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean.

4.6 Discussion

Calcium and potassium ion dynamics play a role in astrocyte function (Kofuji & Newman, 2004; Scemes & Giaume, 2006); however, the impact of treatment with melanocortin ligands on astrocytes' calcium and potassium ion dynamics had not been examined. In this chapter, I have shown in my hands the MCR agonists MTII and Setmelanotide did not increase intracellular calcium levels (iCa^{2+}) in the human U373 astroglioma cell line or mouse cortical astrocytes. Yet, ATP increased iCa^{2+} levels in these cells, confirming that the iCa^{2+} assay was working. This data does not support my hypothesis that iCa^{2+} levels in mouse and human astrocytes will be elevated following MCR pharmacological modulation. I have demonstrated that mouse cortical astrocytes and human U373 astroglioma cell line express inward rectifying potassium channels *Kir 4.1* and *Kir 7.1* using PCR. Despite early positive indications, I cannot reliably confirm the effect of treatment with melanocortin ligands on potassium channel modulation in astrocytes due to the challenges with assay reproducibility.

4.6.1 Key findings

- **Calcium signalling in astrocytes:** Neither human U373 astroglioma cells nor mouse cortical astrocytes demonstrated increases in intracellular calcium (iCa^{2+}) levels in response to MCR agonists MTII and Setmelanotide.
- **Potassium ion flux:** Initial data suggested that MCR ligands modulate potassium ion flux in astrocytes. However, inconsistencies in the dataset leave this finding uncertain.

4.6.2 Human astroglioma cell line and mouse cortical astrocytes did not increase iCa^{2+} ion levels *in-vitro* in response to MCR agonists MTII and Setmelanotide

In **Chapter 3** I investigated signalling pathways modulated downstream of treatment with MCR ligands in human U373 astroglioma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes. The conventional signalling pathway that modulates iCa^{2+} is the protein lipase C β 3 (PLC β 3) inositol trisphosphate (IP3) pathway. I observed subtle changes in PLC β 3 phosphorylation in human U373 astroglioma cells in response to MTII pre-treatment, although there was no statistical significance (**Chapter 3, section 3.5.7**). While suggestive of a potential mechanism to increase iCa^{2+} , this alone does not confirm the ability to elevate iCa^{2+} downstream of MCR activation. Elevations in iCa^{2+} can occur independently of PLC-IP3 activation through other coupling mechanisms (Durkee et al., 2019; Navarrete et al., 2012; Parpura et al., 2011; Petravicz et al., 2008; Takata et al., 2011). For MCRs, this is demonstrated by pharmacological modulation of overexpressed MC5R in HEK293 cells, which showed increases in iCa^{2+} not associated with IP3 (Hoogduijn et al., 2002). Additionally, as MCR pharmacological modulation has been shown to increase extracellular regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) signalling, as I observed, and MCR mediated ERK1/2 signalling independent of calcium fluxes (Herraiz et al., 2009, 2011), it was hypothesised that MCR activation will modulate iCa^{2+} levels directly or indirectly of ERK1/2 signalling.

The calcium ion assay data I present in this chapter did not support our hypothesis and indicated that astrocytes do not increase their iCa^{2+} levels upon treatment with MCR ligands. This may suggest that ERK1/2 had no direct or indirect effect on iCa^{2+} ion modulation. This is in contrast to Sharma et al., who used an assay with Fura-2 AM dye that showed Ca^{2+} modulation when pharmacologically stimulating endogenous MC4R with 1 μ M melanocyte-stimulating hormone (MSH) in mouse hypothalamic GT1-7 cells and some MC4R variants transfected in HEK293 cells (Sharma et al., 2020). Fura-2 AM is a ratio metric dye that measures changes in calcium signals. They found that when stimulated with 1 μ M MSH, wild type and some MC4R variants can

increase intracellular calcium ions, whilst some MC4R variants had a reduction or no response (Sharma, Thibodeau and Lytton, 2020). Therefore, it is possible that changes in iCa^{2+} following treatment with melanocortin ligands could be cell-type dependent. Yet, it is also possible that subtle changes in iCa^{2+} in response to pharmacological MCR modulation could be detected using Fura-2 AM dye but not Fluo-4 AM dye as it is a single wave calcium indicator and non-ratio metric so which emission intensity depends on the level of bound calcium (Lock et al., 2015; Paredes et al., 2008). It is possible that MCR modulation by ligands does not rapidly increase iCa^{2+} levels and is instead time dependent. This theory may be supported by the findings in **Chapter 5** of my metabolic studies, where acute MTII treatments did not immediately influence cell metabolism, unlike longer pre-treatment drug incubations.

Another possible explanation in absence of iCa^{2+} ion modulation is that IP3 activation and IP3 receptors are regulated by cAMP and PKA phosphorylation to modulate iCa^{2+} ion levels (Ferris et al., 1991; Taylor, 2017). In my signalling studies, I observed that PKA was not phosphorylated by MTII in human and mouse astrocytes. Contrarily, MTII showed lower potency in increasing iCa^{2+} levels but increased cAMP in HEK293 cells transfected with MC3R (Langouche et al., 2001). Although I did not see increased PKA phosphorylation, I did not measure cAMP formation, which could be a contributing factor in the absence of iCa^{2+} ion modulation. This suggests a potential crosstalk between the two signalling pathways to modulate iCa^{2+} ions in response to MCR activation in astrocytes. However, multiple studies have demonstrated increases in iCa^{2+} in various MCR transfected cells (Berger, 1986; Buffey et al., 1992; Hoogduijn et al., 2002; Jain et al., 2018; Kim et al., 1997; Konda et al., 1994; Kumar et al., 2021; Langouche et al., 2001; Mountjoy et al., 2001; Newman et al., 2006; Roudbaraki et al., 1999). This may be attributed to the over expressed MCRs that may show enhanced effects that do not reflect on cell physiology compared to that of endogenous MCR expression which may show subtle changes. Therefore, my findings may suggest that MCR activation in astrocytes using an endogenous cell model does not modulate iCa^{2+} ions, as opposed to other cell types using overexpressed models. However, other measures of iCa^{2+} modulation would be required to confirm this.

In summary, I have observed that MCR pharmacological modulation with MTII and Setmelanotide in human U373 cells and mouse cortical astrocytes did not increase iCa^{2+} levels. However, this was limited to *in-vitro* Fluo-4 AM calcium imaging methodology and requires secondary measures such as Fura-2 single cell imaging, cAMP/IP3 assays, and *in-vivo* calcium imaging to increase confidence in the findings. Overall, the effect of MTII / Setmelanotide or other melanocortin ligands on iCa^{2+} levels in astrocytes remains in question.

4.6.3 The effect of pharmacological modulation of MCRs on inwardly rectifying potassium channel activity in the human U373 astroglioma cell line

In agreement with published evidence on the expression of *Kir 7.1* in mouse astrocytes (Papanikolaou et al., 2019) and *Kir 4.1* expression in human glioma cells (Olsen & Sontheimer, 2004; Tan et al., 2008; Zurolo et al., 2012), I observed gene expression of these inwardly rectifying potassium channels in human U373 astroglioma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes by reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). In contrast to this, another published study reported that *Kir 7.1* was not expressed in rat astrocytes (Lv et al., 2022), but it is possible that this is a species-related difference.

Although I confirmed gene expression of *Kir 7.1* and *Kir 4.1* in the cell models used for these studies, mRNA gene expression does not always translate to protein (Kendrick, 2012). This highlights the necessity of investigating these channels at a protein level using Western Blotting. Although my experiments with 1 μ M, 100 nM, and 500 nM MTII showed modulation of potassium channels by increasing thallium sulphate (TI) uptake in human U373 cells, assay reproducibility issues prevent me from drawing firm conclusions. However, Ghamari et al. demonstrated similar potassium flux changes using MCR ligand concentrations of 100 nM and 200 nM on HEK293 cells transfected with MCRs (Ghamari-Langroudi et al., 2015).

One possible reason for my inconsistent results could be the unreliability of the assay and reagents due to shelf life or MTII degradation. Additionally, biological factors may explain my findings. Cell lines exhibit inherent variabilities from their parental cancers, influencing their suitability as models. Studies have shown that cell passage and conditioned medium factors affect cell physiology, signalling, and potassium channel activity. Serial passage of cell lines over time results in genotypic and phenotypic variations, causing heterogeneity in cultures (Calles et al., 2006; Esquenet et al., 1997; Hongshi Yu et al., 1997; Joosten & Shuler, 2003; Kaur & Dufour, 2012; Lin et al., 2003; O'Driscoll et al., 2006; Sambuy et al., 2005; Taciak et al., 2018; Wenger et al., 2004; Woloschak,

1997). Glioma cell models, including U-251 (closely related to U373), show genetic drift and phenotypic changes due to long-term culture and passage numbers (Dai & Holland, 2001; Kaur & Dufour, 2012; Torsvik et al., 2014; Yavuz, 2022). For example, U-251 cells exhibit different profiles in culture, possibly linked to passage number changes (Diao et al., 2019). Despite using U373 cells between passages 18 and 30, genetic changes may have influenced potassium channel activity. The American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) notes that cell line passaging can affect cell behaviour. Interestingly, it has been reported that mis localisation of Kir channel proteins to intracellular compartments can result in a lack of Kir channel currents in glioma cells. Additionally, immature versus mature astrocytes exhibit different Kir channel localization and currents (Olsen & Sontheimer, 2004). While I did not investigate protein expression or localization of Kir channels during my studies, it is possible that mis localisation occurred between cell passage numbers, and genetic profile variances may have contributed to some of the variations in the effects I observed. This issue could be linked to the inherent variability and genetic drift associated with long-term cell culture and serial passaging in cancer cell lines.

Furthermore, GPCR activation, including MC4R in HEK293 cells, regulates Kir7.1 through glycosylation, significantly reducing the glycosylation complex without altering cell surface expression but decreasing channel activity (Carrington et al., 2018). This could have occurred in my experiments, where potassium channel activity decreased between passage numbers. These factors highlight the importance of replicating these experiments in primary astrocytes to ensure more consistent and reliable results. Future experiments investigating MCR glycosylation in primary astrocytes could provide deeper insights into MCR-mediated potassium modulation. By implementing these strategies, future experiments can better address the issues related to cancer cell lines and glycosylation, leading to more reliable and consistent results in the study of MCR-mediated potassium modulation.

Due to the unreliability of the data in this case, I cannot reach any conclusions about the effects of pharmacological modulation of MCRs on potassium channel activity in astrocytes. However, since MC4R couples to Kir7.1 independently of

G proteins, regulating its activity in hypothalamic neurons, I speculate that MCR pharmacological modulation in astrocytes could support brain neuronal activity by regulating potassium buffering through modulation of inwardly rectifying potassium channels (Ghamari-Langroudi, et al., 2015; Ghamari-Langroudi et al., 2018; Litt et al., 2018). Further testing is required using measures in addition to the FluxOR Potassium Ion Channel Assay used in this study, complemented by mechanistic studies looking at Kir channel coupling to MCRs.

4.6.4 Conclusion

Astrocytes are known to signal via increases in iCa^{2+} levels through GPCRs through various pathways (Khakh & McCarthy, 2015; Scemes & Giaume, 2006; Verkhratsky et al., 2012). Additionally, astrocytes express inwardly rectifying potassium channels that are known to play an essential role in potassium ion buffering (Olsen & Sontheimer, 2004; Papanikolaou et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2008; Zurolo et al., 2012). However, in this chapter, both human U373 astrogloma cells and mouse cortical astrocytes did not increase their iCa^{2+} levels in response to MCR agonists: MTII and Setmelanotide. While initial data indicated that MCR ligands modulated potassium ion flux in astrocytes, this remains in question due to inconsistency in the dataset. As my studies were limited to *in-vitro* experiments using a single methodology, I cannot rule out the possibility of subtle changes in iCa^{2+} levels that are not detectable using Fluo4 AM method. The data resulting from this chapter are summarised in **Figure 4.6.4-1**, which shows a hypothetical proposed model of how pharmacological MCR activation modulates calcium and potassium dynamics.

Figure 4.6.4-1 Summary of Chapter 4 with a proposed hypothetical model in astrocytes

ERK1/2 phosphorylation indicated potential changes in iCa^{2+} in astrocytes downstream of pharmacological MCR stimulation in astrocytes. Ca^{2+} indicates calcium ions. MCR pharmacological modulation with MCR ligands showed inconclusive potassium ion uptake (K^+). Both are indicated with a dashed line. The red cross is a theory of the absence of increased iCa^{2+} due to the inactivation of the PKA and PLC pathways involved in iCa^{2+} modulation. Figure created with Biorender.

5 IMPACT OF MCR LIGANDS ON CELL METABOLISM IN ASTROCYTES

5.1 Introduction

Regulation of cell metabolism is essential for energy homeostasis and physiology. Cell metabolism encompasses a variety of processes that are important to regulate physiological activity and provide cellular energy. It is required to provide the energy necessary for various physiological processes and functions essential for life. Cell metabolism provides the energy we require for muscle contraction and nerve impulse transmission. Similarly, cell metabolism also provides energy for immune and brain cells to mount effective responses required for physiological functions (Bonvento & Bolaños, 2021).

Astrocytes are known for supporting neuronal function and neurotransmitter recycling whilst engaging in various metabolic pathways to produce molecules for their own maintenance (Weber & Barros, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023).

Astrocytes are nutrient-sensing and can take up glucose and other substrates from the bloodstream and metabolise them (Weber & Barros, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). They can also create energy substrates through de novo synthesis (a process of synthesizing complex molecules from simple molecular precursors).

In common with many other cells, metabolism in astrocytes involves two main processes: anabolism and catabolism. Anabolism consists of synthesising complex molecules and reactions, including protein synthesis, which leads to the production of carbohydrates and lipids and DNA replication. These anabolic reactions require energy, whereas catabolism, the opposite, involves the breakdown of complex molecules, leading to the release of energy. Catabolic reactions, such as glycolysis and mitochondrial respiration, generate adenosine triphosphate (ATP), the primary energy source required to meet cellular energy demand. Glycolysis breaks down glucose into smaller molecules, leading to ATP production. One glucose molecule can lead to the generation of two pyruvate molecules that can then be converted to two lactate or two acetyl-CoA molecules through a series of enzymatic reactions. **Figure 5.1-1** gives a

simplified schematic diagram of glycolysis. Astrocytes can also store glucose as glycogen, a polysaccharide, broken down into glucose-1-phosphate during periods of high energy demand or glucose shortage to sustain energy production. The end products of glycolysis, such as acetyl-CoA, can then enter further metabolic pathways, such as aerobic respiration, depending on the availability of oxygen and the specific metabolic needs of the cell. The acetyl-CoA formed downstream of glycolysis can enter the mitochondria for mitochondrial respiration. **Figure 5.1-2** demonstrates a simplified schematic of mitochondrial respiration during resting and stimulated metabolic activity. Both glycolysis and mitochondrial respiration tightly regulate and maintain cellular energy homeostasis. However, regulating cell metabolism is far more complex than described here, involving networks of enzymes, signalling molecules, hormones, and other external and internal signals such as cellular energy levels and nutrient availability. These metabolic demands vary dynamically in response to cellular activity and the overall physiological state of the organism, fluctuating between resting and stimulated metabolic rates. This system ensures cells have the energy and molecules required to function while removing waste products to prevent pathology. Disruptions in cellular homeostasis and metabolic dysfunction in astrocytes contribute to neurological disorders and pathological conditions, including dementia, obesity, and diabetes (Zhang et al., 2023). Overall, astrocyte metabolism is linked to brain function and plays an essential role in overall brain homeostasis and the organism's physiology.

Figure 5.1-1 Glycolysis, a catabolic anaerobic process within cell metabolism

This process occurs in the cell's cytoplasm and does not require oxygen, so is an anaerobic process. Glycolysis starts with the breakdown of a single glucose molecule, a six-carbon sugar, phosphorylated by the enzyme hexokinase. Kinases are not shown in this diagram for simplicity. Phosphorylation of glucose requires one molecule of ATP, converting glucose into glucose-6-phosphate. Then glucose-6-phosphate is converted into fructose-6-phosphate by the enzyme phosphoglucose isomerase. Fructose-6-phosphate is then phosphorylated by ATP to form fructose-1,6-bisphosphate, with the help of the enzyme phosphofructokinase-1. Fructose-1,6-bisphosphate is cleaved into two three-carbon molecules: dihydroxyacetone phosphate and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate (G3P) by the enzyme aldolase. G3P is then oxidised and phosphorylated by NAD⁺ to produce 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate, producing NADH in the process. Then, the enzyme phosphoglycerate kinase transfers a phosphate group from 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate to ADP, forming ATP and 3-phosphoglycerate. The 3-phosphoglycerate phosphate group is shifted to form phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) by the enzyme phosphoglycerate mutase and enolase. Finally, PEP is then converted into pyruvate by the enzyme pyruvate kinase, producing another molecule of ATP. The end products of glycolysis results in two molecules of pyruvate, and a net gain of two molecules of ATP and two molecules of NADH. Pyruvate can then be converted to lactate, serving as a metabolic fuel for many organs and the CNS, or conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA serving as a substrate for the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA).

Figure 5.1-2 An overview of resting and stimulated mitochondrial respiration. Mitochondrial respiration is an aerobic process requiring oxygen.

Downstream of glycolysis end products, Acetyl-CoA can enter the mitochondria as a substrate for the TCA cycle (tricarboxylic acid cycle). This process produces NADH and FADH₂ that are pumped out and used in the electron transport chain (ETC). The ETC process generates 38 ATP products. Figure from Biorender template.

As described in **Chapter 1**, MC3R and MC4R are primarily involved in metabolic homeostasis (Begrache et al., 2013; Krashes et al., 2016; You et al., 2016). However, studies have focused primarily on MC4R in neurons on metabolism and/or central melanocortin system modulation on energy/food intake in the context of obesity *in-vivo*, with less attention to *in-vitro* studies particularly those focused on non-neuronal cells such as astrocytes. There is some published evidence on the effect of melanocortin ligands on cell metabolism *in-vitro*. In primary astrocytes, NDP-MSH treatment reduces oxidative damage induced by palmitic acid (Ramírez et al., 2019). In xenopus limb cells, MC4R knockdown and AGRP overexpression increase glycolytic function and ATP production, assessed using the Glycolysis Stress Test and Mitochondrial Stress Test with the Seahorse BioAnalyzer (Zhang et al., 2018). In skeletal muscle cells and a myoblast cell line, α -MSH treatment on cells contributes to increased fatty acid oxidation through AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase) (An et al., 2007). MC1R signalling with the agonist BMS-470539 treatment on neuronal cells reduced levels of oxidative stress by controlling mitochondrial metabolism via the AMPK/SIRT1/PGC-1 α pathway to attenuate early brain injury (Xu et al., 2020). In melanoma cells, metabolic profiling demonstrates that α -MSH treatment results in increased levels of citric acid metabolites and amino acids suggesting enhanced cell metabolism (Seo et al., 2020).

Beside their other roles, astrocytes provide metabolic support to neurons by sensing and responding to changes in the central nervous system (CNS), to support neuronal function and brain homeostasis (Braga et al., 2024; Murphy-Royal et al., 2020). Neurons require a high amount of energy to function properly due to their high metabolic activity, and this is reflected in astrocytes in their increased glucose transport and metabolism compared with neurons (Jakoby et al., 2014). Astrocytes uptake glucose sourced from the blood and use glucose as the primary source of energy to then metabolise and produce lactate. Lactate is then secreted from astrocytes to neurons, as an energy substrate. This process is known as the astrocyte-neuron lactate shuttle, helping meet the high energy demand of neurons (Erllichman et al., 2008; Magistretti & Pellerin, 1999). However, an ongoing debate remains in place regarding the astrocyte-neurone lactate shuttle, as evidence highlights that this

is dependent on the availability of particular substrates and is context-dependent (Erlichman et al., 2008; Murphy-Royal et al., 2020). This highlights the importance of astrocyte metabolism in supporting neuronal function, and changes in astrocyte bioenergetics may thus influence neuronal activity and physiology.

5.2 Rationale & Hypothesis

To date, the characterisation of MCR's pharmacological modulation of mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis in astrocytes has not been investigated. In addition, incorporating findings from **Chapter 3**, the impact of glucose on ERK1/2 signalling in astrocytes provides a potential link between glucose availability and heightened metabolic responses. Increased glucose levels, as shown in U373 cells, led to upregulation of ERK1/2 phosphorylation, suggesting that glucose-rich conditions may enhance metabolic activity through ERK1/2-mediated pathways. This link highlights ERK1/2 as a potential mediator in astrocytic metabolic regulation under varying glucose conditions, emphasising the relevance of glucose-dependent ERK1/2 activation in the metabolic responses observed in astrocytes treated with MCR ligands. This thesis does not focus on the complex networks of metabolism but examines some of the changes in glycolysis and mitochondrial metabolism using the Seahorse Bioanalyzer assay. Since, changes in astrocyte metabolism may regulate neuronal function, here, I investigated the effect of MTII and Setmelanotide treatments on mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis in human U373 astrogloma cells using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer. As secondary measures of metabolism, I measured intracellular ATP (iATP), extracellular L-lactate uptake and mitochondrial membrane potential.

In Chapter 3, I investigated the impact of pharmacological modulation of astrocyte MCRs by examining changes in downstream signalling pathways in cells cultured in standard DMEM containing high glucose (25mM) and physiological brain glucose levels (2.5mM). However, as glucose is a fuel that may impact astrocyte cell metabolism, and as the previous findings were from cells cultured in high glucose conditions, it was essential to investigate metabolic changes in astrocytes cultured in physiological brain glucose levels in response to pharmacological stimulation.

In this chapter, the hypothesis tested is that pharmacological treatment of human U373 astroglioma cells with melanocortin ligands modulates mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis.

5.3 Aims

- 1) To evaluate the effects of high (25 mM) and brain physiological (2.5 mM) glucose concentrations on the basal metabolic phenotype of U373 astroglioma cells after five-hour incubations.
- 2) To assess the acute impact of MTII on basal cell metabolism in U373 cells.
- 3) To investigate the effects of acute versus prolonged MTII pre-treatment on basal metabolism in U373 cells.
- 4) To examine the influence of MCR ligands on mitochondrial and glycolytic pathways under metabolic stress.
- 5) To measure additional bioenergetic parameters relevant to U373 cell metabolism following MTII or Setmelanotide treatment.

5.4 Methods

Detailed methods can be found in Chapter 2.

Basal metabolic measurements in varied glucose conditions: Basal metabolic rates under high (25 mM) and low (2.5 mM) glucose concentrations were compared using real-time measurements of extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) and oxygen consumption rate (OCR) with the Seahorse BioAnalyzer XFe96.

Acute MCR ligand treatment: Five baseline measurement cycles of OCR/ECAR were recorded before injecting treatments. Wells were injected with Vehicle (assay buffer), MTII (1 nM or 1 μ M), or 2-deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50 mM) as a positive control. Continuous OCR/ECAR measurements were taken over 90 minutes post-injection.

MCR ligand pre-treatment: To assess the effects of prolonged MTII exposure, U373 cells in both glucose conditions (25 mM and 2.5 mM) were pre-treated with Vehicle, MTII (1 nM or 1 μ M), or 2DG (50 mM) for five hours and 24 hours. OCR and ECAR were recorded over time following these incubations.

Mitochondrial stress test: To analyse MCR ligand effects on astrocyte bioenergetics under stress, the Mitochondrial Stress Test (Agilent, 103015-100) was conducted using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer. U373 cells were pre-treated with Vehicle, MTII (1 nM), or Setmelanotide (1 nM) for five hours. Following basal respiration measurements, mitochondrial inhibitors—oligomycin, FCCP, and rotenone/antimycin (Rot/A)—were sequentially injected, with OCR/ECAR recorded for 90 minutes.

Glycolysis stress test: The Glycolysis Stress Test (Agilent, 103020-100) assessed the impact of MTII and Setmelanotide on glycolytic function in U373 cells. After a glucose-free incubation, glucose was added to induce maximal glycolytic activity, and ECAR measurements were taken over 90 minutes.

Additional metabolic assessments:

L-Lactate assay: To confirm glycolytic activity changes, extracellular L-lactate (E-L-Lactate) levels were measured following five-hour MTII pre-treatment using the L-lactate Assay Kit (Cayman Chemical, 700510). The L-lactate assay was used to measure the concentration of extracellular L-lactate in cell culture media. The assay measures the amount of L-lactate produced by cells, which is a direct indicator of the glycolytic rate. Elevated levels of extracellular L-lactate typically indicate increased glycolytic activity. The assay relies on an enzymatic reaction where L-lactate is converted to pyruvate by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). During this reaction, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) enzyme is reduced to NADH (H for hydrogen). The produced NADH then reacts with a substrate in the assay kit to produce a detectable fluorometric signal measured using a plate reader. The intensity of the signal is proportional to the concentration of L-lactate in the sample. By comparing the signal from the samples to a standard curve generated with known concentrations of L-lactate, the concentration of L-lactate in the samples can be determined.

Intracellular ATP (iATP):

The ATPlite assay (Perkin Elmer, 6016943) is designed to measure intracellular ATP (adenosine triphosphate) levels. ATP is a key indicator of cellular energy status and viability. High ATP levels correlate with active metabolism and healthy, viable cells, while low ATP levels indicate compromised cellular functions or cell death. Total iATP levels were measured using the ATPlite Luminescence Assay System (Perkin Elmer, 6016943) after 15 minutes and five hours of Vehicle, MTII (1 nM), or 2DG/oligomycin (50 mM/1 μ M) treatment.

Mitochondrial membrane potential: The Mitochondrial Membrane Potential Assay Kit (Abcam, ab287864) was used with TMRE dye to assess mitochondrial membrane potential. Cells treated with Vehicle, MTII (1 nM), Setmelanotide (1 nM), or FCCP (10 μ M) served as control. The “No TMRE” group are cells in the absence of the dye, providing a no stain control.

5.5 Results

5.5.1 High glucose conditions (25mM) increased baseline oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in the human U373 astroglioma cell line

Cells cultured in 25mM glucose DMEM showed higher baseline extracellular acidification rate (ECAR; an indicator of glycolysis), and oxygen consumption rate (OCR; an indicator of mitochondrial metabolism) compared to cells exposed to 2.5mM DMEM (**Figure 5.5.1-1 A-D**).

Figure 5.5.1-1 U373 astrogloma cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM) showed higher basal metabolism compared with cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM) after 5 hours in culture

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. Media was changed to seahorse XF Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Media (DMEM) media with either 2.5mM or 25mM glucose for five hours before measurement. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR; a proxy for oxidative phosphorylation) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR; a proxy for glycolysis) were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer XFe96. Data were normalised to total protein content assessed post-experiment using a Bradford reaction. **A&C** baseline of OCR and ECAR measured over time. **B&D** OCR/ECAR baseline levels taken from cycle 6 measurement of U373 cells in 2.5mM and 25mM glucose DMEM. Unpaired t-test. ****p=0.0001; n=12 wells, data are pooled from across two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.2 Acute treatment with MTII had no effect on baseline OCR and ECAR in human U373 astroglioma cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM)

Neither concentration of MTII altered OCR or ECAR compared to Vehicle treated cells (**Figure 5.5.2-1 A-D**). As anticipated, 2DG decreased ECAR compared to Vehicle treated cells (**** $p < 0.0001$) (**Figure 5.5.2-1 C-D**).

Figure 5.5.2-1 Melanotan II (MTII) treatment did not acutely impact oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U373 cells cultured in high glucose media (25mM)

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer. Data were normalised to total protein content. **A&B:** OCR and **C&D:** ECAR baseline measurements following injections into corresponding wells with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM or 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM) in U373 cells. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle **** $p=0.0001$; ns= not significant, $p>0.05$; $n=18-24$ wells, data are pooled from across two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.3 Five-hours of MTII pre-treatment increased OCR and ECAR in U373 astroglioma cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM)

A 5-hour incubation with either MTII concentration (1nM or 1 μ M) increased OCR compared to Vehicle treated cells (*** $p=0.0001$) (**Figure 5.5.3-1 A-B**). Compared to Vehicle, 2DG reduced ECAR and increased in OCR following five hours of pre-treatment, suggesting changes in cellular metabolism, and increased mitochondrial respiration (**Figure 5.5.3-1 A-D**). Interestingly, 1 μ M MTII increased ECAR compared to Vehicle but 1nM MTII decreased ECAR compared to Vehicle ($*p=0.0163$) (**Figure 5.5.3-1 C-D**).

Figure 5.5.3-1 Five hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased basal oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and altered extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U373 cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM)

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. OCR and ECAR were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer. Data were normalised to total protein content. **A&C** baseline of OCR and ECAR measured over time following five hours of pre-treatment with Vehicle (assay buffer), MTII (1nM or 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM). **B&D** OCR/ECAR baseline levels taken from cycle 6 measurement. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle * $p=0.0163$; **** $p=0.0001$; $n=24$ wells, data are pooled across from two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.4 Twenty-four hours of MTII pre-treatment modulated basal metabolism in human U373 astroglioma cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM)

Twenty-four hours of MTII pre-treatment increased OCR and ECAR compared to Vehicle in U373 cells cultured in high glucose DMEM (**** $p=0.0001$) (**Figure 5.5.4-1 A-D**). As expected, the positive control 2DG reduced ECAR compared to Vehicle (**** $p=0.0001$) (**Figure 5.5.4-1 A-D**).

Figure 5.5.4-1 Twenty-four hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased basal oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U737 cells cultured in high glucose conditions (25mM)

U737 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. OCR and ECAR were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 Bioanalyzer. Data were normalised to total protein content. **A&C** baseline of OCR and ECAR measured over time following five hours of pre-treatment with Vehicle (assay buffer), MTII (1nM or 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM). **B&D** OCR/ECAR baseline levels taken from cycle 6 measurement. following 24 hours pre-treatment with Vehicle (assay buffer), MTII (1nM or 1µM) or 2DG (50mM) in U737 cells. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. **** $p=0.0001$; $n=12$ wells, data are pooled from across two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.5 Acute MTII injections did not alter OCR and ECAR in human U373 astrogloma cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM)

MTII injections at both concentrations, 1nM or 1µM, did not acutely alter basal metabolism in comparison to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.5-1 A-D**); this finding corroborates with the data I presented in **section 5.5.2** in high glucose conditions. As expected, the positive control 2DG decreased ECAR compared to Vehicle (****p=0.0001), indicating inhibition of glycolysis, and slightly reduced OCR in the first 4 cycles after 2DG injection; however, this reduction was followed with an increase in OCR, as observed in the trace, indicating the reliance on mitochondrial respiration (**Figure 5.5.5-1 A-D**). However, as this was a positive control to demonstrate that cell metabolism could be acutely pharmacologically manipulated in these cells, the pattern of changes in OCR in response to 2DG were not the key question of my studies.

Figure 5.5.5-1 Acute Melanotan II (MTII) injections did not change basal oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in U373 cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM)

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. OCR and ECAR were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer. Data were normalised to total protein content. **A&B:** OCR and **C&D:** ECAR baseline measurements followed by Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM and 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM) injections into corresponding wells. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle ****p=0.0001; n=18-24 wells pooled from across two independent experimental plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.6 Five hours MTII pre-treatment modulated baseline OCR and ECAR in U373 astrogloma cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions

U373 cells cultured in physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM) pre-treated with MTII (1nM or 1µM) for five hours increased OCR and ECAR compared to Vehicle (****p=0.0001) (**Figure 5.5.6-1 A-D**). This corroborates the findings I observed in high glucose cell culture conditions in **section 5.5.3**. 2DG reduced OCR and ECAR compared to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.6-1 C-D**).

Figure 5.5.6-1 Five hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U373 cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM)

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. OCR and ECAR were measured using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer XFe96. Data were normalised to total protein content. **A&C** baseline of OCR and ECAR measured over time following five hours of pre-treatment with Vehicle (assay buffer), MTII (1nM or 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM). **B&D** OCR/ECAR baseline levels taken from cycle 6 measurement. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle ****p=0.0001; n=12-13 wells, data were pooled from across two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.7 Twenty-four hours of MTII pre-treatment increased OCR and ECAR in U373 astrogloma cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions.

MCR activation in U373 cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM) with twenty-four hours of MTII (1nM or 1µM) pre-treatment increased OCR and ECAR compared to Vehicle (****p=0.0001) (**Figure 5.5.7-1 A-D**). This finding corroborates the data I presented in **section 5.5.4**, which shows increased OCR and ECAR in U373 cells pre-treated with MTII in high glucose conditions. As expected, 2DG (50mM) decreased ECAR but increased OCR when compared to Vehicle (****p=0.0001), suggesting inhibition of glycolysis and reliance on mitochondrial respiration (**Figure 5.5.7-1 A-D**).

Figure 5.5.7-1 Twenty-four hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased basal oxygen consumption (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U737 cells cultured in brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM)

U737 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well overnight in 96 well Seahorse plates. OCR and ECAR were measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer. Data was normalised to total protein content. **A&B:** OCR and **C&D:** ECAR measurements following 24 hours pre-treatment with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM and 1µM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50mM) in U737 cells. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Compared to Vehicle ****p=0.0001; n=12 wells, data are pooled from across two independent plates. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.8 Five hours of MTII pre-treatment increased mitochondrial function in human U373 astrogloma cells subjected to mitochondrial stress

My findings indicated that MTII pre-treatments increased basal OCR and ECAR in human U373 cells cultured in both glucose conditions. To better mimic brain physiological conditions, all the following experiments further interrogating the impact of MTII on astrocyte metabolism were performed under brain physiological glucose conditions (2.5mM).

In agreement with my previous findings, when compared to Vehicle, five hours of MTII pre-treatment increased basal mitochondrial respiration (OCR; $**p=0.0068$) (**Figure 5.5.8-1 A&B**) and the inferred parameters calculated: ATP production ($**p=0.0091$) (**Figure 5.5.8-1 C**); maximal respiration and spare capacity ($***p=0.0002$) (**Figure 5.5.8-1 D&E**); non-mitochondrial respiration ($**p=0.0092$) (**Figure 5.5.8-1 F**); and proton leak ($**p=0.0059$) (**Figure 5.5.8-1 Figure 5.5.8-1 G**). There were no differences in coupling efficiency compared to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.8-1 H**).

Besides OCR, the Mitochondrial Stress Test also measures the extracellular acidification rate (ECAR). MTII pre-treatment increased basal ECAR when compared to Vehicle ($****p=0.0001$) (**Figure 5.5.8-2 A-B**), this corroborates with previous findings where I demonstrated MTII pre-treatments increased basal ECAR (**Figure 5.5.3-1, Figure 5.5.4-1 C&D, Figure 5.5.6-1 and Figure 5.5.7-1**). Following injections of the mitochondrial inhibitors Oligomycin, FCCP and Rot/A, MTII pre-treatment increased ECAR in U373 cells compared to Vehicle (**C: $***p=0.0004$; D: $***p=0.0038$; E: $**p=0.0012$**) (**Figure 5.5.8-2**). This suggests other catabolic changes in glycolysis or other metabolic substrates and/or glucose turnover via other pathways, such as the pentose phosphate pathway, in parallel to increased mitochondrial respiration.

A

Figure 5.5.8-1 Five hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased astrocyte mitochondrial metabolism when induced with mitochondrial stress

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well in Seahorse XF96 cell culture microplates. Oxidative phosphorylation, represented as the oxygen consumption rate (OCR) of the cells, was measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer in conjunction with a Mitochondrial Stress Test **A**: Representative trace of OCR of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of Oligomycin (Oligo; $0.5 \mu\text{M}$), Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; $1 \mu\text{M}$), and rotenone/antimycin (R/A; $0.5 \mu\text{M}$) during a Mitochondrial Stress Test as indicated by the vertical dotted line. **B**: Initial OCR measured before any inhibitors are added. **C**: Inferred ATP production following oligomycin injection calculated as the difference between the basal OCR and the OCR after oligomycin. **D**: Inferred maximal respiration following FCCP injection. **E**: Inferred calculated difference between the maximal respiration (after FCCP injection, which uncouples the mitochondrial membrane and drives maximum respiration) and the basal respiration rate (before any inhibitors are added). **F**: Inferred non-mitochondrial respiration following Rot/A injection **G**: Inferred calculated proton leak following the oligomycin injection (Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthase inhibitor). Oligomycin reduces ATP production, causing oxygen consumption due to proton leak across the mitochondrial membrane rather than ATP synthesis. **H**: inferred coupling efficiency calculated after the oligomycin injection by comparing the decrease in oxygen consumption (linked to ATP production) to the original basal respiration level. This provides insight into how effectively mitochondria are coupling oxygen consumption to ATP synthesis. Data were normalised per well to the total protein of the same well. Unpaired t-test, $n=87-93$ wells, pooled from three independent plates. Compared to Vehicle **B**: $**p=0.0068$; **C**: $**p=0.0091$; **D&E** $***p=0.0002$; **F**: $**p=0.0092$; **G**: $**p=0.0059$; **H**: ns= not significant, $p>0.05$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

Figure 5.5.8-2 Five hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) during the Mitochondrial Stress Test

ECAR was measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer during the Mitochondrial Stress Test in U373 cells **A**: Representative trace of ECAR of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of Oligomycin (Oligo; 0.5 μ M), Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; 1 μ M), and rotenone/antimycin (R/A; 0.5 μ M) as indicated by the vertical dotted line. Data were normalised to total protein. **B**: baseline ECAR levels prior to mitochondrial stress induction; **C**: illustrates the increase in ECAR following oligomycin addition, which inhibits mitochondrial adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production, prompting a compensatory increase in glycolysis; **D**: shows the increase in ECAR after the effect of FCCP, a protonophore that disrupts mitochondrial membrane potential and forces cells to rely further on glycolysis to meet energy demands, thereby reflecting maximal glycolytic response to mitochondrial uncoupling; **E**: displays increased ECAR following rotenone/antimycin A addition, which fully inhibits mitochondrial respiration, allowing for measurement of glycolysis-driven acidification independent of mitochondrial function. Unpaired t-test, n=87-93 wells, pooled from 3 independent plates. Compared to Vehicle B: ****p=0.0001; C: ***p=0.0004; D: ***p=0.0038; E: **p=0.0012. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.9 Pre-treatment with MTII for five hours did not modulate ECAR in human U373 astroglioma cells during the Glycolysis Stress Test

Five hours of MTII pre-treatment did not increase basal ECAR when compared to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.9-1 A-B**), which is in contrast to the increased ECAR observed in the Mitochondrial Stress Test (**Figure 5.5.9-1 A-E**). Similarly, glycolytic rate, glycolytic capacity, glycolytic reserve and non-glycolytic acidification rate did not change compared to Vehicle following injection of glucose, oligomycin and 2DG (**Figure 5.5.9-1 C-F**).

Figure 5.5.9-1 Pre-treatment with Melanotan II (MTII) for five hours did not modulate extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) in human U373 astrogloma cells during the Glycolysis Stress Test

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well in Seahorse XF96 cell culture microplates. ECAR was measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer **A**: Representative trace of ECAR of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of glucose (10mM), oligomycin (1 μ M), and 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50 mM) as indicated by the vertical dotted line. **B**: Basal ECAR before addition of glucose and inhibitors. **C**: Inferred calculated glycolysis following addition of glucose. **D**: Inferred glycolytic capacity following oligomycin injection. **E&F**: Inferred glycolytic reserve and non-acidification rate following 2-DG injection. Data were normalised per well to the total protein of the well. Unpaired t-test, $n=87-93$ wells, pooled from three independent plates. ns= not significant, $p>0.05$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.10 Five hours of MTII pre-treatment increased extracellular L-Lactate (E-L-Lactate) release from human U373 astroglioma cells

Five hours of MTII pre-treatment increased E-L-Lactate compared to Vehicle (* $p=0.0278$) (**Figure 5.5.10-1**). The positive control group (+ctrl; cells cultured in DMEM without glucose) decreased E-L-Lactate compared to Vehicle (** $p=0.0071$) (**Figure 5.5.10-1**).

Figure 5.5.10-1 Five hours of Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment increased extracellular lactate (E-L-Lactate) secretion from human U373 astrogloma cells

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 2.1×10^5 cells in a 6-well plate a day prior to experimentation. Cells were then pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) or deprived of glucose (positive control +Ctrl) for five hours. Then, cells were degassed for 1 hour at 37°C as per seahorse experiments, and the assay media was collected for extracellular lactate (E-L-Lactate) assessment. The E-L-Lactate assay was then performed as per the manufacturer's protocol, and fluorescence was measured using a plate reader. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test; $n=6$ independent cell cultures; compared to Vehicle * $p=0.0278$; ** $p=0.0071$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.11 Intracellular ATP (iATP) levels were not altered following 15 minutes or five hours of MTII pre-treatment in human U373 astroglioma cells

15 minutes and five hours of MTII pre-treatment did not change iATP levels when compared to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.11-1 A&C**). The combination of 2DG/OLIGO was added as a positive control, resulting in decreased iATP levels (* $p=0.0222$; ** $p=0.0065$) (**Figure 5.5.11-1 B&C**).

Figure 5.5.11-1 Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment did not alter intracellular adenosine triphosphate (iATP) levels in human U373 astroglioma cells

U373 cells were seeded at 4×10^3 cells in black 96 well plates a day prior to experimentation. On the day of experimentation, cells were pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) or 2-Deoxy-D-glucose / Oligomycin (2DG/OLIGO; 50mM/1μM) for 15 minutes (**A&B**) or five hours (**C**). Cells were then lysed, and iATP levels were measured using the ATPlite luminescence-based assay in a plate reader and normalised to total protein content. **A&B**: n=8/9 independent cell cultures unpaired t-test; ns= not significant, $p > 0.05$; compared to Vehicle * $p = 0.0222$; **C**: n=4 independent cell cultures; One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test; compared to Vehicle ** $p = 0.0065$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.12 Impact of MTII treatment on mitochondrial membrane potential in human U373 astroglioma cells

15 minutes and five hours of MTII pre-treatment did not modulate TMRE uptake into cells when compared to Vehicle treatment of U373 astroglioma cells **(Figure 5.5.12-1 A-B)**. This corroborates the absence of change in coupling efficiency after MTII pre-treatment as observed in the Mitochondrial Stress Test **(section 5.5.8)**. In contrast, the positive control, treatment with the mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation uncoupler FCCP decreased TMRE uptake when compared to Vehicle (**** $p=0.0001$; * $p=0.0155$) **(Figure 5.5.12-1 A-B)**. This indicates that the assay can detect changes in mitochondrial membrane potential in response to pharmacological manipulation.

Figure 5.5.12-1 Melanotan II (MTII) pre-treatment did not modulate mitochondrial membrane potential in human U373 astroglioma cells

U373 cells were seeded at 4×10^4 cells per well in a 96 well plate a day prior to experimentation. On the day of experimentation, cells were pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for 15 minutes or five hours. Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; $10 \mu\text{M}$), treatment was for 15 minutes as recommended by manufacturer. All wells then had Tetramethylrhodamine Ethyl Ester (TMRE; 200nM) (except no TMRE stain control) added for 15 minutes at 37°C . Cells were then washed with assay buffer as per manufacturers protocol and relative fluorescence units (RFU) were measured using a plate reader. Data were normalised to the average of Vehicle. **A:** 15 minutes pre-treatment; $n=8$ from independent cell cultures; Compared to Vehicle **** $p=0.0001$; **B:** five hours pre-treatment; $n=3$ from independent cell cultures; * $p=0.0155$ compared to Vehicle; ns=not significant, $p>0.05$; One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.13 Setmelanotide pre-treatment of U373 astrogloma cells increased mitochondrial function in the mitochondrial stress test

Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased basal mitochondrial respiration compared to Vehicle, prior to oligomycin injection (**p=0.0020) (**Figure 5.5.13-1 B**). Setmelanotide did not increase ATP production compared to Vehicle, as calculated following treatment with oligomycin (**Figure 5.5.13-1 C**), although the line trace of OCR suggests Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased OCR after oligomycin injection compared to Vehicle (**Figure 5.5.13-1 A**). However, Setmelanotide pre-treatment resulted in an increase in maximal respiration and spare capacity compared to Vehicle following FCCP injection (*p= 0.0319; *p=0.0399) (**Figure 5.5.13-1 D&E**). Like this, Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased non mitochondrial respiration and proton leak compared to Vehicle (*p=0.0106; **p=0.0062) (**Figure 5.5.13-1 F&G**) when cells were subjected to Rot/A injections but did not change coupling efficiency (**Figure 5.5.13-1 H**). This corroborates the findings of MTII treatment on U373 cells during the Mitochondrial Stress Test (**Figure 5.5.8-1**).

As previously mentioned, ECAR is measured in parallel to OCR during the Mitochondrial Stress Test. Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased basal ECAR when compared to Vehicle (**p=0.0008) (**Figure 5.5.13-2 A&B**). Following sequential injection of the mitochondrial inhibitors Oligomycin, FCCP and Rot/A, ECAR was calculated. Setmelanotide pre-treated cells showed increased ECAR in U373 cells compared to Vehicle following the addition of mitochondrial inhibitors (**B**: ***p=0.0008; **C**: ***p=0.0009; **D**: **p=0.0010; **E**: ***p=0.0008) (**Figure 5.5.13-2**). As with MTII findings on ECAR levels during the Mitochondrial Stress Test, this is suggestive of catabolic changes or usage of other metabolic substrates. And or that glucose turnover is occurring via the pentose phosphate pathway in parallel to increased mitochondrial respiration.

Oligomycin FCCP Rot/A

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

H

Figure 5.5.13-1 Five-hour Setmelanotide pre-treatment altered mitochondrial function in human U373 astrogloma cells

U373 cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well in Seahorse XF96 cell culture microplates. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) was measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer in conjunction with a Mitochondrial Stress Test **A**: Representative trace of extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or Setmelanotide (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of Oligomycin (Oligo; $0.5 \mu\text{M}$), Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; $1 \mu\text{M}$), and rotenone/antimycin (R/A; $0.5 \mu\text{M}$) during a Mitochondrial Stress Test as indicated by the vertical dotted lines. **B**: Initial OCR measured before any inhibitors are added. **C**: Inferred adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production following oligomycin injection calculated as the difference between the basal OCR and the OCR after oligomycin. **D**: Inferred maximal respiration following FCCP injection. **E**: Inferred calculated difference between the maximal respiration (after FCCP injection, which uncouples the mitochondrial membrane and drives maximum respiration) and the basal respiration rate (before any inhibitors are added). **F**: Inferred non-mitochondrial respiration following Rot/A injection **G**: Inferred calculated proton leak following the oligomycin injection (ATP synthase inhibitor). Oligomycin reduces ATP production, causing oxygen consumption due to proton leak across the mitochondrial membrane rather than ATP synthesis. **H**: Inferred coupling efficiency calculated after the oligomycin injection by comparing the decrease in oxygen consumption (linked to ATP production) to the original basal respiration level. This provides insight into how effectively mitochondria are coupling oxygen consumption to ATP synthesis. Data were normalised to total protein. Unpaired t-test, $n=87-93$ wells, pooled from three independent plates. **B**: $**p=**p=0.0020$; **D&E**: $*p=0.0319$; $*p=0.0399$; **F**: $**p=0.0062$; **G**: $*p=0.0106$ compared to Vehicle; ns= not significant, $p>0.05$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

Figure 5.5.13-2 Five-hour Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) during the mitochondrial stress

ECAR was measured using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer XFe96 during the Mitochondrial Stress Test in U373 cells **A**: Representative trace of ECAR of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or Setmelanotide (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of Oligomycin (Oligo; 0.5 μ M), Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; 1 μ M), and rotenone/antimycin (R/A; 0.5 μ M) as indicated by the vertical dotted lines. **B**: baseline ECAR levels prior to mitochondrial stress induction; **C**: illustrates the increase in ECAR following oligomycin addition, which inhibits mitochondrial adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production, prompting a compensatory increase in glycolysis; **D**: shows the increase in ECAR after the effect of FCCP, a protonophore that disrupts mitochondrial membrane potential and forces cells to rely further on glycolysis to meet energy demands, thereby reflecting maximal glycolytic response to mitochondrial uncoupling; **E**: displays increased ECAR following rotenone/antimycin A addition, which fully inhibits mitochondrial respiration, allowing for measurement of glycolysis-driven acidification independent of mitochondrial function. Data were normalised to total protein. Unpaired t-test, n=57-59 wells, pooled from two independent plates. Compared to Vehicle **B**: ***p=0.0008; **C**: ***p=0.0009; **D**: **p=0.0010; **E**: ***p=0.0008. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.14 Five-hours of Setmelanotide pre-treatment in human U373 cells did not impact ECAR during the glycolysis stress test

Five hours of Setmelanotide pre-treatment did not increase basal ECAR or the glycolytic rate (inferred) following glucose injection when compared to Vehicle **(Figure 5.5.14-1 A&C)**. Similarly, the inferred calculations reflecting glycolytic capacity, glycolytic reserve and non-glycolytic acidification rate after oligomycin and 2DG injection did not change compared to Vehicle **(Figure 5.5.14-1 D-F)**. This finding corroborates the Glycolysis Stress Test data I observed in U373 cells pre-treated with MTII **(section 5.5.9)**.

Figure 5.5.14-1 Setmelanotide pre-treatment did not modulate extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) during the Glycolysis Stress Test in human U373 astrogloma cells

Cells were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells per well in Seahorse XF96 cell culture microplates. ECAR was measured using the Seahorse XFe96 BioAnalyzer in conjunction with a Glycolysis Stress Test **A**: Representative trace of ECAR of U373 cells pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or Setmelanotide (1nM) for five hours followed by sequential injections of glucose (10mM), oligomycin (1 μ M), and 2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2DG; 50 mM) as indicated by the vertical dotted lines. **B**: Basal ECAR before addition of glucose and inhibitors. **C**: Inferred calculated glycolysis following addition of glucose. **D**: Inferred glycolytic capacity following oligomycin injection. **E&F**: Inferred glycolytic reserve and non-acidification rate following 2-DG injection. Data were normalised to total protein. Unpaired t-test, n=87-93 wells, pooled from three independent plates. **B-F** ns= not significant, $p > 0.05$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.5.15 Setmelanotide pre-treatment did not alter mitochondrial membrane potential in U373 astroglioma cells

15 minutes and five hours of Setmelanotide pre-treatment did not modulate TMRE uptake when compared to Vehicle in U373 astroglioma cells (**Figure 5.5.15-1 A&B**). This corroborates with the data indicating the absence of a change in coupling efficiency in the Mitochondrial Stress Test following Setmelanotide pre-treatment (**section 5.5.13**). In contrast, the positive control, treatment with the mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation uncoupler FCCP, decreased TMRE uptake when compared to Vehicle (**p=0.0081; ****p=0.0001) (**Figure 5.5-15-1 A-B**).

Figure 5.5.15-1 Setmelanotide pre-treatment did not modulate mitochondrial membrane potential in human U373 astrogloma cells

U373 cells were seeded at 4×10^4 cells in a 96 well plate a day prior to experimentation. On the day of experimentation, cells were pre-treated with Vehicle (assay buffer) or MTII (1nM) for 15 minutes or five hours. Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; $10 \mu\text{M}$), was added 15 minutes before then all wells were added with Tetramethylrhodamine Ethyl Ester (TMRE; 200nM) (except no TMRE stain control) for 15 minutes at 37°C . Cells were then washed with assay buffer as per manufacturers protocol and fluorescence was measured using a plate reader. Data were normalised to the average of Vehicle. **A:** 15 minutes pre-treatment; **B:** five hours pre-treatment; $n=6$ from independent cell cultures; $**p=0.0081$; $****p=0.0001$ compared to Vehicle; ns=not significant, $p>0.05$. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

5.6 Discussion

The melanocortin system plays a key role in cell metabolism and energy homeostasis to support physiological functions. Many studies demonstrated MCR activation effects on metabolism *in-vivo* using knock out or knock in models (Ghamari-Langroudi et al., 2018; Jain et al., 2018; Lute et al., 2014; Y. Xu et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2017). While astrocytes are implicated in neural circuits regulating systemic metabolism (Araque et al., 2014; Ellacott, 2022; García-Cáceres et al., 2019; Magistretti & Pellerin, 1999; Pellerin & Magistretti, 1994) and express MCRs, the role of MCR modulation on astrocyte cell metabolism remain unknown. In this Chapter, I have observed that human U373 astrogloma cells modulate their metabolism *in-vitro* in response to treatment with MCR ligands supporting my hypothesis.

5.6.1 Key findings

- **Glucose concentration and metabolic responses:** U373 cells exhibited altered metabolic activity under physiological glucose conditions (2.5 mM) compared to high glucose conditions (25mM).
- **Basal metabolic measurements:** MCR ligand pre-treatment of U373 cells increased basal oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR).
- **Effect of acute treatments:** Acute injections of MCR ligands did not produce any changes in OCR or ECAR in U373 cells.
- **Influence on mitochondrial respiration:** Prolonged exposure (five to twenty-four hours) with MTII enhanced basal OCR and ECAR in U373 cells.
- **Mitochondrial stress test (MST):** MTII pre-treatment increased mitochondrial respiration, as evidenced by enhanced OCR in U373 cells, and the inferred metabolic parameters.
- **Shift toward glycolysis:** Glycolytic activity, measured by ECAR, showed changes under mitochondrial stress associated with OCR
- **L-Lactate secretion:** U373 cells pre-treated with MTII for five hours exhibited increased extracellular L-lactate release.

5.6.2 The impact of cell culture media glucose concentrations on astrocyte metabolism

Glucose is the primary metabolite used in the brain to meet central nervous system energy demand and is an energy substrate that can affect cell metabolism measurements *in-vitro* (Abe et al., 2006). As discussed in **Chapter 3**, human U373 astrogloma cells are highly glycolytic cells that typically are maintained in cell culture conditions with high glucose (25mM) DMEM yet “normal” physiological brain glucose concentration is thought to be between 0.7mM – 2.5mM or 5.5 mM (Warburg O, Posener K, 1924; Silver and Erecinska, 1994; Silver and Erecińska, 1998; Abi-Saab et al., 2002; De Vries et al., 2003; Abe, Takahashi and Suzuki, 2006; Dunn-Meynell et al., 2009; Heiden, Cantley and Thompson, 2009; Starichaa et al., 2018). In **Chapter 3**, I addressed the impact of cell culture conditions on signalling by investigating the impact of MTII pre-treatment on extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) and protein kinase A (PKA) phosphorylation in high glucose DMEM conditions and physiological brain glucose conditions. This may be important for many reasons, including the fact that high glucose in DMEM can result in high glycogen storage (Abe et al., 2006). Therefore, it was initially important to assess how the metabolism of the U373 cells different between the two experimental conditions. I investigated the effect of 25mM and 2.5mM glucose concentrations on human U373 astrogloma baseline metabolism measuring oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR). I observed that human U373 astrogloma cells cultured in high glucose media (25mM) conditions compared to brain physiological glucose (2.5mM) conditions displayed increased basal metabolism. This suggests that astrocytes increased their metabolic activity when cultured in high glucose conditions. The increased ECAR in high glucose conditions corroborates with what is reported in many cancer lines reliant more on glycolysis due to the Warburg effect (Warburg O, Posener K, 1924). However, I have also observed increases in OCR and ECAR suggesting that in high glucose conditions astrocytes increase their overall cell metabolism using both mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis. This is corroborated by data generated by Dr Josie Robb during her doctoral studies in our laboratory, where she compared U373 cells and mouse primary cortical astrocytes, which indicated that U373 cells predominantly utilise glycolysis as a

source of energy, as opposed to relying on mitochondrial respiration, as observed in mouse primary astrocytes (Robb, 2020). However, I did not personally investigate cell metabolism in mouse astrocytes to directly compare.

5.6.3 Human U373 astroglioma cells showed changed metabolic activity in response to treatment with MCR agonists

There is some published evidence on the impact of melanocortin ligands on reactive oxygen species (ROS) production in mouse primary cortical astrocytes and cell metabolism in *Xenopus* cells *in-vitro* (Ramírez et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2018). Like what I observed after pre-treating cells with melanocortin ligands, Zhang et al showed using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer that cell metabolism OCR and ECAR was increased following treatment with melanocortin ligands (Zhang et al., 2018). The data shown in this chapter indicate that acute MTII treatment did not affect OCR and ECAR in high and physiological glucose U373 cell culture conditions. This observation implies that MCR activation may not rapidly influence cell metabolism. This can be further supported in the absence of changes in iATP and mitochondrial membrane potential following 15-minute MCR ligand pre-treatments in U373 cells. In contrast, under both glucose conditions, pre-treatment with MTII for five and twenty-four hours increased basal OCR and ECAR compared to Vehicle treated U373 cells, suggesting increases in mitochondrial respiration and glycolytic rate. Interestingly, five hours of 1nM MTII pre-treatment in high glucose cell culture conditions decreased basal ECAR compared to Vehicle treatment. Melanocortins are reported to affect glucose homeostasis (Hill & Faulkner, 2017). Published studies indicate that high glucose concentrations in astrocyte cell culture result in high glycogen storage (Abe et al., 2006; Staricha et al., 2020) and there is some evidence that MC4R regulates glucose homeostasis (de Souza Cordeiro et al., 2021; Rossi et al., 2011). Together, this may indicate that MCR activation reduced glycolysis and/or shifted astrocytes towards glycogen storage, restoring glucose homeostasis in astrocytes cultured in high glucose conditions. This observation raises the possibility that MCRs play a role in modulating astrocyte metabolism to regulate brain glucose homeostasis and body physiology and/or regulate hyperglycemia. However, further research is required to confirm this proposition, including mechanistic studies, dose-

response experiments, and genetic models to directly assess the involvement of MCRs in astrocyte metabolism in the context of brain glucose homeostasis.

When putting U373 cells under stress using the Mitochondrial Stress Test, MTII pre-treatment for five hours increased OCR at baseline and following the sequential addition of the mitochondrial function inhibitors, thus resulting in increases in all the calculated mitochondrial parameters. Notably, the ECAR increased concurrently with OCR in real-time, indicating that MCR activation potentially contributes to regulating metabolic homeostasis during stress. This observation raises the possibility that MCRs play a role in modulating astrocyte metabolism, particularly in the context of inflammation or cancer. Evidence indicates that oxidative damage increases ROS production when assessing bioenergetic function in response to oxidative stress using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer (Dranka et al., 2010, 2013). Ramirez et al demonstrated that NDP-MSH treatment prevented palmitic-induced ROS production in primary rat astrocytes. Moreover, Caruso et al. showed that MC4R activation by α -MSH in astrocytes reduced the inflammatory response by increasing bcl-2 (anti-apoptotic) and decreasing caspase-3 activity (an enzyme involved in apoptosis), promoting their survival (Caruso et al., 2007). Therefore, it is possible that when U373 cells were under stress during the Mitochondrial Stress Test, MTII pre-treatment attenuated ROS production, increased bcl-2 and reduced caspase-3 enzyme to maintain cell health and integrity (Caruso et al., 2007; Ramírez et al., 2019). However, I did not investigate ROS production or bcl-2 in my hands. The data observed with MTII was corroborated with the ligand Setmelanotide, demonstrating increased basal mitochondrial respiration and increased mitochondrial function during the Mitochondrial Stress Test following five hours of ligand pre-treatment in physiological cell culture conditions.

In the Glycolysis Stress Test, basal glycolysis and glycolytic rate remained unchanged following five-hour pre-treatments of MTII or Setmelanotide compared to Vehicle. However, it is worth noting that in response to MTII or Setmelanotide, basal ECAR levels increased in both the Mitochondrial Stress Test and basal metabolism experiments. This implies that in these studies, there is a shift in glycolysis despite no changes observed in basal glycolysis during the Glycolysis Stress Test. This is likely to be attributed to variations in

media composition based on the manufacturer's kit. In the Seahorse experiments measuring basal mitochondrial metabolism and in the Mitochondrial Stress Test assay, I used the XF DMEM (part of the seahorse assay) that is supplemented with 2.5mM sodium pyruvate, 2mM L-glutamine and 2.5mM glucose or 25mM glucose. In contrast to this, in the Glycolysis Stress Test assay, XF DMEM was supplemented with 2mM L-glutamine without glucose or sodium pyruvate; this is intended to bring down glycolytic basal levels to enable measurement of changes in glycolysis following glucose injection. The potential influence of MTII on U373 glycolytic activity is strengthened by the measured increase in extracellular L-lactate secretion after a five-hour MTII pre-treatment, which supports the observed ECAR increase in the Seahorse BioAnalyzer studies. Besides glucose metabolism via glycolysis, it is possible that changes in ECAR occurred due to the activity of the pentose phosphate pathway, as both pathways result in lactate production. Interestingly, it was recently reported that extracellular lactate accumulation activates the mitochondrial electron transport chain (ETC), leading to excessive mitochondrial ATP synthesis, suppression of glycolysis, and increased utilisation of pyruvate or alternative respiratory substrates (X. Cai et al., 2023). It was reported that lactate shifts ATP production to the mitochondria, activates the ETC without being metabolised, and lactate-induced activation increases pyruvate oxidation and lactate utilisation. It is possible that during the five-hour MTII pre-treatment, glycolytic activity in these cells was enhanced, resulting in excessive production of lactate, as I observed, leading to suppression of glycolysis in these cells, but not production of lactate. This may be supported by the increased ATP production observed from the inferred parameter during the Mitochondrial Stress Test; if cells were unable to generate ATP through glycolysis, they would have shifted to ATP production through the mitochondria instead. It is worth noting that mitochondrial-derived CO₂ can hydrate the extracellular medium, which leads to additional extracellular acidification besides that contributed by glycolysis. However, there were no changes in the inferred parameter measuring non-extracellular acidification rate during the Glycolysis Stress Test, ruling out this possibility and further validating that changes observed in basal ECAR levels were due to increased extracellular lactate levels. This may suggest that MCR activation increased glucose uptake and the conversion of

glucose to pyruvate to Acetyl-CoA (acetyl-coenzyme A) to enter the Krebs cycle, also known as the citric acid cycle or tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) and increased mitochondrial respiration. Future studies to investigate glycolytic rates under physiological conditions using the Glycolytic Rate Assay from Agilent could provide complementary information and shed further insight into the mechanisms of the glycolytic pathway following MCR pharmacological modulation in astrocytes. Using both assays together can provide a comprehensive understanding of astrocyte energy metabolism in response to MCR pharmacological modulation.

The mitochondrial membrane potential and iATP were assessed as complementary measures of cell metabolism at cell physiological glucose conditions. The TMRE Mitochondrial Membrane Potential Assay and the iATP assay can provide complementary information about mitochondrial function, but they measure different aspects of mitochondrial physiology compared with the Mitochondrial and Glycolysis Stress Tests from Agilent. The ATPlite assay measures total intracellular ATP (iATP), regardless of its source (mitochondrial or glycolytic), reflecting the overall energy status of the cell. In contrast, the Mitochondrial Stress Test allows for calculating ATP production linked to oxygen consumption rate (OCR) following oligomycin injection under stress conditions. Whereas the iATP assay and TMRE assay directly measures changes in iATP and mitochondrial membrane potential following melanocortin ligand pre-treatment under physiological conditions, not under cell stress. Therefore, these two assays are not directly comparable but provide some complementary information on astrocyte bioenergetics in different contexts.

The mitochondrial membrane potential is a key indicator of mitochondrial health and function. It drives the synthesis of ATP through oxidative phosphorylation. A high membrane potential indicates a strong proton gradient, while a low membrane potential suggests a disrupted gradient. Therefore, mitochondrial membrane potential is required for ATP production and decreases in mitochondrial membrane potential result in ATP depletion. Neither iATP nor mitochondrial membrane potential were changed following MTII or Setmelanotide pre-treatments. This corroborates the absence of a calculated change in coupling efficiency observed during the Mitochondrial Stress test. As

changes in mitochondrial membrane potential and iATP could occur rapidly, I additionally assessed changes in the TMRE assay after 15 minutes of ligand pre-treatment (to reflect on treatment time in signalling studies in Chapter 3) but did not observe any differences, agreeing with the five-hour pre-treatment data. This is further supported by the acute treatment of U373 cells with MCR ligands, which showed no change in basal OCR and ECAR, reinforcing that acute MCR pharmacological modulation does not impact astrocyte bioenergetics. The absence of changes in mitochondrial membrane potential treatments suggests that MCR ligands do not alter the integrity of the mitochondrial membrane and proton flow in astrocytes, maintaining cell health and function. In contrast, when astrocytes were subjected to mitochondrial stress, mitochondrial metabolism and ATP production (inferred) increased with both MTII and Setmelanotide, possibly as a mechanism to maintain cell integrity and health, or to meet energy demands under stress.

Overall, the absence of changes in basal OCR and ECAR following acute MCR ligand treatments, as well as the lack of alterations in mitochondrial membrane potential (TMRE uptake) and coupling efficiency (Mitochondrial Stress Test), suggests that MTII and Setmelanotide do not disrupt the fundamental bioenergetic properties of mitochondrial function in astrocytes.

Although this chapter discusses the observed changes in astrocyte metabolism, the overall understanding of the impact on astrocyte metabolic modulation downstream of MCRs remains unclear. New evidence suggests that astrocytes and lactate bioenergetics significantly impact brain function, although these studies do not specifically focus on MCRs. For example, lactate uptake by astrocytes has been shown to regulate orexin neuronal activity in the lateral hypothalamus, influencing the sleep-wake cycle (Braga et al., 2024).

Additionally, stress impairs astrocytic metabolic networks and synaptic plasticity by disrupting the lactate shuttle that astrocytes provide to neurons (Murphy-Royal et al., 2020). Interestingly, Neuro-2A cells treated with lactate demonstrated increased mitochondrial biogenesis, ATP levels, oxidative phosphorylation and mitochondrial membrane potential through the ERK1/2 pathway (Shang et al., 2023). In **Chapter 3**, I observed ERK1/2 phosphorylation in response to MTII pre-treatment in U373 cells, suggesting a potential link to

cellular metabolism modulation. Given the dynamic interplay of astrocytes within the brain, where they can re-uptake lactate, the L-lactate secretion following MTII treatment may be taken up by other astrocytes (or neurons). This could further increase ERK1/2 signalling in astrocytes, promoting enhanced mitochondrial function and lactate release during high energy demands in the brain (Braga et al., 2024; Murphy-Royal et al., 2020; Shang et al., 2023). This dynamic interplay suggests a complex network where ERK1/2 signalling, and lactate metabolism collaborate to support cellular and mitochondrial function in response to metabolic needs in the brain. In summary, while the precise mechanisms remain unclear, there is evidence suggesting that MTII treatment could modulate astrocyte metabolism through ERK1/2 signalling. This modulation might enhance mitochondrial function and lactate dynamics, supporting the brain's energy demands during high activity periods.

However, the mechanistic understanding of how MCR agonist treatment regulates astrocyte metabolism remains unclear. To shed light on this, I examined evidence of MCR modulation of cell metabolism in other cell models, as there are no direct mechanistic studies on how melanocortin ligands regulate astrocyte metabolism *in-vitro* (Tanaka et al., 2007; Chai et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2017; Xu, Yan et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2018). There is also evidence on the role of ERK1/2 in regulating cell metabolism and fate in non-glial cells (Choi & Kim, 2022; Haigh et al., 2020; Papa et al., 2019; Shin et al., 2015).

Mechanistically, ERK1/2 signalling downstream of MCRs in non-glial cells was involved in various metabolic pathways, including those mediated by AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1 α (AMP-activated protein kinase; silencing information regulator 2 related enzyme 1; peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ co-activator 1 α) or mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin) (Chai et al., 2010; Chen et al., 2018; Tanaka et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2017). The AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1 α pathway is known for its role in cellular energy sensing and mitochondrial regulation (Fernandez-Marcos & Auwerx, 2011; Han et al., 2020; Johri et al., 2013; Nijland et al., 2014). Activation of MC4R mediated by AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1 α promotes mitochondrial biogenesis and attenuates oxidative stress during mitochondrial dysfunction in the skeletal muscle of diabetic rats (Zhang et al., 2017). In rodent skeletal tissue, increased phosphorylation of AMPK and ACC is observed following MTII treatment (Tanaka et al., 2007).

Furthermore, mTOR signalling is another crucial pathway involved in cellular metabolism regulation. NDP-MSH treatment, which affects ERK1/2 phosphorylation, has enhanced insulin-stimulated mTOR phosphorylation in the neuronal MC4R expressing GT1-1 cell line (Chai et al., 2010). This suggests a potential interplay between ERK1/2 and mTOR pathways in metabolic regulation. Carniglia et al showed that pharmacological modulation of MC4R in rat astrocytes and microglia increased PPAR γ expression via the involvement of ERK1/2 signalling (Carniglia et al., 2013). PPAR γ is expressed in astrocytes known to play a role in regulating metabolic pathways, including mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation (Fernandez et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2019). The involvement of ERK1/2 signalling in modulating PPAR γ expression further strengthens the link between ERK1/2 activation and metabolic regulation. Collectively, this demonstrates an interlink between ERK1/2 and other metabolic pathways following pharmacological MCR ligand manipulation. Therefore, the observed ERK1/2 signalling and L-lactate secretion in response to MCR pharmacological ligand manipulation likely contributes to the modulation of astrocyte cell metabolism. This modulation may involve increased PPAR γ gene expression and potentially the activation of upstream effectors such as AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1 α or mTOR pathways. Additionally, ERK1/2 signalling may play a role in reducing ROS levels to maintain cellular health under conditions of mitochondrial stress. However, further investigation is needed to explain the precise mechanisms underlying these observations, including the expression/activity of mTOR and AMPK-SIRT1-PGC1 α , as well as ROS production. The intracellular mechanism(s) by which MCR ligands modulate cell metabolism remains unknown, and since cell metabolic networks consist of many branches and pathways, it is possible that changes in metabolism seen in astrocytes induced by MTII and Setmelanotide can further lead to metabolic pathway changes yet to be determined.

Additionally, future studies looking at the inhibition of ERK1/2 signalling may highlight whether the observed changes in astrocyte metabolism were partially mediated via ERK1/2. Finally, further studies exploring adding the MCR antagonist SHU9119 would be important to validate the MCR specificity of the observed metabolic effects, although these ligands have been extensively validated in other contexts (Chai et al., 2006, 2007; Hruby et al., 1995;

Kamermans et al., 2019; Schiöth et al., 1999; Sutton et al., 2005). My studies were limited to the U373 cancer cell line, and further studies are required with mouse primary cortical astrocytes to validate these findings. **Figure 5.6.4-1** summarises the findings of this chapter.

5.6.4 Conclusion

This chapter supports my hypothesis that MCR activation influences astrocyte metabolism, leading to changes in mitochondrial respiration, glycolytic activity, and L-lactate secretion.

Figure 5.6.4-1 Summary illustrating changes in metabolism in U373 astrogloma cells in response to MCR ligand modulation

The bold red arrows indicate increased OCR and ECAR. The red dashed line and question mark indicate potential changes in activity. Dashed line with an end indicates a possible inhibition of the pathway. The black dashed line and question mark indicate whether ERK1/2 is involved in astrocyte metabolism. Figure created in Biorender.

6 GENERAL DISCUSSION

In this chapter, I will summarise the main findings of the thesis. Then I will synthesise the findings and propose further studies to help address questions raised by my studies. I will highlight the limitations of the studies imposed by the methods and resource availability.

6.1 Overarching hypothesis

Melanocortin ligands acting on MCRs modulate astrocyte function.

6.2 Importance of Investigations and contribution to knowledge of this thesis

In **Chapter 3**, I aimed to clarify which MCRs are expressed on astrocytes and the downstream signalling pathways they activate. By examining the expression of all MCRs in astrocytes and assessing the activity of several downstream pathways in response to melanocortin ligands, this investigation enhanced our understanding of how these pathways may influence astrocytic function. This thesis adds to the published knowledge of MCR function, extending our understanding of their role in astrocytes. To date, related work has focused on the role of MC4R in astrocytes in the context of energy homeostasis and inflammation. Most published studies showed some expression of endogenous MCRs in astrocytes without comprehensively investigating the expression of all MCR sub-types. I addressed this knowledge gap in **Chapter 3** where I observed using PCR expression of MC1R, MC2R, MC3R, MC4R and MC5R in mouse primary astrocytes and MC1R to MC4R in human U373 astrogloma cells. Previously published studies focused on select downstream MC4R signalling pathways in astrocytes without investigating other known signalling pathways. Following evaluation of several signalling pathways, my studies presented in **Chapter 3** suggest that ERK1/2 signalling is the predominant downstream pathway activated in astrocytes cell models in culture following treatment with melanocortin ligands.

In **Chapter 4**, the focus was on examining the role of MCR ligands on astrocyte calcium and potassium ion dynamics, as these aspects had not been previously

investigated. This is significant because astrocytes modulate their function and, in turn, the central nervous system (CNS) via increases in intracellular calcium ion levels (iCa^{2+}) and potassium ion buffering. Prior to starting this work there was no published evidence of MCR-induced intracellular calcium changes in astrocytes beyond MC4R transfected cells. I began to address this knowledge gap in **Chapter 4**, however following treatment with MCR ligands I observed no changes in intracellular calcium levels in mouse primary astrocytes and human U373 astrocytoma cells, suggesting that changes in intracellular calcium ions made not be a key downstream effector in this context. The studies on the impact of melanocortin ligands on potassium ion dynamics were inclusive and further studies are required.

Chapter 5 investigated the effects of melanocortin ligands on cell metabolism in the human U373 astrogloma cell line, an area not previously explored in astrocytes. Understanding how MCR modulation influences cell metabolism can reveal how the melanocortin system may modulate astrocytic function to support neuronal activity and brain function, which may have significant implications for our understanding of the cellular basis by which the central melanocortin impacts neuroendocrine and other physiological functions. I addressed this knowledge gap where I observed increased metabolic activity in U373 astrogloma cells following treatment with MCR ligands.

In summary, the evidence I presented in **Chapters 3 and 5** established that there is endogenous *mc1r-mc4r* gene expression in human U373 astrogloma cells and mouse primary cortical astrocytes (*mc1r-mc5r*), and MCR agonist MTII pre-treatment increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation in human U373 cells, indicating ligand-induced receptor activity. MTII and Setmelanotide pre-treatment increased human U373 astrogloma cell metabolism. Combined these findings may have significant implications for our understanding of how melanocortin ligands impact CNS function via astrocytes. The overall findings are summarised in **Figure 6.2-1**. My observations of the expression of all MCRs in mouse primary cortical astrocytes and increased cell metabolism specifically in U373 astrogloma cell line expressing MC1R to MC4R represents a novel contribution to the field; although further assessments are required to investigate MC5R gene expression in U373 cells as my studies were limited to assessing the expression using one set of primers.

Figure 6.2-1 Simplified illustration of key findings generated from this thesis.

Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) were measured using the Seahorse BioAnalyzer. Red arrows indicate increased extracellular regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) signalling, OCR/ECAR and extracellular L-lactate. MTII and Setmelanotide are MCR synthetic agonists. Dashed arrow indicates findings of results with currently unknown cellular mechanisms. Diagram created using Biorender.

6.3 Perspectives on the role of MCRs on astrocytes in CNS function

The primary investigations and findings of this thesis were prompted by and led to several questions: Why are MCRs expressed in astrocytes, and how do melanocortin ligands acting on MCRs modulate astrocyte signalling and metabolism? How do ERK1/2 signalling and increased cell metabolism influence astrocyte function? Does this modulation impact overall brain function? While my results in this area led to new insights (see above), much remains underexplored. This section will speculate on the significance of the melanocortin system acting via astrocytes and ERK1/2 signalling in the broader context of the CNS.

To start this section, I would like to highlight that the MCRs, their interacting partners and their signalling pathways are complex and unpredictable, making them difficult to characterise as a whole and individually (Laiho and Murray, 2022). Yet, within our current knowledge, I will try to reflect on how my data, in the context of the broader literature, may inform us about the importance of MCRs acting via astrocytes on brain function.

6.3.1 Speculation on the physiological role of MCRs in astrocytes

This thesis presents evidence that genes for all MCR subtypes are expressed in astrocytes, highlighting the potential significance of these receptors in astrocyte function. The presence of all MCRs in astrocytes may suggest these cells can respond to a wide array of melanocortin ligands, potentially indicating a more intricate role for MCR signalling across neural cell types than previously recognised. MCR expression and function in astrocytes may vary depending on the brain region, as astrocyte morphology and functions differ between white and grey matter, but this would need to be further explored using neuroanatomical approaches. The roles of MCRs in various astrocyte populations are likely context-dependent, influenced by their location and subtype. In different brain regions, MCRs in astrocytes might regulate the blood-brain barrier (BBB) function or promote synapse formation (Araque et al., 2014; Poskanzer & Yuste, 2016). MCR activation in astrocytes may lead to proliferation and changes in morphology where they can send axonal projections to many brain areas, as supported with previous findings (Zohar & Salomon, 1992).

Knockdown of MC4R in hypothalamic astrocyte of mice increases brain inflammation, body weight, and food intake compared to control groups, suggesting the involvement (Eliason et al., 2022). This suggests that MCRs on astrocytes and may work alongside with the neuronal melanocortin system, to help regulate energy balance (Eliason et al., 2022). Astrocytes, through MCRs, may release gliotransmitters like Acyl-CoA-binding protein (ACBP), to activate proopiomelanocortin (POMC) neurons to regulate food intake and energy balance (Bouyakdan et al., 2019b). Published data indicates that MCR modulation may also be involved in the physiological link between nutritional state, height and puberty (Lam et al., 2021; Y. Zheng et al., 2023) and given recent evidence of a role of astrocytes in activity of the reproductive axis (Torres et al., 2024; Vanacker et al., 2021), melanocortin signalling via astrocytes may represent a novel mechanistic avenue to explore in future studies. Furthermore, alterations in astrocyte metabolism, such as those observed in this thesis in response to melanocortin ligands (**Chapter 5**), could impact synaptic efficacy,

plasticity, and overall neural network activity. For example, astrocyte metabolism/energy production has been shown to impact synaptic transmission in the context of physiological stress in mice (Murphy-Royal et al., 2020), which may be significant as the central melanocortin system is known to be a key regulator of the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) axis (Micioni Di Bonaventura et al., 2022). Additionally, the activation of MCRs is a promising target for new antidepressants (Markov et al., 2023; Micioni Di Bonaventura et al., 2022), as melanocortins help regulate the dysregulation of the HPA axis seen in depression. This dysregulation is linked to decreased BDNF levels, and since MCRs are involved in increasing BDNF expression (Caruso et al., 2012; Ramírez et al., 2015; Saba et al., 2019), melanocortin signalling in astrocytes may play a role in the regulation of depression.

In addition, astrocytes play a critical role in protecting neurons from oxidative stress and excitotoxicity and are key regulators of neuroinflammation (Colombo & Farina, 2016; Giovannoni & Quintana, 2020). Melanocortin peptides acting on MCRs also have anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties, suggesting that MCR activation in astrocytes could enhance their ability to mitigate damage and maintain neuronal health as previously evidenced (Cai et al., 2022; Caruso et al., 2007; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lau et al., 2021; Saba et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2022). This is further supported by published evidence that MCRs function in astrocytes can produce anti-inflammatory cytokines and reduce the production of pro-inflammatory mediators (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lasaga et al., 2008; Ramírez et al., 2019; Saba et al., 2019). Research from our lab has previously shown that changes in cellular metabolic function in astrocytes is critical for their inflammatory response (Robb, 2020), so the modulation of cellular metabolism in astrocytes following treatment with melanocortin ligands observed in this thesis (**Chapter 5**), may provide a cellular mechanistic basis for the impact of melanocortin ligands on CNS inflammation.

Together, these findings highlight the potential for multifaceted roles of MCRs in astrocytes and to impact brain function and overall physiology.

6.3.2 Theories on the impact of astrocyte ERK1/2 signalling downstream of MCRs

This thesis demonstrates that pharmacological stimulation of MCRs can modulate the ERK1/2 signalling pathway in astrocytes. While it remains unclear whether ERK1/2 signalling is directly involved in the changes in astrocyte function, it is known that melanocortins can modulate astrocyte function through ERK1/2-dependent and independent mechanisms. I will now speculate about the potential effects of MCR pharmacological activation on ERK1/2 signalling and its implications for modulating astrocyte and brain function.

ERK1/2, part of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway, is crucial for regulating various cellular processes, including proliferation, differentiation, and response to stress under both physiological and pathophysiological conditions (Cargnello & Roux, 2011; Orlandi et al., 2024; Wei & Liu, 2002; Wortzel & Seger, 2011). ERK1/2 activation has several downstream effects. Firstly, it can lead to changes in gene expression, as ERK1/2 signalling is known to regulate the activity of various transcription factors in physiological and pathophysiological conditions (Caruso et al., 2012; Kamermans et al., 2019; Mebratu & Tesfaigzi, 2009; Rodrigues et al., 2012; Sarkar et al., 2002; Wu et al., 2019; C. H. Yu et al., 2018). These changes in gene expression may alter astrocytic function, potentially enhancing their ability to support neurons through the release of neurotrophic factors, modulation of synaptic activity, and maintenance of extracellular ion balance. This is supported by published evidence that c-FOS and BDNF levels are increased from astrocytes following MCR activation, promoting neuronal survival (Ramírez et al., 2015, 2019). cFOS, is expressed in astrocytes, and is dependent on ERK and RSK activation (R.-H. Chen et al., 1992; R. H. Chen et al., 1993; Mebratu & Tesfaigzi, 2009; Murphy et al., 2002). Its activity is dependent on many conditions not limited to proliferation, differentiation, repair, inflammation, growth, damage, and plasticity (Cruz-Mendoza et al., 2022). Together these data suggesting melanocortin ligands acting via MCRs on astrocytes may increase cFOS and BDNF activity through ERK1/2 signalling to support brain function.

More so, it is possible that ERK1/2 signalling results in astrocyte proliferation and differentiation to support brain function (Zohar & Salomon, 1992).

Therefore, I speculate that MCRs and ERK1/2 signalling in astrocytes support a broader role in contributing to the overall function of the CNS. This is evidenced by MCR mutations and disruptions in ERK1/2 signalling being implicated in various diseases such as melanoma (Herraiz et al., 2009; Inamdar et al., 2010), neuropathic pain (He & Tao, 2014; Mo & Tao, 2013), and obesity (Brouwers et al., 2021). For example, mutations in MCRs have been linked to obesity, highlighting their role in energy homeostasis and metabolic regulation. Similarly, dysregulation of ERK1/2 signalling pathways is associated with chronic pain conditions due to their role in neuronal plasticity and inflammation (Fatima et al., 2022; Yeo et al., 2021). This evidence highlights the significance of MCRs and ERK1/2 signalling in maintaining CNS health and function. With this body of evidence, I propose that MCRs may modulate astrocytic function differently depending on whole body homeostasis and brain physiology. Again, further supported with MC4R knockdown in astrocytes contributing to inflammation and obesity (Eliason et al., 2022). Collectively, these data, along with my findings on the expression of MCRs and ERK1/2 signalling, emphasise the potential importance of MCRs and their signalling pathways in the brain. However, it is important to note that this conclusion is based on current knowledge and remains speculative, as I have not presented direct evidence to support this theory beyond the existing body of literature that informs such a proposition.

6.3.3 Cellular basis of astrocyte metabolic modulation by melanocortin ligands

Under physiological conditions, the modulation of ERK1/2 signalling and metabolism by MCRs in astrocytes (**Chapter 3 and 5**) may support several essential brain functions. Enhanced astrocytic metabolism ensures a steady supply of energy to neurons, facilitating proper synaptic function and plasticity (Bonvento & Bolaños, 2021). Enhanced ERK1/2 signalling in response to MCR activation may upregulate key metabolic enzymes and transporters, leading to increased glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation. My data (**Chapter 5**) suggest that the activation of MCRs by melanocortin ligands modulates U373 astrogloma cell metabolism, as evidenced by changes in oxygen consumption rate (OCR), extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) and increased L-lactate secretion. Whether this is directly mediated by ERK1/2 activity remains in

question. These observed changes indicate a shift in mitochondrial function and glycolytic activity, respectively. This finding is significant because astrocytes play a crucial role in supporting neuronal function and overall brain metabolism (Allaman et al., 2011; Bélanger et al., 2011; Marina et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2023). Astrocytes are central to brain energy metabolism, providing neurons with substrates such as lactate (Magistretti & Allaman, 2018). MCR activation in astrocytes may modulate glucose uptake, glycogen storage, and lactate production, thereby supporting neuronal energy requirements, including those related to circadian rhythms and overall brain metabolism (Braga et al., 2024; Clasadonte et al., 2017; Murphy-Royal et al., 2020). It is possible that enhanced astrocyte metabolism could impact neuronal energy supply, synaptic function, and neuroprotection. MCR expression and function in astrocytes might help regulate astrocytic metabolism in response to metabolic demands or hormonal signals. This could influence overall brain energy dynamics, especially during periods of high demand, such as learning, physiological/psychological stress or recovery from injury.

Based on my findings and the existing body of evidence, I propose that MCR signalling modulates metabolic shifts in astrocytes to meet brain energy demands, particularly in response to changes in neuronal activity. By regulating astrocytic metabolism, MCRs help ensure that neurons receive sufficient energy substrates, such as L-lactate, which is essential for sustaining synaptic transmission and overall brain function. Additionally, MCRs may play a role in maintaining the BBB integrity (Banks & Kastin, 1995; Lisak & Benjamins, 2017; Wu et al., 2019) through ERK1/2-mediated signalling pathways. Astrocytes are crucial for BBB maintenance, and their ability to respond to metabolic and signalling cues via MCRs helps protect the brain from harmful substances and maintain homeostasis (Manu et al., 2023).

Although I did not observe changes in astrocyte iCa^{2+} ion levels in response to melanocortin ligands, this may be due to limitations in the experimental approaches used, it is possible that MCR-induced increases in iCa^{2+} ion levels to modulate astrocytic function and support the broader CNS. This speculation is based on well-established knowledge that astrocytes typically elevate their iCa^{2+} ion levels upon activation (Scemes, 2000; Verkhratsky, Rodríguez and

Parpura, 2012; Khakh and Mccarthy, 2015). Additionally, existing evidence indicates that MC4R stimulation in astrocytes increases BDNF levels, where, in turn, BDNF in astrocytes has been shown to increase iCa^{2+} ion levels (Caruso et al., 2012; Climent et al., 2000; Ramírez et al., 2015). Given that MCR modulation affects BDNF and iCa^{2+} levels in both astrocytes and non-glia cells (Berger, 1986; Buffey et al., 1992; Caruso et al., 2012; Climent et al., 2000; Jain et al., 2018; Kim et al., 1997; Konda et al., 1994; Kumar et al., 2021; Langouche et al., 2001; Mountjoy et al., 2001; Newman et al., 2006; Ramírez et al., 2015; Roudbaraki et al., 1999; Woodcock, 1989). I propose that metabolic changes in astrocytes lead to increased iCa^{2+} levels. Nonetheless, I also propose that astrocytes might not increase their iCa^{2+} levels in response to MCR modulation, although I have not ruled out the possibility that they could do so in response to MCR ligand treatment, which may not have been detected using the method used in this thesis. Therefore, to verify this and explore these theories further, first, it would be necessary to measure astrocyte changes in iCa^{2+} (using different approaches) and BDNF levels in response to MCR ligands. This could provide valuable insights into the proposed cellular mechanism and determine whether astrocytes indeed increase their iCa^{2+} ion levels to support neuronal activity and regulate brain function.

6.3.4 Potential impact of melanocortin ligands acting via astrocytes on brain function in pathophysiological conditions

Although this thesis does not focus on pathophysiological models, this discussion will highlight the role of MCRs in such conditions. Beyond their roles in normal physiology alterations CNS, MCRs and ERK1/2 signalling may also contribute to pathology. Dysregulation of MCR signalling is implicated in obesity, metabolic disorders, and neurodegenerative diseases (Bouyakdan et al., 2019; Brouwers et al., 2021; A. Chen et al., 2000; Eliason et al., 2022; Fatima et al., 2022; He & Tao, 2014; Herraiz et al., 2009; Inamdar et al., 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Mo & Tao, 2013; Orlandi et al., 2024; Pasqualetti et al., 2018; Vaglini et al., 2018; Wong K & N, 1997; Wu et al., 2019; Weilin Xu et al., 2020; Yeo et al., 2021). My findings combined with the published literature

suggest that targeting MCRs in astrocytes could be a novel therapeutic strategy for these conditions. Astrocytes are key players in the brain's immune response (Farina et al., 2007; Giovannoni & Quintana, 2020). The expression of multiple MCR subtypes in astrocytes (**Chapter 3**) alongside the data indicating metabolic regulation of astrocyte function by melanocortin ligands (**Chapter 5**) suggests that melanocortin signalling could modulate astrocytic responses to inflammation and injury via immunometabolic pathways. This aligns with the known anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory roles of melanocortins (Caruso et al., 2013; Catania, 2008; Giuliani, Bitto, et al., 2014), potentially contributing to neuroprotection and the resolution of neuroinflammation. In pathological conditions such as neuroinflammation, neurodegeneration, and metabolic disorders, the role of MCRs in astrocytes becomes increasingly significant. Dysregulation of ERK1/2 signalling and metabolic pathways in astrocytes can contribute to disease progression. For instance, in neuroinflammatory conditions, excessive activation of ERK1/2 can lead to the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, exacerbating neuronal damage. This is evidence in cerebral ischemia models, where melanocortin ligands acting on MCRs reduce the activation of the MAPK pathway, including ERK1/2, and increase Bcl-2 (an anti-apoptotic protein) expression, promoting the survival of brain cells by inhibiting proinflammatory cytokines (Fu et al., 2020; Giuliani et al., 2006; Yu et al., 2022). Conversely, in the context of cancer, inhibition of ERK1/2 and Akt phosphorylation with the selective antagonist ML00253764 has demonstrated anti-cancer effects *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*. This occurs through antiproliferative and proapoptotic mechanisms via MC1R and MC4R in melanoma and glioblastoma cells (Vaglini et al., 2018; Orlandi et al., 2024).

These contrasting effects highlight the context-dependent roles of MCRs and ERK1/2 signalling. In neurodegenerative conditions, MCR activation and ERK1/2 signalling support cell survival and neuroprotection, whereas in cancer, inhibiting these pathways can suppress tumour growth and promote apoptosis. This suggests that the therapeutic targeting of MCRs and ERK1/2 must be tailored to the specific pathological context, considering the dual roles these pathways can play in different diseases.

Given that astrocytes play a role in synapse formation, maintenance, and plasticity, MCR signalling could influence learning and memory processes. For instance, MC4R signalling has been linked to synaptic plasticity and cognitive functions in several neuropathic disease mouse models, potentially impacting behaviour and cognitive functions through astrocytic involvement (Giuliani et al., 2006, 2015; Giuliani, Bitto, et al., 2014; Giuliani, Galantucci, et al., 2014; Shen et al., 2016). This can further be supported with evidence showing that aged brains express less MCRs, correlating with age-related decline of cognitive functions, further strengthening the proposition that MCRs are involved in cognitive function via astrocytic modulation (Zhou et al., 2021). Treatment with MC4R agonists for MC3R/MC4R mutations induces changes in skin and hair pigmentation in patients with leptin-melanocortin pathway mutations (Kanti et al., 2021). This is possibly due to off-target effects of the ligand acting on MC1R. Published studies support this, showing that activation of MC1R leads to increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation, which in turn elevates the expression of genes involved in melanin synthesis promoting pigmentation (Herraiz et al., 2009, 2011). MC4R gene polymorphisms are associated with the risk of glioblastoma and glioblastoma patients with MC4R polymorphisms have a shorter life span (Pasqualetti et al., 2018). The therapeutic modulation of MCRs offers a potential strategy to mitigate these effects. By targeting MCRs, it may be possible to restore normal ERK1/2 signalling and metabolic function in astrocytes, thereby reducing inflammation and supporting neuronal survival. Additionally, in conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, where glucose metabolism is impaired, enhancing astrocytic metabolism through MCR activation could improve energy supply to neurons and slow disease progression. Several studies support this by demonstrating that MCR modulation by melanocortin ligands in astrocytes provides anti-inflammatory properties and neuroprotection through various mechanisms. These include PI3K signalling, increased levels of BDNF, activation of p90 ribosomal S6 kinase 2 (RSK) and the proto-oncogene cFOS, enhanced PPAR- γ activity, and reduced levels of ROS and inflammatory cytokines (Carniglia et al., 2013; Caruso et al., 2007, 2010; Kamermans et al., 2019; Lasaga et al., 2008; Ramírez et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2009, 2012; Saba et al., 2019; Vaglini et al., 2018; Wong K & N, 1997; Xu et al., 2020). Although I was unable to see

changes in iCa^{2+} ion levels, MCR activation in astrocytes may have increased iCa^{2+} ion levels to modulate astrocytes function and support the wider CNS in both physiological and pathophysiological environments (Climent et al., 2000).

Overall, with the known melanocortin immunomodulatory and neuroprotective effects, and the expression of MC1R in the brain, immune cells, and peripheral tissue, this may suggest that both peripheral and central forms of MC1R might impact dopaminergic neurons in neurological disorders, and MC1R attenuates brain injuries, inflammation, and neuropathic pain. Understanding how MCR modulation affects astrocyte function could lead to new insights into the pathogenesis of these diseases and the development of astrocyte-specific interventions.

6.3.5 Conclusion of Chapter 6

The findings of this thesis highlight the role of melanocortin ligands in modulating ERK1/2 signalling and metabolism in astrocytes. These processes are crucial for maintaining brain function under both physiological and pathophysiological conditions. Understanding how MCRs influence these pathways provides valuable insights into potential therapeutic targets for a range of neurological disorders.

Based on my data and the published literature, I propose a model below for how MCRs and their ligands may modulate astrocyte function to regulate central nervous system (CNS) homeostasis, which may in turn impact systemic physiology (**Figure 6.3.5-1**).

Figure 6.3.5-1 Hypothetical model proposed on how MCRs modulate astrocyte function influencing brain function in physiological and pathological conditions

This figure speculates how MCR activation by melanocortin agonists MTII/Setmelanotide may impact astrocyte function. The numbers explain the flow of this theory and the text in bold red highlight the findings of this thesis. (1) For experimental purposes, I used MTII or Setmelanotide that bind to MCRs (except MC2R) in the central nervous system (CNS) and increase ERK1/2 phosphorylation (2). ERK1/2 signalling may then directly or indirectly impact cell metabolism, increasing mitochondrial respiration measured as oxygen consumption rate (OCR), and glycolytic activity measured as extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) (3), extracellular L-lactate is also increased and released from astrocytes which may act on neurons (4). ERK1/2 signalling may also impact and increase expression of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma (PPAR-γ), c-FOS and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (5), which may then result in increased anti-inflammatory properties, neuroprotection, metabolic regulation, and brain/energy homeostasis (6) in the CNS. Dashed black lines indicate potential involvement in the activity and impact on overall brain function (thick bold black dashed line). The red arrow in bold indicates increased activity of astrocyte metabolism.

6.4 General limitations

While this thesis has provided valuable insights into the role of melanocortin receptor (MCR) signalling in astrocytes, several overarching limitations must be acknowledged. These limitations not only contextualise the findings but also highlight opportunities for future research to address gaps and refine methodologies.

1. Use of *in-vitro* models

The studies were conducted using *in vitro* models, specifically the U373 astroglioma cancer cell line and primary cortical astrocytes cultured in two-dimensional (2D) environments. While these models provided controlled systems to explore astrocyte function, they lack the complexity of an intact three-dimensional (3D) biological system, where interactions with neurons, microglia, and other cells are critical. This limitation underscores the need for future studies employing 3D culture systems or brain slice preparations, which can better replicate the *in vivo* environment and provide insights into cellular crosstalk and network dynamics.

2. Cancer-derived cell line

The use of U373 cells, a glioblastoma-derived cell line, introduced additional challenges. While these cells share several properties with long-term cultured primary astrocytes (Volkandt et al., 2002), their cancerous origin means they exhibit altered genetic and metabolic profiles, potentially limiting their physiological relevance. Future research should incorporate primary astrocytes from mature animals or iPSC-derived astrocytes to ensure findings reflect normal astrocytic metabolism and signalling. Moreover, understanding the differences between cancerous and non-cancerous astrocytes may provide translational insights, particularly in the context of cancer-related astrocytic functions.

3. 2D culture limitations

Two-dimensional culture systems limit the ability to model the spatial and functional complexity of astrocytes *in vivo*, which may have impacted the signalling and metabolic responses observed. Incorporating 3D cultures or co-

culture systems with neurons and microglia in future studies would help address this limitation by providing a more representative microenvironment.

4. Variability in cell responses

Experimental outcomes were influenced by factors such as media composition, glucose concentration, and cell passage number, which may have contributed to variations in signalling and metabolic responses. While such challenges are inherent in cell culture studies, future research could further standardize these conditions and/or use genetically modified cell lines, such as MCR-knockout astrocytes, to pinpoint receptor-specific effects.

5. Proxy measurements of metabolism

The reliance on Seahorse BioAnalyzer-derived parameters, such as oxygen consumption rate (OCR) and extracellular acidification rate (ECAR), provided valuable insights into mitochondrial and glycolytic function. However, these measures are indirect and do not fully elucidate the underlying metabolic pathways (Gu et al., 2021; Mayberry et al., 2024). Complementary approaches, such as isotopic tracing of metabolic substrates, detailed analysis of glucose transporters (e.g., GLUT1), and assessment of other metabolic intermediates (e.g., pyruvate, fatty acids), could further unravel the mechanisms driving the metabolic changes observed.

6. Limited focus on endogenous ligands and reactive astrocytes

The studies primarily used synthetic ligands, such as MTII and Setmelanotide, to probe MCR function. While effective, endogenous ligands like α -MSH may provide more physiologically relevant insights. Additionally, the experiments were limited to “healthy” astrocytes, leaving the role of MCRs in reactive astrocytes largely unexplored. Future studies could investigate the effects of endogenous ligands and examine how MCR signalling influences astrocytes during pathological states, such as neuroinflammation or neurodegeneration.

6.5 Future directions

Building on the limitations outlined above, future research can address these challenges by:

1. Physiologically relevant models:

- Employing 3D culture systems or brain slice preparations to investigate astrocyte-neuron interactions in a more representative environment.
- Using primary astrocytes from mature animals or iPSC-derived astrocytes to enhance physiological relevance.

2. Exploring mechanisms:

- Investigating additional metabolic pathways (e.g., AMPK, mTOR) and using advanced methods such as glutamate sensors or gliotransmitter assays to assess astrocyte function.

3. *In-vivo* studies:

- Using *in-vivo* imaging or micro dialysis to study astrocytic MCR function and gliotransmitter release in live animals.

4. Specific ligand studies:

- Developing selective MCR subtype ligands to isolate receptor-specific effects and assess their therapeutic potential.

5. Pathophysiological relevance:

- Investigating MCR function in reactive astrocytes and exploring implications in neurodegenerative or metabolic diseases.

By addressing the limitations, future studies can build on the findings of this thesis, advancing our understanding of MCR function in astrocytes and its broader implications for CNS physiology and pathology.

6.6 Summary of key findings from the thesis

- MC1R-MC4R are expressed in the human U373 astroglioma cell line and MC1R-MC5R on neonatal mouse primary cortical astrocytes, suggesting roles for astrocytes in mediating the effects of melanocortin ligands in the CNS.
- Pre-treatment with the MCR agonist MTII increased ERK1/2 signalling, and the antagonist SHU9119 inhibited this effect in the human U73 astroglioma cell line. This suggests that this pathway is important for mediating astrocyte downstream signalling in response to pharmacological treatment with melanocortin ligand.
- Human U373 astroglioma cell metabolism and extracellular L-lactate production are regulated by melanocortin ligands, which may provide a mechanistic basis but which MCR activation in astrocytes may impact neuronal-glia communication and/or brain homeostasis.

In summary, the expression of MCRs in astrocytes likely plays a significant role in regulating brain metabolism, neuroinflammation, synaptic function, and overall brain health. These receptors may enable astrocytes to respond to hormonal signals by altering their metabolism to meet the metabolic demands of local neuronal networks, providing trophic support to neurons and maintaining overall brain and body homeostasis.

7 APPENDICES

7.1 Representative full immunoblots from Chapter 3

Figure number reflects the position in the main document of **Chapter 3**.

Figure 3.5.3-1 Vehicle, MTII (0.1nM – 100nM) and ATP (100µM) treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.4-1 Vehicle, MTII (1nM), SHU9119 (1µM), (SHU9119 1µM / MTII 1nM) and ATP treatment

Figure 3.5.5-1 Vehicle and MTII treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.6-1 (A) Vehicle and 8 Bromo (100 μ M) treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.6-1 (C) Vehicle and 8 Bromo (100 μ M) time course treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.6-1 (F) Vehicle and m-3M3FBS treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.7-1 Vehicle, MTII and m-3M3FBS treatment on U373 cells astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.8-1 Vehicle and Setmelanotide (0.1nM – 100nM) treatment on human U373 astroglioma cells

Figure 3.5.13-1 Vehicle and MTII (0.1nM – 100nM) treatment on mouse cortical astrocytes

-CTRL (U0126; ERK1/2 inhibitor) and +CTRL (TPA; ERK1/2 activator) were antibodies sent from the supplier for validation

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